

The Chronic Impact of Rare Earth Elements on Biological Species within an Aquatic Benthic-Pelagic Ecosystem

Chantal Kimberley Eline van Drimmelen

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Supervisors Prof. Dr. Susanne Heise
 Prof. Dr. Andrew S. Hursthouse

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DECLARATION STATEMENT

I hereby declare that I have authored this thesis independently, that I have not used other than the declared sources and resources, and that I have explicitly marked all material, which has been quoted either literally or by content from the used sources. The work in this thesis has not been submitted for a DBA, DProf, EngD, PhD or comparable academic award in any university or other institution apart from the University of the West of Scotland and the Hamburg University of Applied Science.

Furthermore, it must be noted that some parts of this thesis are included in submitted papers (co-)authored by myself.

Hamburg, 29 February 2024

Personal details withheld.

Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen

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Hou doe,
Chanti

INDEX OF ABBREVIATIONS

μXRF	Micro-X-ray fluorescence
Ca	Calcium
Cd	Cadmium
Ce	Cerium
Cu	Copper
DCP	3,5-dichlorophenol
DOM	Dissolved organic matter
Dy	Dysprosium
EC _x	Maximal effective concentration
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
Er	Erbium
Eu	Europium
FWC	Fresh weight change
Ga	Gallium
Gd	Gadolinium
GLF	Growth-limiting function
Ho	Holmium
HREE	Heavy Rare Earth Element
ICP-MS	Inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy
ISO	International guideline standards (medium)
ISO-G1P	International guideline standards medium with inorganic phosphate (α-glucose 1-phosphate)
La	Lanthanum
LC _x	Lethal concentration
Ln	Lanthanides
LoD	Limit of Detection
LPO	Lipid peroxidation
LREE	Light Rare Earth Element
Lu	Lutetium
MHSM	Modified high salt medium
Mo	Molybdenum
MOPS	Acide-3-(N-morpholono)propane sulfonic acid
MREE	Middle Rare Earth Elements
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
Nd	Neodymium
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development standards
PAM	Pulse-amplitude-modulated chlorophyll fluorometer
Pb	Lead
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PETG	Polyethylene terephthalate glycol
P _i	Inorganic phosphate
Pm	Promethium
PO ₄ ³⁻	Phosphate
Pr	Praseodymium

INDEX OF ABBREVIATIONS

PSII	Photosystem II
Pt	Platinum
REE	Rare Earth Elements
Sc	Scandium
SI	Supplementary Information
Sm	Samarium
Tb	Terbium
TCE	Technology Critical Elements
Tm	Thulium
TXRF	Total reflection X-ray fluorescence spectrometry
Y	Yttrium
Y(II)	Effective quantum yield of PSII in fluorescence
Yb	Ytterbium

“Not all those who wander are lost”

J.R.R. Tolkien, *The Fellowship of the Ring*

“I confess that I have been as blind as a mole,

but it is better to learn wisdom late than never to learn it at all.”

Sherlock Holmes, *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes* by Arthur Conan Doyle

To my family and all my loved ones

ABSTRACT

Since rare earth elements (REE) are increasingly used in society, they can enter the aquatic environment through a variety of pathways. Their potential adverse ecotoxicological effects on the aquatic food web have made REE a concern as emerging contaminants. The REE attached to sediments and fine organic particle matter are considered not to be bioavailable to aquatic organisms in the water column. However, as part of benthic-pelagic coupling, REE can become bioavailable when organisms consume sediment particles, when chemical equilibria are disrupted, or when environmental conditions change. The aim of this thesis was to investigate the chronic effects of rare earth elements on the aquatic benthic-pelagic ecosystem, to better understand the toxicity on individual aquatic invertebrates and communities. To achieve this, single-species, multi-species, and modeling tools were applied to identify the chronic ecotoxicological effects of benthic-pelagic coupling of lanthanum (La) and gadolinium (Gd) on multiple aquatic organisms. The results demonstrated the significance of researching the impact of REE contamination in both the sediment and water phase. Low concentrations of REE over a long period of time should not be considered trivial, and contaminated sediment leads to active avoidance by pelagic invertebrates. The results also showed that strong partitioning of REE with the sediment can still cause adverse effects to multiple species in sediment-water systems. Acute and chronic exposure in both the water and sediment phase should be taken into account, as well as the special characteristics of REE that make it complex to fully comprehend the mechanisms underlying the negative effects – many of which are still unknown. This thesis presents research on the possible long-term impacts of REE concentrations on the aquatic benthic-pelagic ecosystem. It also discusses the need to consider different experimental systems, test species, and exposure durations in order to assess the risk of REE toxicity on the aquatic community.

CHAPTER 1

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1. Critical and in demand: Rare Earth Elements as emerging contaminants

Rare Earth Elements (REE) are emerging contaminants that have become a concern for their potential ecotoxicological adverse effects in aquatic ecosystems. Discovered in 1787 in the form of a strange black rock by a miner in Ytterby, Sweden, that drew the attention of a Swedish Army Lieutenant Karl Arrhenius. He sent the sample to the Finnish chemist Johann Gadolin who was able isolate impure yttrium oxide in 1794 (Fernandez, 2017; Klinger, 2015). The REE were presumed to be scarce as they had not been found anywhere else until then. However, we come into contact with REE in our daily life. The name “rare” in REE is now known to be misleading as they are found in similar abundance to more commonly known metals like lead and copper (Ce (cerium) $60 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, Y (yttrium) $20 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, and La (lanthanum) $30 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$; compared to lead: $10 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ and copper: $55 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) (Chen, Chen and Chen, 2022). The abundance of REE follows the Oddo-Harkins rule (Oddo, 1914; Harkins, 1917), where elements with an even atomic number show greater abundance compared to those with an odd atomic number (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014). However, their name is correct in the fact that the REE are not as well-known as other elements. Terms such as rare earth metals, rare earth oxides, lanthanoids, and lanthanides (Ln) might also be applied for REE depending on the context and the authors. In this thesis will the term REE primarily be used.

The REE consist of the 15 lanthanides (Ln), ranging from lanthanum ($_{57}\text{La}$) to Lutetium ($_{71}\text{Lu}$), and the elements scandium ($_{21}\text{Sc}$) and yttrium ($_{39}\text{Y}$) (Figure 1-1). Due to the shared number of chemical characteristics these minerals are often found together in large deposits (Brown *et al.*, 1990). REE can be divided into two groups: 1) light rare earth elements (LREE) with an atomic weight ≤ 153 and an effective radius of more than 95 pm (La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, and Eu), and 2) heavy rare earth elements (HREE) with an atomic weight ≥ 154 and effective radius less than 95 pm (Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, Lu, and Y) (Tyler, 2004; Wells and Wells, 2012). Some studies also consider a third class of middle REE (MREE), based on intermediate mean atomic mass and ionic radius, but this classification is not very well defined (Tyler, 2004; Anastopoulos, Bhatnagar and Lima, 2016; Chen, Chen and Chen, 2022). The REE group shows the greatest similarities between the elements within, compared to elements outside of this group. They have unique structural, physical, and chemical properties (e.g., stable outer shell, electropositive, lanthanide contraction), and are generally an isolated in oxidation state of +3 (Brown *et al.*, 1990; Dang *et al.*, 2021; Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018). For Ce and Eu, the +4 and +2 oxidation states are also commonly observed (Ramos *et al.*, 2016; Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018). These similar properties are exhibited throughout the series with two electrons occupying each 4f-orbital in the f subshells for the lanthanides (Malhotra *et al.*, 2020; Brown *et al.*, 1990).

CHAPTER 1

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
1 H																	2 He
3 Li	4 Be											5 B	6 C	7 N	8 O	9 F	10 Ne
11 Na	12 Mg											13 Al	14 Si	15 P	16 S	17 Cl	18 Ar
19 K	20 Ca	21 Sc	22 Ti	23 V	24 Cr	25 Mn	26 Fe	27 Co	28 Ni	29 Cu	30 Zn	31 Ga	32 Ge	33 As	34 Se	35 Br	36 Kr
37 Rb	38 Sr	39 Y	40 Zr	41 Nb	42 Mo	43 Tc	44 Ru	45 Rh	46 Pd	47 Ag	48 Cd	49 In	50 Sn	51 Sb	52 Te	53 I	54 Xe
55 Cs	56 Ba	57 La	72 Hf	73 Ta	74 W	75 Re	76 Os	77 Ir	78 Pt	79 Au	80 Hg	81 Tl	82 Pb	83 Bi	84 Po	85 At	86 Rn
87 Fr	88 Ra	89 Ac	104 Rf	105 Db	106 Sg	107 Bh	108 Hs	109 Mt	110 Ds	111 Rg	112 Cn	113 Nh	114 Fl	115 Mc	116 Lv	117 Ts	118 Og
			58 Ce	59 Pr	60 Nd	61 Pm	62 Sm	63 Eu	64 Gd	65 Tb	66 Dy	67 Ho	68 Er	69 Tm	70 Yb	71 Lu	
			90 Th	91 Pa	92 U	93 Np	94 Pu	95 Am	96 Cm	97 Bk	98 Cf	99 Es	100 Fm	101 Md	102 No	103 Lr	

Figure 1-1 The Periodic Table with in bold the rare earth elements in bold: in blue the lanthanides and in green scandium and yttrium. Designed by Chantal van Drimmelen

These unique properties have made the REE crucial for the continuous innovation of several critical industrial sectors in the modern world (e.g., electronics, the automotive industry, healthcare, defense, renewable energy sources, and communication technologies) (Dang *et al.*, 2021). There are five industry sectors where the REE are critical for continued development (Figure 1-2): 1) high-tech products (e.g., computers, screen displays, lasers, medical X-ray), 2) low-carbon economy or decarbonized economy (e.g., permanent magnets, electrical cars, hybrid cars, batteries, wind turbines), 3) agriculture (fertilizer and feed additives), 4) environmental applications (e.g., water treatment and ecological restoration), and 5) other applications (e.g., cracking of crude petroleum, glass production) (Dang *et al.*, 2021; Sager and Wiche, 2024). As REE have risen in global importance, the growing demand for REE has led to an increased interest in the mining, extraction, and recycling of these metals.

Between 2000 and 2020 the global demand for REE rapidly increased from 75,500 tons to 170,000 tons (Goodenough, Wall and Merriman, 2018). There are very few substitutes in technical applications for REE and these elements are not recycled in large quantities, raising many questions and concerns about the future availability of REE (Malhotra *et al.*, 2020; Dang *et al.*, 2021). Currently China is the dominant supplier of rare earth raw materials with ± 95% of the global REE production (Sager and Wiche, 2024; Chen,

Chen and Chen, 2022; Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018). Which has resulted in more than 300 abandoned mines in Ganzhou by 2010 (Chen, Chen and Chen, 2022). The shortage of and monopoly on the sources of REE, the unsustainability of mines, and the increased need for these elements in various technologies and economies has led to REE being classified as critical raw materials or so-called Technology Critical Elements (TCE) (Chen, Chen and Chen, 2022; Cobelo-García *et al.*, 2015).

Natural background levels for REE, due to geological processes (e.g., mineral deposits, erosion and weathering mobilization, and volcanic activity) range between $<0.002 - 0.064 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in stream waters and $0.38 - 66.6 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ in stream sediments (Piarulli *et al.*, 2021; Salminen *et al.*, 2005). However, the increased demand for these elements has led to anthropogenic contamination of water, soil, and sediments (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014). There are currently no regulatory restrictions for the discharge of REE, such as drinking water standards, in place for any international health organization (Balaram, 2019). Thus, next to being TCE, REE are now also recognized as emerging contaminants, and it has become very important to address their environmental fate and the potential adverse effects for both humans and the environment.

Figure 1-2 Conceptual representation of REE applications, sources of pollution, and their transfer to aquatic ecosystems. Modified from A. Kokeb Alemu (PANORAMA Summer school, June 2022) based on Gwenzi *et al.* (2018), Piarulli *et al.* (2021), and Dang *et al.* (2021).

1.2. Toxic or not?: Potential effects of REE on the aquatic environment

Ecotoxicology is the study of the potential effects of contaminants and stressors on individual organisms, populations, communities, and ecosystems. It can be used to support regulatory decisions through identifying and assessing contamination in ecosystems (Schmitt-Jansen *et al.*, 2008). It deals with the transfer of contaminants in air, water, soil, and sediment, and through food chains (Walker *et al.*, 2012). Contaminants are defined as a substance occurring above normal levels being present where they should not be (Chapman, 2001). A pollutant is a contaminant, but not all contaminants are pollutants as pollution is a result of adverse biological effects in the environment by the contaminant (Chapman, 2001). A contaminant (e.g., metal) is considered to be toxic when the rate of uptake exceeds the detoxification and excretion, causing the contaminant to bind to molecules with affinity which can prevent the normal metabolic role of the molecule resulting in adverse effects to the organisms. The toxicity of metals is linked to the threshold concentration of metabolically available metals and not the accumulated metal concentration (Rainbow, 2007; Rainbow, 2002). Even though metals are naturally occurring, they can be considered as contaminants when they are discharged from anthropogenic activities like mining and industry. Toxicity for invertebrates occurs for many metals at comparatively low environmental concentrations (e.g., $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) (Adams *et al.*, 2020). Individual invertebrates can take up metals through their surroundings (e.g., water), from food, or through a combination. Aquatic invertebrates living in the same habitat accumulate metals at varying concentrations in their tissues, organs, and bodies, even within closely related taxa and species (Rainbow, 2002).

With the rising concern about the effects of REE on the environment, there has also been an exponential growth in ecotoxicological studies related to these elements (Kang and Kang, 2020). A wide variety of studies have been performed on various organisms, experimental set-ups, and endpoints (both lethal and sub-lethal). However, in the literature there is a big discrepancy with both positive and negative effects being reported, with EC_{50} values (half maximal effective concentration) differing by several orders of magnitude. Due to the similar chemical behaviour, it has also been suggested that effects between the individual REE were similar (Tai *et al.*, 2010; Joonas *et al.*, 2017). Yet, various studies on bacteria and microalgae have shown that the toxicity of REE varies between elements, and is correlated to the atomic number (González *et al.*, 2015; Técher *et al.*, 2020; Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020). Although the number of ecotoxicological studies on REE have increased our knowledge on the adverse effects for anthropogenic concentrations remains limited (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Malhotra *et al.*, 2020).

Chapter 2 of this thesis reviews detailed information on the potential effects of REE on the aquatic ecosystem. It provides the current state-of-the-art knowledge on aquatic toxicity for organisms in the

freshwater, marine, and sediment phase. A total of 38 publications were analysed for the effective (EC_x) and lethal concentrations (LC_x) of REE; 26 on freshwater organisms, 12 on marine organisms. Sediment organisms (e.g., *Caenorhabditis elegans*) were categorized under either freshwater or marine environments. The reliability of the selected ecotoxicity publications for the review were evaluated by following the criteria of Klimisch, Andreae and Tillmann (1997). These criteria included: references to guidelines, data on exposure period, clear description of test procedure, specification of test substances (e.g., purity, composition, origin, by-products), data on test animals (e.g., species, age, strain, sex, life cycle information), number of individuals tested, data on measured parameters (e.g., endpoints including definitions), data on physical and chemical test conditions (e.g., pH, conductivity, light, oxygen), determined effect concentrations (e.g., EC_x, LC_x), data on statistical evaluations (including method), data on dosing of the test substance (e.g., static, semi static, flow through system), data on feeding of the test animals (only for chronic tests).

The review highlights the many challenges faced when performing ecotoxicological studies with REE and includes recommendations for improving the performance of bioassays. The challenges that were identified for the interpretation of REE toxicity data includes addressing the complicated chemical speciation and its relevance when assessing bioavailability, the impact of water hardness, influence of pH, the role of dissolved organic matter (DOM), mixtures of REEs, adsorption of REE (e.g., to glass vessels and sediments), and quantifying exposure conditions (e.g., measured vs nominal concentrations).

1.3. How bioavailability and chemical speciation of REE cause complexity

Many of the challenges in relation to assessing REE ecotoxicology are related to the chemical speciation and consequently the bioavailability of these metals. Chemical speciation refers to the occurrence of elements in different chemical forms within a system (de Paiva Magalhães *et al.*, 2015; Drexler *et al.*, 2003). In comparison to organic compounds, metals differ in that they do not degrade but can be present in different chemical forms (e.g., ionic charge, oxidation state, complexed with environmental ligands) through which they cycle in the environment (Drexler *et al.*, 2003). There are many factors that can influence metal speciation in freshwater ecosystems, which include ionic strength of the medium, hardness of the water, presence of organic matter, pH, redox potential, and the valence state of the metal (de Paiva Magalhães *et al.*, 2015). The complexation and precipitation of metals with inorganic and organic ligands are correlated with pH (Moermond *et al.*, 2001; Millero *et al.*, 2009; Han, 2020).

Due to the high affinity of REE to inorganic ligands (e.g., carbonate, chloride, hydroxide, and phosphate) REE can form complexes and react to precipitate (Moermond *et al.*, 2001; Millero *et al.*, 2009; Wood, 1990; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). The complexation of inorganic ligands, for example phosphate, can have consequences for organisms. Phosphate is an essential nutrient for microalgae growth. The complexation of phosphate with REE can induce nutrient limitation in the form of phosphate starvation for the algae (Goecke *et al.*, 2015) (see also **Chapter 3**). REE also have high complexation ability with divalent cations (e.g., Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) (Du *et al.*, 2019; Marang *et al.*, 2008), DOM (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022), Silicates (SiO_4^{4-}) (main compound of glass) (Weltje *et al.*, 2002a), and sediments and fine organic matter (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018; Schaller, 2013; Tijink and Yland, 1998; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b).

The chemical speciation of REE makes working with these metals for aquatic ecotoxicology experiments very complex. In aquatic ecotoxicology metals in aquatic systems are considered to be bioavailable when they are present as free ions (REE^{3+}); and can be taken up by an organism reaching the toxic site of action with the potential for distribution, metabolism, elimination, and bioaccumulation (Adams *et al.*, 2020; Newman and Jagoe, 1994; Drexler *et al.*, 2003). The free ions are quantified through analytical techniques such as voltammetry (Lee, Chung and Kim, 1997) or in inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) (Haraguchi *et al.*, 1998). This quantification is presented as either the total recoverable metal (based on acid digestion) or the dissolved concentration (based on filtering the metal through a 0.45 μm filter) in solution. Although, it has been suggested that the dissolved metal concentration better reflects the bioavailability, but this had not been standardized in ecotoxicology assays (Adams *et al.*, 2020).

The limiting factors for bioavailability of metals are due to the chemical speciation and the binding sites for which the contaminants compete with ions and molecules in the organisms (Adams *et al.*, 2020). The free ionic forms of most metals, including REE, are considered to be more toxic than other chemical forms (de Paiva Magalhães *et al.*, 2015; Drexler *et al.*, 2003; Moreira *et al.*, 2020). However, metal toxicity can also be caused by more chemical species than only the free ion form (Adams *et al.*, 2020; Drexler *et al.*, 2003). Still a better understanding of bioavailability of these metals can reduce the uncertainties in evaluation of REE toxicity (Anderson, 2008; Drexler *et al.*, 2003; Meyer, 2002). The bioavailability of the chemical REE species varies with each individual element (Cao, Wang and Zhao, 2000) and also depends on the exposure media used (Blinova *et al.*, 2018). This can impact the REE toxicity assessment, as the evaluation of EC_{50} values changes dramatically due to the influence of REE speciation which impacts the bioavailability (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022).

Thus, chemical speciation and bioavailability are considered to be of importance when assessing the ecotoxicity of REE but are still not fully understood. Speciation modelling using geochemical software (e.g., PHREEQC, Visual MINTEQ, Geochemist's Workbench, and WHAM) can be a useful tool in providing a deeper understanding on the complex formation of REE (Parkhurst, 1995; Gustafsson, 2011; Bethke, 2022; Tipping, 1994). However, the use of geochemical models in ecotoxicology remains limited as thermodynamic databases lack information on REE, in particular (validated) equilibrium constants of organic compounds are missing (Iqbal *et al.*, 2023; Marsac *et al.*, 2021) and living organisms are often not taken into account in these models (see **Chapter 4**).

1.4. Benthic-pelagic coupling and the important role of sediment

Evaluation and assessment of sediment quality has become part of achieving good environmental status. The sediment-water interactions in aquatic ecosystems plays an important role in controlling the transport and exposure processes of metals (Ahlf, Drost and Heise, 2009). Benthic-pelagic coupling (Figure 1-3) refers to the exchange of energy, organic material, organisms, and dissolved substances between the benthic (sediment phase) and the pelagic (water phase) layer. These exchanges occur through physical, chemical, biological processes, and anthropogenic disturbances (Testa *et al.*, 2020; Marinelli and Williams, 2003). Benthic-pelagic coupling has been recognized as one of the most important habitat couplings in aquatic ecosystems (Schindler and Scheuerell, 2002).

Sediments are a major reservoir for pollutants and contaminants in aquatic environments (Yang *et al.*, 1999; Khan *et al.*, 2017; MacMillan *et al.*, 2017; Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2018; Balaram, 2019). The high adsorption of REE to sediment particles and to fine particulate organic results in benthic organisms and plants (see also **Chapter 5**) being more exposed to REE contaminated sediment than pelagic species (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018; Schaller, 2013; Tijink and Yland, 1998; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). Around 99% of all REE present in aquatic systems are either in the sediment or attached to suspended matter (Weltje *et al.*, 2002b). Sediments are more likely to be enriched with LREE than HREE, due to that LREE are more likely to form complexes with carbonates available in the sediment (Smrzka *et al.*, 2019).

The REE that are bound to sediments are generally considered to not be bioavailable to aquatic organisms in the water column (pelagic species). But REE can become bioavailable when organisms ingest sediment particles, chemical equilibria are disturbed, or when there is a change in environmental conditions as part of benthic-pelagic coupling (Yang *et al.*, 1999; Mori, 1999; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b; Andrade *et al.*, 2020). Most standardized studies with sediments for the assessment of ecotoxicology do not

consider pelagic species but focus only on benthic invertebrates (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Lécrivain, Frossard and Clément, 2019). If REE stay bound to the sediment and are not available in the water system, they are not of concern unless pelagic organisms avoid the REE contaminated sediment (**Chapter 7** and **Chapter 8**). Which seems unlikely as metals cannot be sensed or detected by the olfactory system of most pelagic and benthic species. So, there should be no reason for them to avoid REE contaminated sediment. Our knowledge of the toxicity of REE-contaminated sediments is still scarce compared to other metals (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 1-3 Simplified benthic-pelagic coupling in a simulated aquatic ecosystem with the pelagic layer (water column) and the benthic layer (sediment phase) for rare earth elements (REE).

1.5. Experimental systems: single species bioassays or “cosm” studies?

When performing ecotoxicological tests it is important to consider pros and cons of the chosen experimental set-up (Figure 1-4) (Amiard-Triquet, 2015). One of the main tools in aquatic ecotoxicology are single species bioassays (Schmitt-Jansen *et al.*, 2008). Single-species toxicity tests are standardized, relatively easy to perform, and have low costs (Pontasch, Niederlehner and Cairns, 1989; Haegerbaeumer *et al.*, 2016). These bioassays cover a wide range of toxicants and mode of actions, and are because of this considered a very useful tool in prognostic risk assessment (Schmitt-Jansen *et al.*, 2008). This results in single-species toxicity tests being chosen to identify, regulate, and monitor environmental problems for contaminants and other stress factors (Pontasch, Niederlehner and Cairns, 1989).

However, there has been growing criticism of the accuracy and relevance of these toxicity tests which are limited to individual species, for understanding (more) natural ecosystems (Pontasch, Niederlehner and Cairns, 1989; Haegerbaeumer *et al.*, 2016). Single-species bioassays are performed under ideal conditions (pH, oxygen, diet, temperature, light, etc.) in well-defined standardized media (see also **Chapter 3 - Chapter 7**). While they provide valuable information for individual organisms and insight in the ecotoxicity of the chosen contaminant (Haegerbaeumer *et al.*, 2016), they do not address concerns of contaminants having indirect effects among the different trophic levels. Metals accumulated in prey species at the lower trophic levels have the potential to be taken up by predator species higher up in the food chain (Rainbow, 2002).

Establishing toxicity of contaminants, like REE, to aquatic organisms in natural freshwater ecosystems is challenging, especially in sediments (Gu *et al.*, 2020). Due to this complexity of the benthopelagic coupling, benthic and pelagic habitats are examined separately in many studies (Schindler and Scheuerell, 2002). This causes the various factors linked to benthopelagic coupling to be overlooked in single-species bioassay. This is a concern, as contaminants are the main drivers of deteriorating aquatic ecosystems (Schmitt-Jansen *et al.*, 2008).

An alternative for the single-species bioassays are so called “cosm” studies (see also **Chapter 8**). These are experimental systems that are designed to simulate more realistic ecosystems. There are many variations of “cosm” studies such as, in size (nano-, micro-, meso-), indoor or outdoor, enclosed or open, aquatic or terrestrial, etc. This makes “cosms” suitable to address various research objectives, and allows for the effects of contaminants to be tested on several species and communities (Bradshaw *et al.*, 2015). “Cosm” approaches allow for species interaction (e.g., predator-prey relationships) and different exposure route observations, while considering the physico-chemical environment (e.g, benthic-pelagic coupling) (Santos *et al.*, 2018). This makes “cosms” usually more ecologically relevant in comparison to single-species bioassays (Clements and Newman, 2003). Despite all these benefits, “cosm” studies are not widely used (Auffan *et al.*, 2019) and those that are performed mainly focused on microbenthic invertebrates (Brinke *et al.*, 2011). The application of “cosm” studies with REE are even more limited (Fuma *et al.*, 2001).

The drawback of “cosm” experiments is that there is an increased complexity compared to single-species bioassays. They, are relatively costly and time consuming to perform (Amiard-Triquet, 2015). Because of this “cosm” studies often lack replication, and some physical-chemical parameters and biological endpoints measured in single-species bioassays cannot be determined in “cosm” experiments (Auffan *et al.*, 2019). Thus, both single-species bioassays and “cosm” studies have different attributes to

be explored in toxicity research. Ultimately, to fully understand the impact of emerging contaminants like REE both single-species bioassays and “cosm” studies should be performed.

Figure 1-4 Different experimental approaches in ecotoxicology presented along a gradient scale for variability, control, cost, and number of contaminants tested modified from Amiard-Triquet (2015).

1.6. Objectives

The overall objective of this thesis is to investigate the chronic effects of rare earth elements on the aquatic benthopelagic ecosystem, to better understand the toxicity effects on individual aquatic invertebrates and communities. To achieve this, a combination of acute and chronic exposure for single-species and multi-species experiments were performed to gain a deeper insight into the role of sediment re-suspension for lanthanum (La) and gadolinium (Gd). This was done as a first step to benthopelagic coupling and to connect different trophic levels in sediment and water phase. **The main hypotheses for this thesis are:**

- 1. Acute effects by REE occur at concentrations that are not environmentally relevant, chronic effects at low concentrations are thus negligible.**
- 2. As metals cannot be sensed by olfactory systems, they will not cause any active avoidance behavior by pelagic invertebrates.**
- 3. Multispecies tests in sediment-water systems will not show any effects because of the strong partitioning of REE to the sediments.**

1.7. Methods

1.7.1. Model Rare Earth Elements

This study focused on two REE: Lanthanum (La, atomic number 57) and Gadolinium (Gd, atomic number 64) (Figure 1-1)(Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Rogowska *et al.*, 2018; Trapasso *et al.*, 2021). They were chosen due to their widespread application in modern society, wide range of uses, and being representative of the LREE (La) and HREE (Gd) subgroups. The natural concentration of REE in aquatic systems is influenced by rock composition and water chemistry (Elderfield, Upstill-Goddard and Sholkovitz, 1990). REE usually appear in the same relative natural concentrations, when they deviate from these concentrations they are referred to as positive anomalies. These anomalies can be due to anthropogenic applications like mining and industry (Tepe, Romero and Bau, 2014). Anthropogenic input in freshwater ecosystems has led to reports of both La and Gd having positive anomalies in surface waters globally (Klaver *et al.*, 2014; Rogowska *et al.*, 2018; Trapasso *et al.*, 2021; Bau and Dulski, 1996). The predicted further increase of REE demand will likely result in even higher positive anomalies, resulting in elevated adverse effects for our aquatic systems. Existing information and data on these two elements provides a basic understanding and makes it easier to interpret the outcomes of the work in this thesis.

Lanthanum is the first and lightest element within the lanthanide group. It is applied for various purposes such as a fertilizer, in ceramics, in catalysts for cracking crude petroleum, in battery electrodes, optical components, and for the removal of phosphates in wastewater treatment plants (Pagano, 2016; Weltje *et al.*, 2002a; Chen, Chen and Chen, 2022; Dang *et al.*, 2021). It is also known to be more bioavailable to benthic organisms, due to the high adsorption of La to sediment particles (Tijink and Yland, 1998; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b). Both Gd^{3+} and La^{3+} compete with Ca^{2+} (calcium) ions on the binding sites in organisms (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Martino *et al.*, 2018; Sherry, Caravan and Lenkinski, 2009)

Gadolinium is used in nuclear reactor control rods, neutron capture, computer memory, and television screens (Dang *et al.*, 2021; Rogowska *et al.*, 2018; Pagano, 2016). A Gd anomaly was reported for the first time in river waters in 1996 (Bau and Dulski, 1996), which has been linked to hospital effluents. This is due to its application as a contrast agent in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). For every MRI performed is 1.2 g of Gd used, which makes up 5% of the total Gd production (Künnemeyer *et al.*, 2009).

Chapter 5 also included the LREE cerium (Ce, atomic number 58) and Neodymium (Nd, atomic number 60) to study the potential adverse effects aquatic macrophyte *Myriophyllum aquaticum*. Aquatic plants significantly influence freshwater ecosystems, by performing primary productivity and providing food and habitats for diverse aquatic organisms. Ce has been mainly used as a catalyst, metal alloy, and lens polishers. It is also one of the few REE elements that have the potential to oxidize from Ce^{3+} to Ce^{4+}

(Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018). The application of Nd consists of magnets for laptops, lasers, fluid-fracking catalysts, electrical motors, and communication devices (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014).

While Ce together with La is one of the most studied REE (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014), Nd is one of the least studied in ecotoxicology (Malhotra *et al.*, 2020). However, both Ce and Nd have been used in various plant studies for which both positive and negative toxicity effects have been found (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014; Gjata *et al.*, 2022; Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2021). Both Ce and Nd are heavily used in fertilizers for plants, and the accumulation of the REEs in plants follows the amount of the REE content in the fertilizer (Ramírez-Olvera *et al.*, 2018; Sneller *et al.*, 2000; Zhang and Shan, 2001). This makes Ce and Nd great additions to La and Gd for studying the possible adverse effects on aquatic plants.

1.7.2. Model organisms

1.7.2.1. Freshwater Pelagic Organisms

The organisms chosen to address the objective of this thesis are freshwater invertebrates that play an important role in the ecosystem. The choice was made for organisms that can be studied in single-species bioassays but also for the predator-prey relationships between two pelagic species. *Daphnia magna* was used in this thesis to study the role of freshwater invertebrate primary consumer (**Chapter 8**) but also as a single species to determine behavioral changes (**Chapter 7**), and reproduction, mortality, and biodistribution (**Chapter 6**).

The freshwater crustacean *D. magna* (Figure 1-5a) is a primary consumer that can be found in many freshwater ecosystems. These filter feeders regulate the microalgae population and are a food source for various predators like fish (Bownik, 2017). Because of this they play an important key role in the aquatic food web (Ebert, 2005). The short life cycle, rapid reproductive cycle, and being easy to culture in the lab made this species a key model for ecotoxicological testing (OECD, 2012; OECD, 2004). *Daphnia* have been shown to be very sensitive to a range of contaminants and consequently have been used to assess the adverse effects of REE in numerous studies (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Blinova *et al.*, 2018; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Lachaux *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 1-5 a) Adult *Daphnia magna*, b) *Raphidocelis subcapitata*, c) *Scenedesmus vacuolates*, and d) *Chlorella vulgaris*, and their real-life size. All images taken by Chantal van Drimmelen; a) was photographed using a phone through the eyepiece of Wiloskop stereomicroscope (Hund Wetzlar, Wetzlar, Germany). b-c) were captured using an Olympus CKX53 inverted microscope (Shinjuku, Tokyo, Japan) with EP50 colour camera and the imaging software EPview.

As stated above, daphnia feeds on microalgae, these are unicellular phytoplankton that are ecologically important due to their role as primary producers in freshwater ecosystems. Similar to daphnia, microalgae have been used to investigate sensitivity of pelagic species to REE (Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020; Joonas *et al.*, 2017; Ramasamy, Porada and Sillanpää, 2019; Tai *et al.*, 2010). To study the potential effects of REE contaminated sediment on the dynamics predator-prey relationship of two pelagic species, the microalgae *Raphidocelis subcapitata* (Figure 1-5b) was chosen as a prey for *D. magna* (Chapter 8). This microalgae species is the recommended organism for standardized microalgae tests such as the ISO 8692:2012 (ISO, 2012).

However, this raises questions about the different use of microalgae species as representatives of a wider group and the interaction of phosphate within the standardized media with REE (Chapter 3 and Chapter 4). Phosphate is an essential nutrient for the growth of microalgae. However, the strong affinity with REE can cause for the formation of REE-PO₄ complexes and the precipitation leads to less REE but also can cause phosphate starvation for microalgae (Tai *et al.*, 2010; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014; González *et al.*, 2015). To investigate what the chemical behavior of REE-PO₄ in media is (Chapter 4) and how this precipitation can mask the toxicity of REE (Chapter 3), different phosphate sources were tested using three microalgae species. In addition to *R. subcapitata* were *Chlorella vulgaris* (Figure 1-5c) and *Scenedesmus vacuolatus* (Figure 1-5d) chosen. *C. vulgaris* is another microalgae species used in various studies (Ozaki *et al.*, 2003; Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2019; Sun *et al.*, 2019) and *S. vacuolatus* is interesting due to its potential to accumulate and store PO₄³⁻ in its cells (Kessler, 1976; Aharchaou *et al.*, 2020).

1.7.2.1. Freshwater Plant

Aquatic macrophytes are plants that grown in or near water, these primary producers influence the carbon and nutrient cycle, provide food and habitats for organisms in aquatic environments (Wetzel, 2001). *Myriophyllum aquaticum* (Figure 1-6) grows directly in the sediment, and are thus able to detect and remove pollutants (Souza *et al.*, 2013). *Myriophyllum spp.* has been used as a plant model to test pesticides and herbicide toxicity (Forney and Davis, 1981; Paterson and Wright, 1987; Turgut, 2005). However, a significant reduction in the abundance of these plants can impact the whole aquatic ecosystem (Lewis, 1995). *M. aquaticum* could impact on the resuspension and bioavailability of REE in sediments, it is also easy to culture, grows fast, is not prone to contamination by other organisms. It is relatively sensitive which makes it an ideal model to test the impact of REE contaminated sediment (**Chapter 5**).

Figure 1-6 Whorl of *Myriophyllum aquaticum*. Picture taken by Chantal van Drimmelen

1.8. Structure

This thesis is divided into 11 chapters including the current one and a general discussion. Four out of the nine chapters have been submitted for publication in scientific journals. A short summary for each chapter is given below and Figure 1-7 shows a visual abstract of the presented chapters:

Chapter 2 is an extensive literature review with the title “**Effects of REE in the aquatic environment – and implications for ecotoxicological testing**”. This chapter dives into the current state of the scientific knowledge and understanding regarding the ecotoxicity of REEs to aquatic species in freshwater, marine, and sediment environments. This critical review provides an insight into the contradictory conclusions among the current scientific published literature, the challenges that come-up for conducting bioassay with REE and gives suggestions for the improvement of performing ecotoxicological studies. This publication has been submitted to Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology in December 2023.

Chapter 3 is titled “**Does phosphate mask toxicity of two REE for different microalgae species?**”. The objective was to study of the toxicity of La and Gd on microalgae is caused by the bioavailability of the elements or by phosphate-limitation. The inhibitory effect of La and Gd was evaluation on three different microalgae species in three media each containing a different source of phosphate. Not only provides this chapter emphasize the need to integrate chemical speciation and interspecies microalgae sensitivity, but it also provides a deeper understanding of what happens with the pelagic prey species in **Chapter 6** and **Chapter 8**. This publication was submitted to the journal *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* in November 2023.

Chapter 4 is related to the previous chapter and investigates the bioavailability of La and Gd for the different phosphate sources by comparing the nominal concentrations, the dissolved concentrations, and the predictions made by speciation modelling using the software PHREEQC (Parkhurst, 1995). This chapter is titled “**Importance of speciation analysis for REE toxicity in presence of phosphate and microalgae**”. The objective was to assess the applicability of geochemistry models in predicting the bioavailability of REE in microalgae bioassays. This chapter highlights the need for integration of biological factors into chemical speciation models so that they can help understand and predict the REE bioavailability in experiments like those of **Chapter 3**, **Chapter 6**, and **Chapter 8**.

Chapter 5 focusses on the aquatic macrophyte *M. aquaticum* as these plants provide habitats for other organisms, like daphnia, and the significant reduction of these plants can result in a shift into algae-dominated systems. These plants could also play a role in the resuspension and bioavailability of REE in sediments. The objective was to investigate the ecotoxicological responses to La, Ce, Nd, and Gd. This chapter is titled “**Impact of Rare Earth Elements on the growth and photosynthetic efficiency in *Myriophyllum aquaticum***” and provides an additional look into the ecosystem dynamics, especially in combination with **Chapter 8**, and the toxicity of different REE. This chapter was submitted to the *Journal of Soils and Sediments* in February 2024.

Chapter 6 provides the role of different exposure pathways on the chronic toxicity and biodistribution of La and Gd on *D. magna*. This work is titled “**Toxicity and biodistribution of La and Gd in *Daphnia magna* following chronic dietary and waterborne exposure**”. The objective of this chapter was

to investigate the effects of chronic waterborne, dietary, and combined exposures of La and Gd on mortality, growth, and reproduction of *D. magna*. The observed effects showed that considering dietary exposure is of importance for chronic bioassays. This chapter provides a better understanding of the observed behavioural changes in **Chapter 7** and the predator-prey relationship of **Chapter 8**. It was submitted to the journal *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* in October 2023.

Chapter 7 titled “**To Avoid or Not to Avoid Rare Earth Element Contaminated Sediment? That is the Question for *Daphnia magna***” investigated the observed behavior of the daphnia seen in the nanocosms of **Chapter 8**. The objective of this chapter was to determine if sediment contaminated with lanthanum (La) or gadolinium (Gd), leads to avoidance behaviour by pelagic species such as *D. magna*. Behaviour is a more sensitive endpoint than for example mortality, and could help with risk assessment and understanding the impacts of REE-contaminated sediment.

Chapter 8 applies nanocosm to stimulate the impact of REE in water-sediment systems with two pelagic species. This chapter is called “**14-Day nanocosm to investigate the toxicity of La and Gd along the food chain microalgae-daphnia**”. This set-up was chosen because in **Chapter 2** the importance of sediment was identified and the gathered data on *R. subcapitata* and *D. magna* provides a baseline understanding. The *R. subcapitata*-*D. magna* under environmentally and anthropogenically relevant concentrations of REE provides further insight to our understanding of the adverse effects on ecosystem communities in the aquatic environment.

Chapter 9 is titled “**Microcosms as a tool to study REE toxicity in a simulated aquatic food web**”. The objective was to investigate the impact of sediment resuspension on the transfer of 0.5 mg kg^{-1} Gd from benthic layer to the pelagic layer at the first consumer level. The 2 L glass microcosms was used to establish a stimulated aquatic ecosystem with six biological species: daphnia (*Daphnia magna*), microalgae (*Raphidocelis subcapitata*), oligochaeta worm (*Lumbriculus variegatus*), natural lake sediment bacteria, and ostracods (*Heterocypris incongruens*). This study demonstrates the adverse effects of Gd on the aquatic food web and which species were the most sensitive. Even though the experiment had to be terminated prematurely.

Chapter 10 is a discussion and conclusion bringing together previous work and provides a prototype food web model for the chronic impact of La and Gd on six biological species. It is entitled **“Simple Food web model for the chronic impact of Rare Earth Elements in an aquatic ecosystem”**. Multispecies tests (**Chapter 7, Chapter 8, and Chapter 9**) can be complex to perform and the food web model could help us understand better of the impact REE have on different organisms. It introduces the prototype model and also addresses the lessons learned and the future outlook for its further development.

Figure 1-7 Visual abstract of this thesis

1.9. References

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CHAPTER 1

Zhang, S. and Shan, X. (2001) 'Speciation of rare earth elements in soil and accumulation by wheat with rare earth fertilizer application', *Environmental Pollution*, 112(3), pp. 395-405.

CHAPTER 2

EFFECTS OF REE IN THE AQUATIC ENVIRONMENT - AND IMPLICATIONS FOR ECOTOXICOLOGICAL TESTING

Marion Revel^{1,2∞}, Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen^{1,2∞}, Lennart Weltje³, Andrew S. Hursthouse², Susanne Heise¹

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¹ Life Sciences, Hamburg University of Applied Science, Ulmenliet 20, D-21033 Hamburg, Germany

² University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

³ BASF SE, Agricultural Solutions – Ecotoxicology, Speyerer Strasse 2, D-67117 Limburgerhof, Germany

[∞] Equal contribution as first authors

Abstract

Rare earth elements (REEs) are recognized as emerging pollutants due to their widespread use in modern society. This leads to anthropogenically elevated concentrations in water, soil and sediments, raising questions around the potential consequences for the environment. This review intends to critically present the current scientific knowledge on aquatic bioavailability and toxicity of REEs at different ecosystem levels. The bioavailability of REEs and consequently their toxicity varies strongly with the prevailing geochemical conditions. We identify important features of their chemical speciation and mode of action, when working with these sparingly soluble elements. REE toxicity appears to be species dependent but also related to the type and concentration of REE. Furthermore, we highlight contradictory findings, major outcomes, and provide general conclusions from the review to offer a new perspective to facilitate the interpretation and conducting of laboratory bioassays with these elements.

2.1. Introduction

The Rare Earth Elements (REE) are a group of metals comprising the 15 elements from the lanthanide (Ln) series with atomic numbers (Z) from 57 to 71 and chemically similar elements scandium (Sc) (Z=21) and yttrium (Y) (Z=39) (Wall, 2021). Despite being called “rare earth elements”, they are not particularly rare in the earth crust as the most common REE, cerium (Ce), has a similar crustal abundance to nickel (Ni) and copper (Cu). With the exception of promethium (Pm), which has no stable isotopes, even the rarest lanthanides, thulium (Tm) and lutetium (Lu), are more common than silver (Ag) or the platinum (Pt) metals (Cotton, 2006). However, concentrated deposits are unusual.

The 17 REEs show similar but not identical physical and chemical properties. Among the Ln, from lanthanum (La) to lutetium (Lu), electrons occupy the inner 4f orbitals with little effect on bonding properties. The effective nuclear charge which is weakly screened by the 4f electrons causes a decrease in atomic radius with increasing atomic number which is known as the lanthanide contraction. This influences their chemical behaviour, as heavier Ln with subsequently higher charge densities have an increased affinity for negatively charged groups. In aqueous solution, Ln as well as Y and Sc occur mostly in a trivalent (3+) oxidation state. The only other environmentally relevant oxidation states are 4+ for Ce, under oxidising conditions, and 2+ for europium (Eu), under reducing conditions (Henderson, 1996). The REE are often divided into light (La to samarium (Sm) and heavy rare earth metals (Eu to Lu), with the separation of the categories being slightly different and if and whether Sc and Y are included.

Due to their low solubility in water and with the assumption, that only the trivalent free ions were available, the REE appear historically to present no or little environmental risk, and regulatory restrictions such as drinking water standards are not in place. However, due to their unique magnetic and/or optical properties there has been a growing demand for REE in new technologies in for example the automotive industry and in renewable energy generation systems over the last decades. Intensified use goes along with increasing emissions to the environment. While REE used to serve as natural geological tracers in hydrological systems, their current anthropogenically elevated concentrations in water, soil and sediments raise the questions of whether these could have negative consequences for humans and the environment. This concern is reflected by the relatively rapid increase in the number of scientific publications addressing the topic of REE and (eco)toxicity along with the rise of world production of the elements (Figure 2-1).

A number of detailed experimental studies and literature reviews have been published over the last 10 years or more (Weltje, 2002; Ng *et al.*, 2011). The more recent studies focus on specific elements such as La (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016) and Gd (Trapasso *et al.*, 2021a) or solely on marine waters (Piarulli *et al.*, 2021). Others provide extremely useful summaries on the current level of knowledge (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014; Blinova *et al.*, 2020; Malhotra *et al.*, 2020; Kang and Kang, 2020) but focussed on individual REE, in

single matrices or organisms (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Malhotra *et al.*, 2020). We provide a review of the current scientific knowledge on the aquatic toxicity (the marine- and fresh-water phase, and sediment) for the most commonly used REE highlighting studies that provide results reaching agreement or provide conflicting observation and whether general conclusions can be drawn on the basis of what is currently known about their toxicity. We use this analysis to highlight the most critical steps when performing biotests with REE, to make more meaningful suggestions to improve the assessment of environmental risk. We have excluded studies on nanoparticles from the review as their behavior within the water and the organisms are known to be different. All papers related to ecotoxicology have been checked using the criteria of Klimisch, Andreae and Tillmann (1997).

Figure 2-1 World mine production of rare earth elements (REE) and the number of publications published from 1956 to 2023 containing "rare earth" AND "**tox*", as listed in the SCOPUS database. Source for world production data: 1900-2020: U.S. Geological Survey (2014); 2021: U.S. Geological Survey (2023); 2022-2023: U.S. Geological Survey (2024).

2.2. Natural occurrence and anthropogenic emissions to the aquatic environment

Because of their chemical similarity, REE behave as a group and are distributed in the environment through geogenic erosion processes. Their concentrations in environmental media maintain a consistent pattern. In general the REE follow the Oddo-Harkins rule (Oddo, 1914; Harkins, 1917) with the highest concentrations being found for the first even-numbered REE (Ce), while the lowest concentrations are found for the last two odd-numbered REE (Tm and Lu), with concentrations typically two orders of magnitude lower than for Ce (Table 2-1).

Out of the seventeen REE Pm is the only REE without a stable isotope and has therefore no natural occurrence. An analysis of geochemical data prepared by the Forum of European Geological Surveys (FOREGS) (Salminen *et al.*, 2005) concluded that the overall distribution pattern over Europe is entirely due to the geological characteristics. Concentrations in water vary over two orders of magnitude, depending on the regional geology. No evidence of anthropogenic sources on the scale of the FOREGS data has been found, which would not detect local anomalies (Fedele *et al.*, 2008).

Table 2-1 The median concentrations of rare earth elements (REE) in the upper continental crust (Rudnick and Gao (2003) as reported in the Forum of European Geological Surveys (FOREGS database) and the median REE concentrations and ranges in stream water and stream sediment in Europe according to the FOREGS database (Salminen *et al.*, 2005).

REE	Upper continental crust	Stream Water, filtered <0.45 µm		Stream sediment, size fraction <150 µm	
		Median	Range	Median	Range
	µmol kg ⁻¹	µmol l ⁻¹	µmol l ⁻¹	µmol kg ⁻¹	µmol kg ⁻¹
Sc	311	No data		No data	
Y	236	7.20×10 ⁻⁰⁴	<3.37×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 7.34×10 ⁻⁰²	289	7.63 - 3630
La	223	2.45×10 ⁻⁰⁴	<1.44×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 1.15×10 ⁻⁰⁷	230	1.33 - 705
Ce	450	3.93×10 ⁻⁰⁴	<1.43×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 7.21×10 ⁻⁰²	475	0.33 - 46.50
Pr	50.40	6.39×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.42×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 1.06×10 ⁻⁰²	49.70	1.27 - 576
Nd	187	2.77×10 ⁻⁰⁴	<1.39×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 3.99×10 ⁻⁰²	191	0.13 - 91.20
Sm	31.30	5.99×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.33×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 7.12×10 ⁻⁰³	34.60	0.68 - 481
Eu	6.58	3.29×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.32×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 1.32×10 ⁻⁰³	6.51	0.24 - 101
Gd	25.40	6.36×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.27×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 6.17×10 ⁻⁰³	31	0.42 - 275
Tb	4.40	1.26×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.26×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 8.18×10 ⁻⁰⁴	4.85	0.12 - 38.10
Dy	24	4.92×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.23×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 4.86×10 ⁻⁰³	27.40	0.58 - 247
Ho	5.03	1.21×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.21×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 1.03×10 ⁻⁰³	5.40	0.11 - 34.50
Er	13.80	3.59×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.20×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 2.87×10 ⁻⁰³	15.50	7.63 - 3'630
Tm	1.78	1.18×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.18×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 4.03×10 ⁻⁰⁴	2.31	1.33 - 705
Yb	11.30	3.47×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.16×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 2.37×10 ⁻⁰³	14.30	0.33 - 46.50
Lu	1.77	1.14×10 ⁻⁰⁵	<1.14×10 ⁻⁰⁵ - 4.00×10 ⁻⁰⁴	2.17	<1.27 - 576

The absolute concentration of REE in aquatic systems depends on the rock composition in the respective catchment and the water chemistry (Elderfield, Upstill-Goddard and Sholkovitz, 1990). When normalizing dissolved REE concentrations to shale composition, usually a smooth pattern results. Small anomalies in this pattern can be caused by differences in the stability of complexes or redox-sensitivities

(Tepe, Romero and Bau, 2014), while large positive anomalies point to anthropogenic sources. For example, local and regional anomalies derive from substantial targeted mining and intentional application in industrial products. Most extensive REE mining is carried out in China equating to 62% of global production in 2019 (Garside, 2021). Data compiled from mining areas in China (Liang, Li and Wang, 2014) where soil contamination reached magnitudes of mM, well above the world averages (Figure 2-2). In acidic waters from mining sites on a branch of the Yellow river in China, REE were enriched by a factor of more than 1000, compared to the less affected main river section. In suspended particulate matter and deposited sediment, REE-concentrations exceeded average values of rivers in Northern China up to 200-fold (Liang, Li and Wang, 2014).

REE concentrations in soil samples in Chinese mining areas

Figure 2-2 The soil concentrations of select rare earth element (REE) in Chinese mining areas compared with the world average concentrations (stars), based on data from Liang *et al.* (2014). The box and whisker plots display the distribution of the measured concentrations, with limits of the boxes indicating the range of the central 50 % of concentrations measured at seven mining areas, the central line indicating the median, and the whiskers extending to the minimum and maximum values.

Outside of China's mining areas, product manufacturing and related technological processes can lead to elevated environmental concentrations. Transport pathways that link production and uses to elevated concentrations in the aquatic environment may be atmospheric deposition, surface run-off and effluents. Among these, atmospheric deposition may occur but has not been shown to contribute substantially to the contaminant load of rivers (Cidu *et al.*, 2013), at least outside of mining areas. However, one could perform ecotoxicological testing through the deposition of particles with an appropriate filter system, which could be tested using nematodes. Speciation studies would be more

important in aquatic systems than these ecotoxicological tests, but probably not with REE adsorbed to solid surfaces.

Substantial Gd anomalies in surface waters due to the presence of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) contrast agents in hospital effluents have first been described by Bau and Dulski (1996) and have now been reported for all rivers worldwide that flow through densely populated areas (Klaver *et al.*, 2014). Anthropogenic Gd fluxes in the Garonne watershed in France, for example, increased from 203 mol year⁻¹ in 2003 to 477 mol year⁻¹ in 2017 (Lerat-Hardy *et al.*, 2019). Also, production sites of fluid cracking catalysts lead to substantial increase in Ce, La, and Sm, as do mining activities (Table 2-2).

REE containing industrial effluents can be directly discharged into surface waters, as REE are currently unregulated. A study by Kulaksız and Bau (2011) traced a La anomaly in the Rhine river to an upstream plant producing fluid cracking catalysts in Worms and emitting substantial quantities of La into the river, and it has been demonstrated that La could be traced till the North Sea (Klaver *et al.*, 2014). While these elevated levels are still in the range of natural background concentrations (Table 2-1), they mostly exceed the median values. With continuous and increasing emissions, these concentrations are likely to rise in future and will specifically accumulate in sediments. However, elevated loads by themselves do not necessarily give rise to concern. Discussion of environmental impact needs to address environmental concentrations, speciation, partitioning, and bioavailability in relation to the ecotoxicity of the elements in question.

Table 2-2 Detected anomalies of rare earth elements (REE) in aquatic systems and the reported concentrations. WWTP = Wastewater treatment plant.

REE	Concentrations	Unit	Matrix	Region/location	Country	Probable Source	Reference
Ce	$1.19 \times 10^{+03}$	$\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$	sediment	Anning River, Sichuan Province	China	Mining activity	Wang et al., (2021)
Ce	1.10×10^{-05} - 1.01×10^{-03}	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Rhine River, ca. 250 km downstream of effluent	Germany	Fluid cracking catalyst production	Kulaksız & Bau, (2013)
Ce	$1.21 \times 10^{+03}$	$\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$	sediment	Rhine estuary	The Netherlands	Artificial fertilizer plant	Bakkenist & van de Wiel, (1995)
Gd	1.70×10^{-05} - 1.18×10^{-04}	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Suzhou City (urban waters)	China	WWTP	Shilin et al., (2021)
Gd	9.79×10^{-06} - 5.51×10^{-04}	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Jinzhong Stream	China	WWTP from a hospital	Zhang et al., (2019)

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Gd	$4.58 \times 10^{-05} - 2.09 \times 10^{-04}$	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Han-River, influenced by a WWTP	South Korea	WWTP from hospitals	Song et al., (2017)
Gd	$1.14 \times 10^{-05} - 4.58 \times 10^{-05}$	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Garonne River	France	WWTP from hospitals	Lerat-Hardy et al., (2019)
Gd	1.01×10^{-03}	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Havel River	Germany	WWTP from hospitals	Bau & Dulski (1996)
La	3.42×10^{-05}	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Anning River, Sichuan Province	China	Mining activity, industrial and agricultural activity	Wang et al., (2021)
La	2.38×10^{-03}	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Rhine River, ca. 50 km downstream of effluent	Germany	Fluid cracking catalyst production	Kulaksız & Bau, (2011)
La	$9.07 \times 10^{-05} - 6.41 \times 10^{-04}$	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Rhine River, ca. 250 km downstream of effluent	Germany	Fluid cracking catalyst production	Kulaksız & Bau, (2013)
La	$5.76 \times 10^{+02}$	$\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$	sediment	Rhine estuary	The Netherlands	Artificial fertilizer plant	Bakkenist & van de Wiel, (1995)
Nd	$5.55 \times 10^{+02}$	$\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$	sediment	Rhine estuary	The Netherlands	Artificial fertilizer plant	Bakkenist & van de Wiel, (1995)
Pr	$2.13 \times 10^{+02}$	$\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$	sediment	Rhine estuary	The Netherlands	Artificial fertilizer plant	Bakkenist & van de Wiel, (1995)
Sm	$1.27 \times 10^{-05} - 2.11 \times 10^{-04}$	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	surface water	Rhine River, ca. 250 km downstream of effluent	Germany	Fluid cracking catalyst production	Kulaksız & Bau, (2013)
Sm	$1.33 \times 10^{+02}$	$\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$	sediment	Rhine estuary	The Netherlands	Artificial fertilizer plant	Bakkenist & van de Wiel, (1995)
Y	$2.70 \times 10^{+01} - 3.60 \times 10^{+02}$	$\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$	sediment	Tagus estuary	Portugal	Chemical and phosphorus fertilizer industry	Brito et al., (2018)

2.3. Behaviour and Fate

2.3.1. Speciation

In water, REE partitioning between bulk waters, pore waters, dissolved fraction and colloidal fraction is controlled by speciation and adsorption (Zhong and Mucci, 1995). The speciation of REE is characterized by the competition between stables aqueous complexes and the adsorption or (co)precipitation in the solid phase. Therefore, REE exist as free metal ions or complexed with organic or inorganic ligands and is impacted by colloidal composition and water chemistry (Verplanck, 2013).

With a similar ionic radius, REE also compete with divalent cations such as calcium (Ca^{2+}) and magnesium (Mg^{2+}) for binding sites of organic ligands (Du *et al.*, 2019; Marang *et al.*, 2008). Apart from being present in their free ionic form (REE^{3+}), REE can form complexes with inorganic ligands such as carbonate, hydroxide, phosphate, and chloride (Moermond *et al.*, 2001a; Millero *et al.*, 2009; Wood, 1990). While REE-nitrates, chlorides, and sulfates are more soluble, REE-carbonates, phosphates, and hydroxides have high stability constants (Table 2-3) and are considered insoluble (Wells and Wells, 2012). Metal complexation and precipitation with inorganic and organic ligands are positively correlated with pH (Moermond *et al.*, 2001; Millero *et al.*, 2009; Han, 2020).

Dissolved organic matter (DOM, often expressed in dissolved organic carbon, DOC) has very high complexation ability with REE. In freshwater solutions, about 95% of REE is associated with DOM, which mainly consists of humic and fulvic acids, that bind REE to their carboxylic and phenolic groups (Dupré *et al.*, 1999; Marang *et al.*, 2008; Perdue, Reuter and Parrish, 1984; Torres and Choppin, 1984). Presence of DOM strongly affects REE speciation as it can increase the solubility of REE by counteracting precipitation and increasing the mobility of REE in the environment by serving as a transport vehicle (Choppin, 1986; Mccarthy, Sanford and Stafford, 1998). However, at higher concentrations, the presence of DOM in water system significantly reduced bioaccumulation and toxicity of REEs for pelagic species due to strong complexation and precipitation (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b; Tang and Johannesson, 2003; Vukov, Smith and McGeer, 2016; El-Akl, Smith and Wilkinson, 2015).

Solution composition and chemical speciation should be taken into account when assessing the toxicity of REE, as the EC_{50} values calculated strongly influence environmental risk assessment (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a). While chemical speciation is an essential consideration when investigating REE behavior and toxicity, it remains a challenge to define. Apart from analytical techniques such as voltammetry (labile fraction including the free REE ion) (Lee, Chung and Kim, 1997) or inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) (Haraguchi *et al.*, 1998) that allow to quantify the dissolved metal concentration in solution, speciation modelling can be carried out with the use of geochemical modeling software such as PHREEQC (Parkhurst, 1995), Visual MINTEQ (Gustafsson, 2011), Geochemist's Workbench (Bethke, 2022)

or the WHAM (Tipping, 1994). Speciation calculations on natural waters demand a large analytical effort to characterize the system in terms of its components and also simplification when considering the influence of DOM (Dupré *et al.*, 1999) and other factors such as fluctuation of abiotic or the presence of organisms.

Table 2-3 Solubility constants of selected rare earth elements (from NIST Database 46 Version 8.0)

REE species	log(K)
La(OH)	5.5
La(CO ₃)	6.98
La(NO ₃)	0.7
La(SO ₄)	3.64
LaCl	0.53
La(PO ₄) _(s)	25.75
Gd(OH)	6.2
Gd(CO ₃)	7.64
Gd(NO ₃)	0.61
Gd(SO ₄)	3.66
GdCl	-1.06
Gd(PO ₄) _(s)	25.6
Lu(OH)	6.6
Lu(CO ₃)	8
Lu(NO ₃)	0.4
Lu(SO ₄)	3.52
LuCl	-1.97
Lu(PO ₄) _(s)	24.8

2.3.2. Adsorption

Sediments, and more precisely mineral phases such as iron (Fe-) and manganese (Mn-) oxyhydroxides, are efficient adsorbents for REE (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018). Metals associated with Fe-containing aluminosilicate mineral fraction can undergo diagenesis after deposition in sediments (Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004; Wen, Warnken and Santschi, 2008).

Silicates (SiO₄⁴⁻) are the main compound of glass and is known to be a strong adsorbent of REE. Silicate materials are for example used to remove these metals in industrial wastewater (Callura *et al.*, 2018; Perea *et al.*, 2018; Weltje *et al.*, 2002a). The amount of REE that can be adsorbed by glass (silica) is up to 25% of the total La present in the medium (Weltje *et al.*, 2002a). It is therefore recommended to avoid the use of glass apparatus for bioassays and apply containers with lower adsorption capacity for REE.

However, a lot of other material surfaces used in apparatus in bioassays can adsorb a certain amount of metal ions and include materials such as polyethylene, polypropylene, Teflon, stainless steel, borosilicate glass, quartz, and “soft glass” (Eichholz, Nagel and Hughes, 1965; Weltje *et al.*, 2002a). In fact, Ce adsorption (measured in % adsorption per cm²) was found to be stronger on polypropylene than borosilicate glass (Eichholz, Nagel and Hughes, 1965). Furthermore, a decrease in pH significantly reduced the adsorption on glass and had an even more pronounced effect on plastic. However, it has been suggested that REE adsorption remains low enough to be neglected in bioassays (Eichholz, Nagel and Hughes, 1965). For example, Aharchaou *et al.* (2020) measured La and Ce concentration variation in abiotic media and found that even after 120 hours, less than 20% of the initial value was adsorbed on the walls of the test vessel.

Sorption of REE on aquatic organisms such as microorganisms, algae, invertebrates or vertebrates has been well studied and differs strongly between organisms (Cheng *et al.*, 2018; Das, Sharma and Talukder, 1988; Das, Varshini and Das, 2014; Martinez, Pourret and Takahashi, 2014; Ramasamy, Porada and Sillanpää, 2019; Tamjidi and Ameri, 2020). For example, La sorption has been quantified at 1010 µmol g⁻¹ for crab shell (Vijayaraghavan *et al.*, 2009), 7200 µmol g⁻¹ for the green freshwater algae *Desmodus multivariabilis* (Birungi and Chirwa, 2014) and 1080 µmol g⁻¹ for the marine brown algae *Turbinana canoides* (Vijayaraghavan, Sathishkumar and Balasubramanian, 2010). Affinity of REEs for *Bacillus subtilis* has been demonstrated to increase with the atomic number, which suggests an enrichment of HREE on the surface of that bacteria (Martinez, Pourret and Takahashi, 2014). The Langmuir isotherm model pointed towards carboxylic groups on the cell wall of bacteria as potential REE adsorption sites.

2.4. Potential environmental impact of REE

2.4.1. Uptake of REE and occurrence in biota

REE are considered non-essential elements but can bioaccumulate in almost all organisms including microorganisms (Tsuruta, 2006), phytoplankton (Ramasamy, Porada and Sillanpää, 2019), zooplankton (MacMillan *et al.*, 2017; MacMillan *et al.*, 2019), benthos (Merschel and Bau, 2015), and other aquatic invertebrates (Amyot *et al.*, 2017; Pastorino *et al.*, 2020). Bioaccumulation of REE seems to be biological species and size (e.g., age) dependent (Merschel and Bau, 2015; Hanana *et al.*, 2017; Perrat *et al.*, 2017; Kazak *et al.*, 2021) and is often related to the surface area of an organism (Palumbo, 1963) and the location (Weltje *et al.*, 2002b). These variations can be explained through the site-specific REE availability and the different feeding pathways (e.g., grazing and filter feeding), as well as exposure routes (Bustamante and Miramand, 2005; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b). Accumulation of the different elements in algae and bacteria reflects the environmental concentrations, and under natural conditions follow the Oddo-

Harkins rule (Weltje *et al.*, 2002b). However, this does not seem apply to crustaceans (González *et al.*, 2015).

Lanthanides are not equally distributed between the shells and soft tissue of bivalves (Weltje *et al.*, 2002b; Akagi and Edanami, 2017; Tijink and Yland, 1998), with the concentrations of REE being up to 10 times higher in the tissues than in the shells (Akagi and Edanami, 2017). Among these soft tissues, the digestive gland of bivalves tends to bioaccumulate the most of REE (Bustamante and Miramand, 2005; Lobel *et al.*, 1991; Perrat *et al.*, 2017). This difference of bioaccumulation among the organs is also present in fish. For instance, La and Gd bioconcentration are known to decrease in the order of internal organs > gills > skeleton > muscle in carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) (Qiang *et al.*, 1994).

REE are also known to bioaccumulate in both micro- and macroalgae (Diniz and Volesky, 2005; Oliveira, Guibal and Garcia, 2012; Yang and Wilkinson, 2018; Ramasamy, Porada and Sillanpää, 2019). Concentration of seven REE in 35 different marine species sampled in China varied from 8.69×10^{-05} to $0.27 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ of dry weight (Hou and Yan, 1998). This accumulation varied with algae species but also with the specific REE or the atomic number. These observations were not consistent with Bingler *et al.* (1989) who found a difference of uptake by the marine diatom *Skeletonema costatum* between light REE (LREE) and the heavy REE (HREE). It was concluded that LREE were preferentially adsorbed or taken up by the algae while HREE showed a stronger affinity for the solution phase.

If a food-borne compound is bioaccumulated, it may also biomagnify, i.e., lead to concentrations in the organisms that increase with the trophic level. Up to now, the biomagnification potential of REE is unclear. On the level of plants and invertebrates, limited potential of biomagnification was found (MacMillan *et al.*, 2017; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b). Others found that the opposite effect dominated, and the metal concentration decreased with trophic level (biodilution) in both freshwater and marine food chains (Liu *et al.*, 2011; Amyot *et al.*, 2017; MacMillan *et al.*, 2017).

La^{3+} was found to adhere to the bacterium *E. coli*, which are commonly used as food organism in bioassays with *C. elegans* (Zhang *et al.*, 2010). Elemental mapping *C. elegans* indicated a dose-dependent manner of accumulation of La. The bioaccumulation of La might mostly be due to the ingestion of high levels of La absorbed to *E. coli*. A huge accumulation of La in *C. elegans* can lead to a distinct elemental imbalance where there is a decline in concentrations of Ca^{2+} , potassium (K^+) and zinc (Zn^{2+}) (Zhang *et al.*, 2010). Several studies have suggested that REEs ions can bind to the binding sites for Ca^{2+} of several proteins in nematodes (Wakabayashi *et al.*, 2016; Fujimori and Jencks, 1990; Burroughs *et al.*, 1994).

Sediment-bound REE are usually considered not to be available but may become so, when sediment particles are ingested by organisms, or when environmental conditions are changed (Mori, 1999). As such, the sediment may be considered a source for REE in water. Benthic fishes have a higher

concentration of REE than pelagic-feeding fish species (Mayfield and Fairbrother, 2015). Benthic fish species are in direct contact with the sediments and can ingest greater amounts of REE from benthic organisms (Mayfield and Fairbrother, 2015; Wang *et al.*, 2019). It was suggested that non-predatory microbenthic invertebrates accumulate more REE than predatory organisms because the most efficient route of assimilation is through the intake of sediment (Pastorino *et al.*, 2020).

However, it remains challenging to replicate identical exposure conditions between laboratory and natural environments, which could explain the discrepancies observed between field and laboratory results. REEs concentrations in organisms seemed to be negatively correlated with trophic level in marine ecosystems. For marine ecosystems REE toxicity also remains nonexistent, which might be explained by the difficulty to experiment with salt water in the case of REEs.

2.4.2. Effect assessment

2.4.2.1. Freshwater conditions

Research on the toxicity of REEs to freshwater organism has been studied more widely among different levels of the aquatic food web in comparison to marine organisms. A variety of studies has investigated both the lethal and sub-lethal effects of the REEs on freshwater organisms. However, there are still knowledge gaps that require further investigation in order to fully understand the ecotoxicological impact of REEs.

2.4.2.1.1. Bacteria

Bacteria have been studied extensively in relation to the biological effects of common trace metals in the aquatic environment. However, there are in comparison relatively few studies on the effect of REE on bacteria even though they are directly exposed to REE enriched water. Although, it is known that microorganisms influence the bioavailability, bioaccessibility, solubility and mobility of metals to some extent. Indeed, bacteria can control the mobility and adsorption of REE contaminated effluents by producing organic matter with a high affinity for REE (Perelomov and Yoshida, 2008). This affinity results in the creation of low-dissolved REE complexes, which notably increase as pH levels decrease in the water (Takahashi *et al.*, 2010; Martinez, Pourret and Takahashi, 2014).

However, it has been found that bacteria are often more sensitive to REE than other microorganisms (e.g., fungi) (Talbert and Johnson, 1967). The toxicity of REE also varies with the element. For instance, Técher *et al.* (2020) characterized the toxic effects of 16 REE on the growth kinetics of *Escherichia coli*. The estimated EC₅₀ indicated that four HREEs (Er to Lu) and Y were the most toxic metals (Table 2-4) with values ranging between 3.00 to 8.30 µM followed by Sc with an EC₅₀ of 1.10 µM (Técher

et al., 2020). EC_{50} of REE of freshwater bacteria are currently rare, while several studies have addressed the effect of REE to marine bacteria, especially *Aliivibrio fischeri* (Weltje *et al.*, 2004; González *et al.*, 2015; Kurvet *et al.*, 2017) (Table 2-5) (**2.4.2.1.1. Bacteria**). The general consensus between the study on freshwater (Técher *et al.*, 2020) and marine bacteria (Weltje *et al.*, 2004; González *et al.*, 2015; Kurvet *et al.*, 2017) studies is that REE could be toxic to microbial cells in a concentration-dependent manner. Both *E. coli* and *A. fischeri* appear to follow the pattern that LREEs are less toxic than HREEs, with the exception of the LREE classified Sc (Técher *et al.*, 2020).

A study found that the LREE inorganic compound La_2O_3 showed antimicrobial activity against the gram-positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus*, but not against the Gram-negative species *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Balusamy *et al.*, 2012). This is in agreement with the study of Técher *et al.* (2020) that LREE were not very toxic to gram-negative bacteria and that there was an interaction between the gram-positive bacterial cell wall and REE toxicity. HREE appeared to have different effects on bacterial activity. It has been demonstrated that Y^{3+} can inhibit the ammonium oxidation rate of bacteria commonly used in wastewater treatment systems (Su *et al.*, 2020). However, this inhibition effect was appearing only at concentrations higher than 1120 μM , suggesting that the ammonium oxidizing bacteria (AOB) and the specific nitrate production rate are particularly resistant to Y^{3+} . Moreover, 300 and 500 μM Gd could temporarily reduce the nitrite production of the gram-negative nitrifying bacterium *Nitrosomonas europaea* (Fujita *et al.*, 2020). Thus, there are indications that elevated Gd concentrations as high as 360 μM do not negatively impact AOB. More studies are needed to determine the toxicity of HREE to different freshwater bacteria and the consequences for the bacterial activity in both wastewater treatment systems and the environment.

2.4.2.1.2. Microalgae

The impact of REE on freshwater algae has been well studied over the last 10 years and different hypotheses have been developed for their toxicity to microalgae. Several studies identified a similar sensitivity to REE among different microalgae species (Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020; Joonas *et al.*, 2017; Tai *et al.*, 2010) (Table 2-4 and Table 2-5). While some studies measured similar toxicity among the REE of microalgae (Tai *et al.*, 2010; Joonas *et al.*, 2017), other studies indicated that REE toxicity was positively correlated with their atomic number (González *et al.*, 2015; Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020). For instance, a stronger sensitivity of *C. vulgaris* to Sm (atomic number = 62, EC_{50} 170 μM) than for La and Nd (atomic number = 57 and 60, respectively, and EC_{50} 340 and 380 μM , respectively) was recorded by Bergsten-Torralba *et al.* (2020). This difference of toxicity could be explained by a difference of biodistribution in

the microalgae cells. Indeed, Řezanka *et al.* (2016) found by fluorescence microscope that La and Gd were biodistributed in the cytoplasm of *Desmodesmus quadricauda* while Nd and Ce were localized in their chloroplasts. Further studies would be necessary to validate this hypothesis.

REE toxicity to algae depends on their high capacity to form complexes and eventually precipitate in the presence of hydroxides, phosphates, and carbonates. REE precipitation as phosphate not only complicates the process of assaying toxicity but also limits the availability of this nutrient for algae, leading to indirect effects on their growth (Goecke and Goecke, 2016; González *et al.*, 2015). Sequestration of nutrients from algal growth media by REE is a phenomenon which has been clearly demonstrated by several authors (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014; González *et al.*, 2015; Tai *et al.*, 2010).

REE presence exhibits intriguing dual effects due to their chemical similarities with certain elements. REE can act as competitors and cause adverse effects on algae. However, REE also have the potential to alleviate Ca deficiency in reacting with Ca^{2+} receptors, influencing algae metabolism (Goecke *et al.*, 2015; Li *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, REE's high affinity to phosphate allows interactions with algal phospholipid cell membranes, leading to metal agglomeration on the membrane surface and potentially induce nutrient deficiencies that hinder growth and photosynthesis (Joonas *et al.*, 2017).

Low concentrations of $NdCl_3$ have been shown to enhance the photosynthetic rate and increase total chlorophyll content, albeit with a decrease in the chlorophyll a/b ratio (Řezanka *et al.*, 2016). Conversely, higher concentrations of $NdCl_3$ inhibit photosynthetic rate, indicating potential consequences for plant growth (Goecke *et al.*, 2015; Joonas *et al.*, 2017).

Furthermore, on *Microcystis aeruginosa*, low doses of La have been observed to promote the production of microcystins (MCs), while high doses decrease this process (Shen *et al.*, 2018; Liu *et al.*, 2020). This modulation was accompanied by significant changes in the ratios of different MC variants. The activation of clathrin-mediated endocytosis by La enables the absorption of essential elements, stimulating algal growth, photosynthesis, and MCs production (Liu *et al.*, 2020). The ability of REE to promote growth at low concentrations has also been shown in other algal species and terrestrial plants (de Oliveira *et al.*, 2015; Ramírez-Olvera *et al.*, 2018; Řezanka *et al.*, 2016), and explains why REE are currently used as fertilizer in some countries such as China (Tommasi *et al.*, 2020).

2.4.2.1.3. Invertebrates

The highest concentrations of REEs are often found at the lower trophic levels, especially in aquatic invertebrates (MacMillan *et al.*, 2017). Aquatic invertebrates are more likely to be directly at risk from REE discharges in aquatic ecosystems because they have been shown to be among the most sensitive

organisms to REEs at the first consumer level compared to other taxonomic groups (Bergsten-Torrallba *et al.*, 2020; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). Although some results indicate that crustaceans are the least sensitive species when using standardized protocols compared to cnidaria, rotifera, algae, and bacteria (González *et al.*, 2015), they are among the most studied aquatic organisms in ecotoxicology.

For instance, the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*, even though not considered as an aquatic organism, has been used very often as a model organism to assess aquatic toxicity because of its easy use, short life cycle, cellular simplicity and sensitivity (Williams and Dusenbery, 1990; Tejada-Benitez and Olivero-Verbel, 2016). Tatara *et al.* (1998) found the LC₅₀ after 24-hour exposure to La for *C. elegans* to be 9.72 µM. However, Zhang *et al.* (2010) found that LaCl₃ had adverse effects on the growth, brood size, and number of eggs in the body, but no mortality occurred. The EC₅₀ for the brood size was 1.42 µM of La, making it the most sensitive endpoint for La exposure (Table 2-4). However, several studies suggested that La, Nd, Pr, and Sc could reduce the body length and brood size of *C. elegans* without causing any mortality (Zhang *et al.*, 2010; Wakabayashi *et al.*, 2016; Xu *et al.*, 2017). Sc and Lu were found to be more toxic than the other REEs (Lan *et al.*, 2023), but less toxic than Cu (Wakabayashi *et al.*, 2016). Suggesting that the two REEs may not have the same mode of action and negative effects as other potentially toxic elements.

Various studies have revealed that neurophysiological processes such as locomotor frequencies of body bends, head thrashes and pharyngeal pumping in *C. elegans* were affected by REE (Xu *et al.*, 2017; Han *et al.*, 2022). Although the life stage of *C. elegans* influences the sensitivity (Han *et al.*, 2022), Wakabayashi, Nojiri and Takahashi-Watanabe (2020) found that a variety of neurons are involved in the REEs avoidance behavior of *C. elegans*. The nematodes use these chemosensory neurons to improve their avoidance behavior to REEs ions. The avoidance toward Y and all Ln was very clear. This was however not the case for Sc; which could be due to the relative high toxicity and permeability of Sc³⁺ in the body of *C. elegans* in comparison with other REEs ions (Wakabayashi *et al.*, 2016; Wakabayashi and Nakano, 2019). The chemosensory system used by *C. elegans* to avoid REE ions is similar to that used for heavy metal ion avoidance. However, the avoidance response for both the REE and heavy metal ions are only partially overlapping, suggesting that the avoidance mechanisms used by *C. elegans* for REE is specific (Wakabayashi, Nojiri and Takahashi-Watanabe, 2020).

There is currently only one study that addressed the environmental toxicity of REE salts through the oligochaete freshwater sludge worm *Tubifex tubifex* express test. Rucki *et al.* (2021) studied the movement inhibition (EC₅₀) of the worms by exposing the worms to all REEs except Sc at five different concentrations for 3 minutes. The acute toxicity for *T. tubifex* shows an EC₅₀ value around 1.11 M for almost all the tested REEs (Table 2-4). This was in comparison with the results found for barium and

cadmium salts, meaning that REEs could be classified as exerting acute toxic effects on the aquatic environment.

REE toxicity to *Daphnia* is also particularly well documented (Table 2-4). However, difference in sensitivity was found between crustaceans' species. For instance, *Hyalella azteca* seems to be more sensitive to REE than *Daphnia spp.* (Vukov, Smith and McGeer, 2016). Contradictory information can be found regarding the difference of toxicity among the REE on *Daphnia*. Several studies suggested a difference of toxicity among these elements on daphnid, with Nd^{3+} appearing to be the most toxic element (Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020; Egler *et al.*, 2023; Ma *et al.*, 2016). In contrast, other studies calculated similar toxicity to daphnids, regardless of the element (Blinova *et al.*, 2018a; Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a). Similar EC_{50} values of $0.02\text{E-}03$ M for Nd, Gd, and Yb were obtained after 48h exposure of *D. magna* (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a). Furthermore, the LC_{50} values calculated for CeCl_3 (8860 μM ; Table 2-4) from the study of Blaise *et al.* (2018) are similar to the results found by the study of Blinova *et al.* (2018a) in the chronic tests with *D. magna*.

Chronic toxicity of REE to crustaceans are currently rare, but the ones available on *Daphnia* has demonstrated that the organisms were by far more sensitive to REE during chronic tests compared with acute tests (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Ma *et al.*, 2016; Blinova *et al.*, 2018a). Only one long-term multigenerational study is so far available (Galdiero *et al.*, 2019). This study suggested that the effect of Ce and Er (3.85 and 2.83 μM , respectively) on *D. magna* both reduced survival, growth, and reproduction. Er also had greater adverse effects than Ce as indicated by the suggested presence of phenotypic adaptation mechanisms (e.g., detoxification) by the decrease of dead organisms at the end of each generation of daphnid.

The different conclusions found in the literature could be due to the use of different chemical form of REE, that seem to have different toxicity to crustaceans (Blinova *et al.*, 2018b). However, it also could be due to a difference of REE speciation (Borgmann *et al.*, 2005; Vukov, Smith and McGeer, 2016; Loveridge, Smith and McGeer, 2021). It has been demonstrated that under the standardized acute test (OECD, 2004), La precipitated more than Gd, leading to a difference of metal biodistribution and toxicity to *D. magna* (Revel *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, studies are now recommending to consider metal speciation and to measure dissolved concentrations when calculating the EC_{50} values (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b). This is in agreement with a study that examined the toxicity to REE on *H. azteca*: Loveridge *et al.* (2021) demonstrated that the presence of organic matter increases the 96h LC_{50} of Tm due to stronger metal complexation. This toxicity for individual REE was found to be similar when tested individually but also in mixtures. This finding contrasts with the results of Hanana *et al.* (2022) that suggest an antagonistic effect of REE mixture (La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm) on *Hydra vulgaris* as these mixtures were less toxic than the sum of

the constituents REE's single toxicities. This implies that La, Ce, Pr, Nd, and Sm compete for the same physiological uptake systems (e.g., calcium channels) but may cause different toxic effects in the organisms. Proving that cnidarians are similar to daphnids in chronic toxicity responses towards REEs.

2.4.2.1.4. Vertebrates

A large number of different effects have been described for fish and the toxicity of REE varied between fish species, the exposed life stage and the type of REE (Máková *et al.*, 2011). Except when studying fish cells (Fleurbaix *et al.*, 2022), toxicity of REE to fish generally increases with their atomic number (Dubé *et al.*, 2019; Hanana *et al.*, 2021; Cui *et al.*, 2012) (Table 2-4). This toxicity can be explained by the similar ionic radius of REEs and Ca^{2+} , creating a competition on the action site and perturbing different cell functions of the organism. Furthermore, REE can affect the *SPARC3* expression which codes for a glycoprotein that binds Ca and participates in the calcium homeostasis (Dubé *et al.*, 2019; Hanana *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, it is consistent with the fact that La can perturb calcium homeostasis in inhibiting calcium influx in killifish (Zimmer, Brix and Wood, 2019).

Five REE chlorides (Ce, Er, Gd, La, Nd and Sm) were found to affected several gene expressions in the liver of juvenile rainbow trout (Dubé *et al.*, 2019). These alterations resulted in various perturbations, such as cell growth arrest, DNA and protein damage, cell proliferation, disturbances in calcium homeostasis and metabolism, as well as disruption of the detoxification pathway mediated by hemoproteins and protein chaperones. Furthermore, Hanana *et al.* (2021) identified that the presence of Dy or Lu activated the xenobiotic detoxification pathways of rainbow trout juveniles. GdCl_3 was found to trigger change in lipid peroxidation (LPO) level, antioxidant gene activity, and oxidative stress in trout hepatocytes (Laville *et al.*, 2004). On the contrary, La did not cause any oxidant stress on glass eels (*Anguilla anguilla*) due to a good protection against ROS activity (Figueiredo *et al.*, 2018).

REE are also known to affect several biological functions in fish causing severe physiological and histological alterations, in a concentration and exposure time-dependent manner (Chen *et al.*, 2020b; Correia *et al.*, 2019; Su *et al.*, 2022; Gong *et al.*, 2021; Cui *et al.*, 2012; Hua *et al.*, 2017). For instance, Nd activated apoptosis pathway in neurons of *Danio rerio* embryos while significant cerebrovascular arrangement structure changes and the cerebrovascular disappearance was observed which could be affected by the autophagy downregulation flux in the cerebrovascular vessels (Chen *et al.*, 2020b). Furthermore, the activity of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) was significantly higher in La^{3+} exposed glass eels, which suggests that La inhibited acetylcholine concentration in the brain of the fish (Figueiredo *et al.*, 2018), leading to neurotoxic effects.

Gills and liver are the vital organs that were studied and appeared to be particularly affected by REE exposure (Correia *et al.*, 2019; Hua *et al.*, 2017). Severe histopathological changes were observed in the gills and liver of rare minnow (*G. rarus*) after 21 days of La exposure, which suggested some metabolic disturbance (gas exchange in the case of the gills)(Hua *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, LaCl₃ had an inhibitory action on mitochondrial energy turnover in the liver of goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) (Wu *et al.*, 2015). These several alterations were accompanied by abnormal behavior of the fish, which could be due to nervous system damage (Hua *et al.*, 2017).

A few studies have investigated the effect REE mixtures on freshwater fish. Exposure for 96h to binary mixtures (Nd, Gd, and Yb) resulted in a notable synergistic effect on the fish cell viability, suggesting that the combined presence of these lanthanides had a greater impact than their individual effects (Fleurbaix *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, additive effects of La and Gd mixtures were observed on *D. rerio* (Kang *et al.*, 2022).

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Table 2-4 Effect concentrations and selected exposure conditions for freshwater organisms. Hyphen (-) indicates missing or incomplete information. e = Embryo, j = Juvenile, 1 = Adopted to current names, L1 = L1 stage of *C. elegans*, L4 = L4 stage of *C. elegans*, cl = cell lines, m = measured concentration, n = nominal concentration. Detailed literature is available at the end of the table.

Species	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (µM)	Interv. effect. conc. (µM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
Bacteria									
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	La	LaCl ₃	7.5h	22.90	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	La	La ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	7.5h	31.00	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ce	CeCl ₃	7.5h	24.40	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Pr	PrCl ₃	7.5h	44.60	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Nd	NdCl ₃	7.5h	24.70	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Sm	SmCl ₃	7.5h	25.80	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Eu	ErCl ₃	7.5h	27.60	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	7.5h	21.40	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Tb	TbCl ₃	7.5h	26.30	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Dy	DyCl ₃	7.5h	24.40	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ho	HoCl ₃	7.5h	24.90	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Er	ErCl ₃	7.5h	16.10	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Tm	TmCl ₃	7.5h	14.60	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	7.5h	5.10	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Lu	LuCl ₃	7.5h	4.20	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Y	YCl ₃	7.5h	16.00	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Sc	ScCl ₃	7.5h	1.50	-	Growth	EC ₅₀	m	[1]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰³	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Sc	ScCl ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ce	CeCl ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Y	Y(NO ₃) ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Pr	PrCl ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Sm	Sm(CH ₃ COO) ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Sm	SmCl ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Eu	Eu(NO ₃) ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Gd	Gd(CH ₃ COO) ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Tb	Tb(CH ₃ COO) ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Tb	TbCl ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Dy	DyCl ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Dy	Dy(CH ₃ COO) ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ho	HoCl ₃	24h	<1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Survival	IC ₅₀	n	[2]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measuremen t type	Reference
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ho	$\text{Ho}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3$	24h	$<1.00 \times 10^{+04}$	-	Survival	IC_{50}	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Er	ErCl_3	24h	$<1.00 \times 10^{+04}$	-	Survival	IC_{50}	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Er	$\text{Er}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3$	24h	$<1.00 \times 10^{+04}$	-	Survival	IC_{50}	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Tm	$\text{Tm}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3$	24h	$<1.00 \times 10^{+04}$	-	Survival	IC_{50}	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Tm	TmCl_3	24h	$<1.00 \times 10^{+04}$	-	Survival	IC_{50}	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Yb	YbCl_3	24h	$<1.00 \times 10^{+04}$	-	Survival	IC_{50}	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Lu	LuCl_3	24h	$<1.00 \times 10^{+04}$	-	Survival	IC_{50}	n	[2]
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Lu	$\text{Lu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3$	24h	$<1.00 \times 10^{+04}$	-	Survival	IC_{50}	n	[2]
Microalgae									
<i>Scenedesmus vacuolatus</i> ¹	Ce	$\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	120h	0.57	0.49 - 0.67	Growth (cell density)	EC_{50}	m	[3]
<i>Scenedesmus vacuolatus</i> ¹	Ce	$\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	120h	0.36	0.26 - 0.50	Growth (cell density)	EC_{20}	m	[3]
<i>Scenedesmus vacuolatus</i> ¹	La	$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	120h	0.78	0.54 - 1.11	Growth (cell density)	EC_{50}	m	[3]
<i>Scenedesmus vacuolatus</i> ¹	La	$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	120h	0.20	0.12 - 0.36	Growth (cell density)	EC_{20}	m	[3]
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	La	La_2O_3	72h	339	326 – 371	Growth (cell density)	IC_{50}	n	[4]
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Nd	Nd_2O_3	72h	382	351 – 429	Growth (cell density)	IC_{50}	n	[4]
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Sm	Sm_2O_3	72h	171	160 – 180–	Growth (cell density)	IC_{50}	n	[4]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i>	La	La_2O_3	72h	372	340 – 417	Growth (cell density)	IC_{50}	n	[4]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i>	Nd	Nd_2O_3	72h	395	354 – 454	Growth (cell density)	IC_{50}	n	[4]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i>	Sm	Sm_2O_3	72h	439	369 – 517	Growth (cell density)	IC_{50}	n	[4]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i> ¹	Ce	CeCl_3	72h	45.10	-	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC_{50}	m	[5]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i> ¹	Gd	GdCl_3	72h	14.10	-	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC_{50}	m	[5]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i> ¹	Lu	LuCl_3	72h	11.90	-	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC_{50}	m	[5]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i> ¹	Ce	CeCl ₃	72h	<45.70	-	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	n	[5]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i> ¹	Gd	GdCl ₃	72h	19.80	-	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	n	[5]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i> ¹	Lu	LuCl ₃	72h	11.80	-	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	n	[5]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i> ¹	Ce	CeCl ₃	72h	0.01	-	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₁₀	m	[5]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i> ¹	Gd	GdCl ₃	72h	0.01	-	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₁₀	m	[5]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i> ¹	Lu	LuCl ₃	72h	0.01	-	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₁₀	m	[5]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	72h	9.14	6.91 - 11.30	Growth (cell density)	EC ₅₀	n	[6]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i>	Ce	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	72h	8.78	7.85 - 9.71	Growth (cell density)	EC ₅₀	n	[6]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i>	Gd	Gd(NO ₃) ₃	72h	7.69	6.42 - 8.90	Growth (cell density)	EC ₅₀	n	[6]
<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i>	Pr	Pr(NO ₃) ₃	72h	9.65	7.24 - 12.10	Growth (cell density)	EC ₅₀	n	[6]
Invertebrates									
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	La	LaCl ₃	72h	14.30	-	Brood size	EC ₅₀	m	[7]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	La	LaCl ₃	72h	>20.00	-	Body length	EC ₅₀	m	[7]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	La	LaCl ₃	72h	>20.00	-	Nr of eggs	EC ₅₀	m	[7]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Nd	NdCl ₃	48h	399	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[8]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Pr	PrCl ₃	48h	636	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[8]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measuremen t type	Reference
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Sc	ScCl ₃	48h	703	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[8]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Nd	NdCl ₃	96h	293	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[8]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Pr	PrCl ₃	96h	199	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[8]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Sc	ScCl ₃	96h	580	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[8]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	24h	9.54x10 ⁺⁰³	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[9]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L1)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	24h	341	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L1)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	48h	215	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L1)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	72h	107	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L1)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	96h	83.80	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L1)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	120h	78.10	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L4)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	24h	3.90	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L4)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	48h	1.50	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L4)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	72h	546	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L4)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	96h	294	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans (L4)</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	120h	183	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	La	LaCl ₃	3min	7.60x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Ce	CeCl ₃	3min	8.52x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Pr	PrCl ₃	3min	7.55x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Nd	NdCl ₃	3min	7.20x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Sm	SmCl ₃	3min	6.89x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Eu	EuCl ₃	3min	7.34x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	3min	7.36x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Tb	TbCl ₃	3min	8.46x10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Dy	DyCl ₃	3min	8.36X10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Ho	LuCl ₃	3min	7.14X10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Er	ErCl ₃	3min	8.27X10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Tm	TmCl ₃	3min	8.25X10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Yb	YCl ₃	3min	8.01X10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Lu	LuCl ₃	3min	8.80X10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	Y	YCl ₃	3min	7.20X10 ⁺⁰⁴	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	21d	3.31	2.74 - 3.82	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Ce	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	21d	2.14	1.64 - 2.57	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Pr	Pr(NO ₃) ₃	21d	2.06	1.49 - 2.70	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	21d	2.15	1.46 - 3.05	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	Gd(NO ₃) ₃	21d	3.12	2.23 - 3.31	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	48h	224	158 – 289	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	48h	144	118 – 171	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	Gd(NO ₃) ₃	48h	118	112 – 123	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Ce	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	48h	188	163 – 213	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Pr	Pr(NO ₃) ₃	48h	169	167 – 170–	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[12]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Ce	CeCl ₃	48h	1.75	0.59 – 6.67–	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[13]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Er	ErCl ₃	48h	1.82	0.56 – 7.71–	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[13]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Ce	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	24h	16.40	13.20 – 20.80–	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	m	[14]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Ce	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	48h	10.70	8.60 – 13.40–	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[14]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	48h	6.24	-	Immobilization	EC ₅	n	[15]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	48h	1.88	-	Immobilization	EC ₅	n	
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	48h	2.06	-	Immobilization	EC ₅	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	48h	13.90	-	Immobilization	EC ₃₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	48h	5.11	-	Immobilization	EC ₃₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	48h	4.90	-	Immobilization	EC ₃₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	48h	20.10	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	48h	7.53	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	48h	7.23	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	48h	25.70	-	Immobilization	EC ₆₅	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	48h	9.95	-	Immobilization	EC ₆₅	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	48h	9.29	-	Immobilization	EC ₆₅	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	48h	30.50	-	Immobilization	EC ₇₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	48h	12.10	-	Immobilization	EC ₇₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	48h	11.40	-	Immobilization	EC ₇₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	9.71	-	Immobilization	EC ₅	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	4.30	-	Immobilization	EC ₅	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	1.29	-	Immobilization	EC ₅	n	[15]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃ DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	21.50	-	Immobilization	EC ₃₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	8.34	-	Immobilization	EC ₃₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	3.87	-	Immobilization	EC ₃₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	29.80	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	10.80	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	5.94	-	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	37.40	-	Immobilization	EC ₆₅	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	13.20	-	Immobilization	EC ₆₅	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	8.26	-	Immobilization	EC ₆₅	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	45.10	-	Immobilization	EC ₇₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	15.30	-	Immobilization	EC ₇₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia magna</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃ + DOM 8 mg C L ⁻¹	48h	10.30	-	Immobilization	EC ₇₀	n	[15]
<i>Daphnia similis</i>	La	La ₂ O ₃	48h	67.70	64.40 – 71.30	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[4]
<i>Daphnia similis</i>	Sm	Sm ₂ O ₃	48h	85.90	83.80 – 108	Immobilization	EC ₅₀	n	[4]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measuremen t type	Reference
<i>Daphnia similis</i>	Sm	Sm ₂ O ₃	48h	149	-	Mortality	EC ₅₀	n	[16]
<i>Daphnia similis</i>	La	La ₂ O ₃	48h	127	-	Mortality	EC ₅₀	n	[16]
<i>Daphnia similis</i>	Nd	Nd ₂ O ₃	48h	176	-	Mortality	EC ₅₀	n	[16]
<i>Daphnia similis</i>	Sm	Sm ₂ O ₃	48h	71.80	-	Mortality	EC ₅₀	n	[16]
<i>Daphnia similis</i>	La	La ₂ O ₃	48h	90.70	-	Mortality	EC ₅₀	n	[16]
<i>Daphnia similis</i>	Nd	Nd ₂ O ₃	48h	63.70	-	Mortality	EC ₅₀	n	[16]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Y	YCl ₃	96h	0.73	0.59 - 0.92	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	La	LaCl ₃	96h	0.57	0.51 - 0.62	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Ce	CeCl ₃	96h	0.89	0.64 - 1.21	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Pr	PrCl ₃	96h	2.26	1.66 - 3.07	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Nd	NdCl ₃	96h	0.86	0.70 - 1.09	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Sm	SmCl ₃	96h	2.11	1.78 - 2.52	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Gd	GdCl ₃	96h	1.40	1.16 - 1.69	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Tb	TbCl ₃	96h	1.87	1.53 - 2.36	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Dy	DyCl ₃	96h	1.83	1.49 - 2.23	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Er	ErCl ₃	96h	1.05	0.84 - 1.49	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Lu	LuCl ₃	96h	0.75	0.57 - 0.92	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Y	YCl ₃	96h	0.10	0.07 - 0.13	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	La	LaCl ₃	96h	0.19	0.14 - 0.24	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Ce	CeCl ₃	96h	0.13	0.08 - 0.19	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Pr	PrCl ₃	96h	0.08	0.06 - 0.10	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Nd	NdCl ₃	96h	0.25	0.17 - 0.36	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measuremen t type	Reference
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Sm	SmCl ₃	96h	0.49	0.36 - 0.69	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Gd	GdCl ₃	96h	0.27	0.19 - 0.40	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Tb	TbCl ₃	96h	0.27	0.19 - 0.38	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Dy	DyCl ₃	96h	0.72	0.58 - 0.85	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Er	ErCl ₃	96h	0.26	0.18 - 0.37	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> ₁	Lu	LuCl ₃	96h	0.26	0.18 - 0.39	Morphological alterations	EC ₅₀	n	[17]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Sc	-	7d	0.65	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Y	-	7d	0.74	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	La	-	7d	0.13	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Ce	-	7d	0.20	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Pr	-	7d	0.25	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Nd	-	7d	0.38	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Sm	-	7d	0.49	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Eu	-	7d	0.74	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Gd	-	7d	0.95	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Tb	-	7d	0.53	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Dy	-	7d	1.00	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Ho	-	7d	0.87	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Er	-	7d	1.14	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Tm	-	7d	<0.01	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Yb	-	7d	0.40	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Lu	-	7d	0.17	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Sc	-	7d	2.22	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Y	-	7d	2.06	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	La	-	7d	1.65	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Ce	-	7d	0.83	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Pr	-	7d	1.30	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Nd	-	7d	2.34	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Sm	-	7d	1.97	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Eu	-	7d	2.67	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Gd	-	7d	2.86	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Tb	-	7d	2.30	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measuremen t type	Reference
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Dy	-	7d	2.98	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Ho	-	7d	3.00	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Er	-	7d	3.34	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Tm	-	7d	4.27	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Yb	-	7d	1.43	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Lu	-	7d	0.69	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Sc	-	7d	3.89	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Y	-	7d	6.18	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	La	-	7d	12.00	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Ce	-	7d	4.14	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Pr	-	7d	3.13	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Nd	-	7d	3.54	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Sm	-	7d	5.63	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Eu	-	7d	4.72	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Gd	-	7d	3.81	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Tb	-	7d	4.36	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Dy	-	7d	5.52	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Ho	-	7d	4.58	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Er	-	7d	5.55	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Tm	-	7d	4.37	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Yb	-	7d	1.61	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Lu	-	7d	6.02	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[18]
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	Tm	-	96h	3.40	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[19]
Vertebrates									
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss (j)</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	96h	50.90	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[20]
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss (j)</i>	Nd	NdCl ₃	96h	416	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[20]
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss (j)</i>	Sm	SmCl ₃	96h	10.60	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[20]
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss (j)</i>	Ce	CeCl ₃	96h	604	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[20]
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss (j)</i>	La	LaCl ₃	96h	864	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[20]
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss (j)</i>	Er	ErCl ₃	96h	47.80	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[20]
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss (j)</i>	Y	YCl ₃	96h	7.87	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[20]

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<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss (j)</i>	Lu	LuCl ₃	96h	4.83	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[21]
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss (j)</i>	Dy	DyCl ₃	96h	29.30	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[21]
<i>Danio rerio (e)</i>	La	LaCl ₃	72h	603	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[22]
<i>Danio rerio (e)</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	72h	268	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[22]
<i>Danio rerio (j)</i>	La	LaCl ₃	144h	637	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[23]
<i>Danio rerio (e)</i>	La	LaCl ₃	144h	624	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[23]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	La	LaCl ₃	96h	864	760 – 969–	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Ce	CeCl ₃	96h	760	663 – 857–	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Pr	Pr(NO ₃) ₃	96h	793	706 – 879–	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	96h	672	567 – 776	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Sm	Sm(NO ₃) ₃	96h	823	696 – 950	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Eu	EuCl ₃	96h	1.05 x10 ⁺⁰³	917 – 1.18 x10 ⁺⁰³	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	96h	849	717 – 981	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Tb	TbCl ₃	96h	1.07x10 ⁺⁰³	865 – 1.27x10 ⁺⁰³	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Dy	Dy(NO ₃) ₃	96h	668	593 – 744	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Ho	HoCl ₃	96h	673	547 - 799	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Er	Er(NO ₃) ₃	96h	480	449 – 512	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Tm	Tm(NO ₃) ₃	96h	501	298 – 705	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	96h	576	488 – 665	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (cl)</i>	Lu	LuCl ₃	96h	242	79.00 – 404	Cell viability	EC ₅₀	n	[24]
<i>Danio rerio (j)</i>	La	LaCl ₃	72h	171	162 – 180	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[25]
<i>Danio rerio (j)</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	72h	149	142 – 156	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[25]
<i>Gobiocypris rarus</i>	La	LaCl ₃	96h	13.80	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	m	[26]
<i>Poecilia reticulata (j)</i>	La	LaCl ₃	144h	523	-	Mortality	LC ₅₀	n	[23]

References: [1] (Técher *et al.*, 2020), [2] (Wakabayashi *et al.*, 2016), [3] (Aharchaou *et al.*, 2020), [4] (Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020), [5] (González *et al.*, 2015), [6] (Joonas *et al.*, 2017), [7] (Zhang *et al.*, 2010), [8] (Xu *et al.*, 2017), [9] (Tatara *et al.*, 1998), [10] (Han *et al.*, 2022), [11] (Rucki *et al.*, 2021), [12] (Blinova *et al.*, 2018a), [13] (Galdiero *et al.*, 2019), [14] (Ma *et al.*, 2016), [15] (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a), [16] (Egler *et al.*, 2023), [17] (Blaise *et al.*, 2018), [18] (Borgmann *et al.*, 2005), [19] (Loveridge, Smith and McGeer, 2021), [20] (Dubé *et al.*, 2019), [21] (Hanana *et al.*, 2021), [22] (Cui *et al.*, 2012), [23] (Máková *et al.*, 2011), [24] (Fleurbaix *et al.*, 2022), [25] (Kang *et al.*, 2022), [26] (Hua *et al.*, 2017).

2.4.2.2. Marine conditions

Research on the toxicity of REEs to marine organisms is limited compared to freshwater environments. While bioaccumulation studies have been conducted, the focus on their toxic effects has been sparse, particularly regarding marine vertebrates. This knowledge gap highlights the need for further investigation to understand the potential risks and ecological implications of REEs in marine ecosystems.

2.4.2.2.1. Bacteria

Most studies that address the effect of REE on marine bacterium focus on the EC₅₀ (Weltje *et al.*, 2004; González *et al.*, 2015; Kurvet *et al.*, 2017) for the naturally luminescent gram-negative bacterium species *Aliivibrio fischeri* (also known as *Vibrio fischeri* and *Photobacterium phosphoreum*). For this organism, the toxicity of REE increases with atomic number (González *et al.*, 2015; Kurvet *et al.*, 2017) (Table 2-5). For instance, González *et al.* (2015) calculated nominal EC₅₀ after 30 minutes of exposure of 18.30 µM for Lu, 47.70 µM for Ce, and 40.70 µM for Gd (Table 2-5). The EC₅₀ for Gd is slightly higher than 22.40 µM estimated by Kurvet *et al.* (2017). These differences can be due to the difference of chemical form used by the two studies (GdCl₃ and Gd(NO₃)₃), as suggested in the freshwater algae chapter **(2.4.2.1.2. Microalgae)**.

It was also hypothesized that the kinetics of the luminescence of the bacteria could act as a good mechanistic toxicity endpoint (Kurvet *et al.*, 2017). Indeed, it reflects the early changes in the bacterial membrane due to the exposure to REEs and the high affinity of REEs to phosphates. According to the acute kinetics of *A. fischeri* bioluminescence, the toxicity of REEs was triggered by disturbing the integrity of the cell membrane. However, both studies Kurvet *et al.* (2017) and González *et al.* (2015) stated that REEs do not appear to have harmful effects on marine bacteria in the current environmental concentrations and forms (e.g., insoluble salts) with exception of hotspots or where peak concentrations appear.

The toxicity of REE to bacteria is particularly sensitive to the presence of organic matter. Indeed it was demonstrated that the effect of Lu on the bioluminescence of *V. fischeri* decreased in the presence of malate oxalate (Weltje *et al.*, 2004). However, this study estimated a low elimination rates of free ion Lu³⁺ and calculated an EC₅₀ after 15 minutes of exposure of 1.57 µM of Lu³⁺. This findings would suggest that Lu is more toxic than bivalent metals such as Cd²⁺ or Zn²⁺ (McCloskey, Newman and Clark, 1996) (Table 2-5). This hypothesis is contrary to many studies that suggested REEs have in general a lower toxicity than Cd, Cu, Pb and Zn for the marine bacteria *A. fischeri* (Newman and McCloskey, 1996).

2.4.2.2.2. Microalgae

The effect on the growth of the marine diatom, *Skeletonema costatum* growth, vary with the REE, leading to different EC₅₀ ranging from 21.90 to 43.20 μM (Tai *et al.*, 2010) (Table 2-5). In this study, the toxicity of a mixed solution containing the same amount of the 13 REE was also studied on *S. costatum* and the EC₅₀ of this mixture was not significantly different to the toxicity of single REE. Similar sensitivity to REE was found among two marine microalgae species such as *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* (Siciliano *et al.*, 2022) or the diatom *S. costatum* (Tai *et al.*, 2010). No interactions on *S. costatum* were identified when REE were in mixture (Tai *et al.*, 2010). However, Sun *et al.* (2019) demonstrated that the toxicity of La(NO₃)₃ varied with the algae species with a nominal EC₅₀ of 23.30 and 13.10 μM for *C. vulgaris* and *P. tricornutum* respectively (Table 2-5). To understand the mechanism of toxicity of REE, fluorescence yield and antioxidant responses were measured on the two microalgae species. The fluorescence of *P. tricornutum* decreased rapidly compared to *C. vulgaris* at the same concentration of La(NO₃)₃.

La exposure increases in a dose-dependent manner, the activity of four enzymes involved in the antioxidant responses of *P. tricornutum* (catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidase (POD) and glutathion (GSH)) (Sun *et al.*, 2019). This study also demonstrated that the destruction of the photosystem II (PS II) and the antioxidant system caused by La(NO₃)₃ are responsible for the growth inhibition in algae. However, after 48h photosynthesis was restored while oxidation stress remained present and affected in a longer term the growth of algae. The oxidant stress and destruction of PS II as a reason for the inhibition of algae growth, would imply the importance to study the impact of REE on essential elements for marine algae, just as it has been done for freshwater algae.

2.4.2.2.3. Invertebrates

Most of the marine invertebrates studied to determine REE toxicity are classified as macrozoobenthos. REE are known to strongly affect sea urchin embryos, and effects vary with the REE, REE concentration, and sea urchin species (Table 2-5) (Gravina *et al.*, 2018; Trifuoggi *et al.*, 2017; Martino *et al.*, 2017; Pagano *et al.*, 2016; Oral *et al.*, 2017). The LC₅₀ of Gd on four different species was compared, out of the four species, *Heliocidaris tuberculata*, that naturally developed a more extensive skeleton, was the most sensitive to Gd exposure (LC₅₀ 5.60×10⁻² μM) compared to *Paracentrotus lixula* who produces a simpler skeleton (LC₅₀ 2.10×10⁺⁰¹ μM) (Martino *et al.*, 2017). Because of ionic radius similarities with Ca²⁺, Gd³⁺ can act as blocker of the divalent channels (Sherry, Caravan and Lenkinski, 2009). If Gd³⁺ blocks the Ca²⁺ channel, it could lead to a calcification response and the development of skeletal abnormalities. Therefore, species with a high need for Ca could be more impacted compared to species which do not

have this need. This high variation of response in the sea urchin species highlighted the importance of evaluating the toxicity of REEs on more than one species.

Most of the studies using sea urchins revealed that embryogenesis damage occurs after REE exposure, such as inhibition of the mitotic activity and increase of the mitotic aberrations (Oral *et al.*, 2017; Pagano *et al.*, 2016), oxidative stress (Pagano *et al.*, 2016) or skeletal abnormalities in sea urchin embryos (Saitoh, Kuroda *et al.* 2010, Martino, Bonaventura *et al.* 2017, Martino, Chiarelli *et al.* 2017, Oral, Pagano *et al.* 2017, Gravina, Pagano *et al.* 2018, Martino, Costa *et al.* 2018).

Bivalves are also macrozoobenthic organisms commonly used to study REE toxicity for marine invertebrates. Ecotoxicity tests on embryos and juveniles oyster *Crassostrea gigas* (Moreira *et al.*, 2020) and the mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (Mestre *et al.*, 2019) showed that La exerted significantly higher toxicity than Y. The La toxicity for *C. gigas* had an EC₅₀ of 4.82×10^{-2} μM after 24h and 0.26 μM after 48 h.. The EC₅₀ for Y was at 24h 1.65 μM and at 48h 2.50 μM (Table 2-5). Thus, La is more toxic for the developing embryos than Y in the case of *C. gigas* (Moreira *et al.*, 2020). Although, La was found to be more toxic compared to Y to the developing embryos of *M. galloprovincialis* than to juveniles, Y appeared to be more toxic to juveniles compared to embryos (Mestre *et al.*, 2019). The toxicity levels of a REE can vary by a factor of 100 for the different life-cycle stages of these bivalves (Mestre *et al.*, 2019). However, more ecotoxicological data on macrozoobenthos will be needed to further develop ecological risk assessment of REEs, which should not only be limited to EC₅₀ but also for example development or metabolic and oxidative stress.

Several studies have already measured the capacity of REEs to trigger oxidant stress through lipid peroxidation levels (LPO). The marine bivalve *M. galloprovincialis* showed significantly higher levels of LPO when exposed to Gd in comparison to control organisms (Henriques *et al.*, 2019; Trapasso *et al.*, 2021b; Andrade *et al.*, 2022b). Similar results were found for this bivalve species when exposed to Nd (Freitas *et al.*, 2020b) and Dy (Freitas *et al.*, 2020a). LPO levels significantly decreased in *M. galloprovincialis* when exposed to La (Pinto *et al.*, 2019). Although Andrade *et al.* (2022a) found that La did increase LPO levels after 28 days of exposure at 7.20×10^{-8} M. For Tb no cellular damages on the lipids were found in *M. galloprovincialis* regardless of the concentrations tested up to 0.25 μM for 28 days (Andrade *et al.*, 2023).

Further research might be necessary on the effect of REEs in combination with multiple stressors like climate change for example. Several studies have found that La and Gd in combination with other climate related stressors, like increased temperatures and variable salinities, caused an increase in metabolic depression, GSTs (Glutathione S-transferases) activation, antioxidant enzyme inhibition, and higher LPO levels in *M. galloprovincialis* and *Spisula solida* (Andrade *et al.*, 2022a; Andrade *et al.*, 2022b; Figueiredo *et al.*, 2022; Andrade *et al.*, 2023; Andrade *et al.*, 2021).

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Table 2-5 - Effect concentrations and selected exposure conditions for marine organisms. Hyphen (-) indicates missing or incomplete information. e = Embryo, j = Juvenile, 1 = Adopted to current names, m = measured concentration, n = nominal concentration. Detailed literature is available at the end of the table.

Species	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (µM)	Interv. effect. conc. (µM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
Bacteria									
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Ce	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	30min	15.40	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[1]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Gd	Gd(NO ₃) ₃	30min	7.82	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[1]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	30min	48.30	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[1]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	30min	15.70	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[1]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Pr	Pr(NO ₃) ₃	30min	28	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[1]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Ce	CeCl ₃	30min	>17.20	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Gd	GdCl ₃	30min	>17.20	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Lu	LuCl ₃	30min	8.22	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[2]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Lu	LuCl ₃	30min	5.24	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	m	[2]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Ce	CeCl ₃	30min	9.40x10 ⁻⁰³	-	Luminescence	EC ₁₀	m	[2]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Gd	Gd(NO ₃) ₃	30min	2.70x10 ⁻⁰³	-	Luminescence	EC ₁₀	m	[2]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Lu	LuCl ₃	30min	2.00x10 ⁻⁰⁴	-	Luminescence	EC ₁₀	m	[2]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Lu	Lu ³⁺ no ligand	7.5min	2.16	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[3]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Lu	Lu ³⁺ no ligand	15min	1.57	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[3]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Lu	Lu ³⁺ no ligand	22.5min	1.44	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[3]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	Lu	Lu ³⁺ no ligand	30min	1.37	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[3]
<i>Aliivibrio fischeri</i> ¹	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	15min	1.69 x10 ⁺⁰³	-	Luminescence	EC ₅₀	n	[4]
Microalgae									
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	96h	23.30	-	Growth yield	EC ₅₀	n	[5]
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	96h	14.80	-	Growth yield	EC ₂₀	n	[5]
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	96h	7.55	-	Growth yield	EC ₁₀	n	[5]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>			96h	13.10	-				[5]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃				Growth yield	EC ₅₀	n	
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>			96h	5.27	-				[5]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃				Growth yield	EC ₂₀	n	
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>			96h	2.91	-				[5]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>				17.70	6.26 - 52.80	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₁₀	n	
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>	La	La(NO ₃) ₃	72h						[6]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>				19.90	7.63 - 48.80	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	m	[6]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>	Eu	Eu(NO ₃) ₃	72h						[6]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>				10.90	2.28 - 55.30	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	m	[6]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricorutum</i>	Ce	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	72h						[6]

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Species	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (µM)	Interv. effect. conc. (µM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>	Gd	Gd(NO ₃) ₃	72h	6.23	2.35 - 17	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	m	[6]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>	Nd	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	72h	22.10	14.50 - 33.80	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	m	[6]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>	Dy	Dy(NO ₃) ₃	72h	24.70	10.30 - 59.70	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	m	[6]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>	Sm	Sm(NO ₃) ₃	72h	87.90	6.85 - 920	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	m	[6]
<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>	Er	Er(NO ₃) ₃	72h	9.27	49.00 - 49	Growth (fluorescence activity)	EC ₅₀	m	[6]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	La	LaCl ₃	72h	29.20	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Ce	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	72h	29.70	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Nd	NdCl ₃	72h	30.30	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Sm	SmCl ₃	72h	28.70	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Eu	Eu(NO ₃) ₃	72h	29.20	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Gd	Gd(NO ₃) ₃	72h	29.80	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Tb	TbCl ₃	72h	28.50	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Dy	DyCl ₃	72h	28.30	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Ho	HoCl ₃	72h	29.30	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Er	Er(NO ₃) ₃	72h	28.70	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Tm	TmCl ₃	72h	28.80	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	72h	28.50	-	Growth: Cell density	EC ₅₀	n	[7]

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Species	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Lu	LuCl_3	72h	28.60	-	Growth: Cell density	EC_{50}	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Sc	ScCl_3	72h	21.90	-	Growth: Cell density	EC_{50}	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Y	$\text{Y}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	72h	43.20	-	Growth: Cell density	EC_{50}	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	La	LaCl_3	96h	29.20	-	Growth: Cell density	EC_{50}	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Y	$\text{Y}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	96h	43.20	-	Growth: Cell density	EC_{50}	n	[7]
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Sc	ScCl_3	96h	21.90	-	Growth: Cell density	EC_{50}	n	[7]
Invertebrates									
<i>Arbacia lixula (e)</i>	Gd	$\text{Gd}(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_3$	48hpf	2.10	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	n	[8]
<i>Arbacia lixula (e)</i>	Y	YCl_3	72hpf	4.00	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Arbacia lixula (e)</i>	La	LaCl_3	72hpf	15.50	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Arbacia lixula (e)</i>	Ce	CeCl_3	72hpf	1.90	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Arbacia lixula (e)</i>	Nd	NdCl_3	72hpf	1.50	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Arbacia lixula (e)</i>	Sm	SmCl_3	72hpf	1.91	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Arbacia lixula (e)</i>	Eu	EuCl_3	72hpf	1.47	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Arbacia lixula (e)</i>	Gd	GdCl_3	72hpf	1.55	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Centrostephanus rogersii (e)</i>	Gd	$\text{Gd}(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_3$	48hpf	132	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	n	[8]
<i>Heliocidaris tuberculata (e)</i>	Gd	$\text{Gd}(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_3$	48hpf	56.00	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	n	[8]
<i>Paracentrotus lividus (e)</i>	Gd	$\text{Gd}(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_3$	48hpf	1.18	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	n	[8]
<i>Paracentrotus lividus (e)</i>	Y	YCl_3	72hpf	0.79	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Paracentrotus lividus (e)</i>	La	LaCl_3	72hpf	0.66	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Paracentrotus lividus (e)</i>	Ce	CeCl_3	72hpf	5.30	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Paracentrotus lividus (e)</i>	Nd	NdCl_3	72hpf	1.51	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Paracentrotus lividus (e)</i>	Sm	SmCl_3	72hpf	$4.84 \times 10^{+07}$	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]
<i>Paracentrotus lividus (e)</i>	Eu	EuCl_3	72hpf	1.96	-	Embryotoxicity	EC_{50}	m	[9]

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Species	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (µM)	Interv. effect. conc. (µM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
<i>Paracentrotus lividus (e)</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	72hpf	0.20	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	m	[9]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Ce	CeCl ₃	48hpf	13.00	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Dy	DyCl ₃	48hpf	1.60	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Er	ErCl ₃	48hpf	0.70	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	48hpf	0.90	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Ho	HoCl ₃	48hpf	1.90	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Lu	LuCl ₃	48hpf	1.80	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Yb	YbCl ₃	48hpf	4.50	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	n	[10]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Y	YCl ₃	72hpf	0.47	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	m	[9]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	La	LaCl ₃	72hpf	0.06	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	m	[9]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Ce	CeCl ₃	72hpf	1.33	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	m	[9]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Nd	NdCl ₃	72hpf	1.70	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	m	[9]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Sm	SmCl ₃	72hpf	0.41	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	m	[9]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Eu	EuCl ₃	72hpf	0.96	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	m	[9]
<i>Sphaerechinus granularis (e)</i>	Gd	GdCl ₃	72hpf	5.56	-	Embryotoxicity	EC ₅₀	m	[9]
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis (e)</i>	La	LaCl ₃	96h	0.14	-	Embryo development	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis (e)</i>	Y	YCl ₃	96h	2.64	-	Embryo development	EC ₅₀	n	[11]
<i>Crassostrea gigas (e)</i>	La	La ₂ O ₃	24h	0.05	-	Embryo development	EC ₅₀	m	[12]
<i>Crassostrea gigas (e)</i>	La	La ₂ O ₃	48h	0.23	-	Embryo development	EC ₅₀	m	[12]

CHAPTER 2

<i>Species</i>	REE Species	Compound	Exposure time	Effect. conc. (μM)	Interv. effect. conc. (μM)	Endpoint biological	Endpoint	Measurement type	Reference
<i>Crassostrea gigas</i> (e)	Y	Y ₂ O ₃	24h	1.65	-	Embryo development	EC ₅₀	m	[12]
<i>Crassostrea gigas</i> (e)	Y	Y ₂ O ₃	48h	2.50	-	Embryo development	EC ₅₀	m	[12]

References : [1] (Kurvek *et al.*, 2017), [2] (González *et al.*, 2015), [3] (Weltje *et al.*, 2004), [4] (McCloskey, Newman and Clark, 1996), [5] (Sun *et al.*, 2019), [6] (Siciliano *et al.*, 2022), [7] (Tai *et al.*, 2010), [8] (Martino *et al.*, 2017), [9] (Trifuoggi *et al.*, 2017), [10] (Gravina *et al.*, 2018), [11] (Mestre *et al.*, 2019), [12] (Moreira *et al.*, 2020).

2.4.2.3. Effects from exposure to REE in Sediment

Anthropogenic REE anomalies in sediments can reach high concentrations (Table 2-2), as ions in the water phase adsorb to particle surfaces and solid complexes are formed and deposited. In experiments with microcosms, it was found that after 12 hours more than 80% of the spiked REE (La, Ce, Sm, Gd, Y) were in the sediments (Yang *et al.*, 1999). Metal uptake with food particles seems to be an important exposure pathway for benthic organisms and collector-gatherers among macrobenthic invertebrates have been suggested as good tracers of REE in freshwater systems (Pastorino *et al.*, 2020). While bioaccumulation of REE from sediments has been studied frequently (**2.4.1. Uptake of REE and occurrence in biota**), information on the toxicity of REE in sediments remains to be rare.

A number of studies have demonstrated elevated toxicities in REE-contaminated environmental sediment samples (Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2018; Dickman and Rygiel, 1996), concluding on the relative toxicity of REE is even more difficult than in water samples due to the commonly large number of potential contaminants in sediments with different sorption kinetics, and due to the complexity of sediment geochemistry. Toxicity-testing of spiked sediments would facilitate understanding of cause-effect relationships (US EPA, 2000), but in the case of REE, it has been restricted to three studies which were all performed with La and all carried out on behalf of a company (Grace GmbH & Co. KG. Worms) and are thus not freely available.

Most of the macrozoobenthos species are exposed to REE through sediments due to the high adsorption of metal to sediment particles (Tijink and Yland, 1998; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b) and fine organic matter (Schaller, 2013). The accumulation of REE is in general higher in benthic invertebrates compared to other species (MacMillan *et al.*, 2017; Amyot *et al.*, 2017). Two studies, Hanana *et al.* (2017) and Hanana *et al.* (2018), found that there was no significant change in LPO levels in the freshwater zebra mussel *Dreissena polymorpha* after 28 days of exposure to Gd, Sm, and Y. Although the levels of LPO were not significant for Gd there was still a mild increase observed for 37.90 and 0.19 μM (Hanana *et al.*, 2017). These findings suggest that REEs can induce cellular damage, which may compromise the physiological performance (e.g., growth and reproduction success) of freshwater bivalves. There might be an inter species difference for REE toxicity and a comparison with marine bivalves should be carefully approached as the toxicodynamic of REE can differ due to salinity differences. Although the toxicodynamic of REE and salinity is not yet fully understood.

Other tests have been performed with benthic organisms but with exposure to water only (e.g., (Zhang *et al.*, 2015; Mestre *et al.*, 2019; Rucki *et al.*, 2021)). The challenges, when carrying out and interpreting sediment toxicity data, are to be aware of confounding factors that can alter the bioavailability and thus the toxicity of REE. The impact of physicochemical properties of sediments and media

composition on results of sediment contact tests was clearly demonstrated when testing sediments with naturally elevated REE concentrations (Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2018). A study that investigated the influence of soil composition with REE and heavy metal co-contamination. They found that shifts in microbial communities does depend on both the metal contamination and the physiochemical properties of soil (Luo *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the physiochemical properties of soils and sediments in combination with REE can have major implications for ecological risk assessment.

2.5. Concluding: Critical parameters and potential pitfalls in bioassays with REEs

Rare earth elements as high-technology metals are increasingly used and emitted to the environment. Due to the wide range of geogenic background concentrations in water and sediment (Table 2-1), anthropogenically elevated concentrations (Table 2-2) often are within the potential natural range but considerably exceed the natural median values. This gives rise to concerns regarding their potential impact on biological communities. REE are taken up by bacteria, algae and plants, invertebrates, and fish but too little is known yet about the species-specific toxicodynamics of the elements to relate elevated tissue concentrations to toxicity. Evidence points to the chemical similarity of REE³⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions as an important cause for cytological effects, and La³⁺ is an efficient Ca-channel blocker. Oxidative stress and impairment of gene expression have also been demonstrated for various rare earths, but most of the mechanisms of action for effects remain to be elucidated.

Experimental bioassays with REE which could serve to study cause-effect relationships have resulted in EC₅₀ values which partly differed by several orders of magnitude - even with the same biological species and for a specific REE (e.g., EC₅₀ for *A. fischeri*: 48 µM of La (Kurvet *et al.*, 2017) compared to 1690 µM of La (McCloskey, Newman and Clark, 1996); EC₅₀ for *R. subcapitata*: 9.14 µM of La (Joonas *et al.*, 2017) compared to 372 µM of La (Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020). Aside from the fact that different endpoints, exposure durations, and the use of different REE salts can complicate the comparison of bioassay results, rare earth bioassays present a number of obstacles, and interpretation of the data requires special attention; a number of aspects are discussed below.

Complex formation in the presence of carbonates, phosphates, and hydroxides: As indicated by their high complex stability constants, REE form especially strong complexes with carbonates, phosphates, and hydroxides, leading to precipitation. Carbonates are often used in test media for bioassays with algae and daphnids as buffers. Phosphates are usually needed in bioassays with algae as inorganic nutrient. In combination with REE, complexes are formed and the concentration of free REE ions as well as nutrients

is reduced. Whether this has led to an overestimation of REE toxicity in the past by confusing the effect of nutrient limitation with the effect of metals, or whether complex formation has masked the toxic potential of REE, should be investigated in the future.

The impact of water hardness: REE are similarly affected by these confounding factors as other metals. Concentrations of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions in water have been shown to influence the toxicity of many divalent metals (Pascoe, Evans and Woodworth, 1986; Borgmann *et al.*, 2005), and this has also been shown for REE^{3+} . Barry and Meehan (2000) reported marked differences in La toxicity to *D. carinata* by 2 orders of magnitude based on the water hardness, with a 48h EC_{50} of 0.31, 0.35, and 8.49 μM of La for water with a hardness of 220, 979, and 1600 μM of CaCO_3 , respectively. Lower toxicity at increasing water hardness may be caused by competition of REE^{3+} and Ca^{2+} for the same binding sites or by the decrease of potentially bioavailable species such as La^{3+} or LaOH^{2+} through carbonate complexation (Moermond *et al.*, 2001). A linear dependency of REE toxicity to water hardness, however, still has to be shown (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016).

Influence of pH and use of buffer: pH strongly affects the bioavailability of REEs. Consequently, accurate measurement and maintenance of pH levels become imperative in ensuring the consistency of toxicity studies. Organisms such as microalgae can absorb CO_2 and secrete metabolites affecting the aquatic environmental pH (Wu *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, buffering agents are commonly employed in ecotoxicological bioassays to maintain a constant pH. When performing bioassays, the suitability of the pH buffer used should be considered. A study with Eu(III) indicated that the pH buffers' ability to form complexes with the metal varied significantly, with MOPS (3-(N-morpholino)propane sulfonic acid) exhibiting the highest capacity. In contrast, TRIS (tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane) had no significant interaction with Eu(III) while the other buffers did (Mandal, Kretzschmar and Drobot, 2022). However, metal-buffer complexation should not be the only factor to be considered when deciding the best fitting pH-buffer. For example, it has been demonstrated that test media buffered with NaHCO_3 increased the toxicity of copper and zinc for algae, while no differences in metal toxicity were observed for the pH buffers MOPS and HCl (De Schamphelaere, Heijerick and Janssen, 2004). However, metal sensitivity can also be altered when buffers are at higher concentrations than the NOEC (no-observed-effect concentration), as the buffer can disturb the physiology of organisms (De Schamphelaere, Heijerick and Janssen, 2004). Biological effects and metal-buffer complexation should both be taken into account (Ferreira *et al.*, 2015).

Role of DOM on REEs toxicity: Studying the effects of DOM on metal bioavailability and toxicity is important as organic matter is ubiquitous in natural environments. Low DOM concentration can increase the solubility of REEs (Choppin 1986; McCarthy, Sanford, and Stafford 1998), while high concentrations can reduce the bioaccumulation and toxicity of REE (Lachaux et al. 2022; Tang and Johannesson 2003; Vukov, Smith, and McGeer 2016; El-Akl, Smith, and Wilkinson 2015). Thus, DOM should be considered when assessing the toxicity of REE due to its influence on the bioavailability of the metals. There seems to be a big gap in the knowledge of DOM on REE, especially when testing with DOM could enhance the environmental realism of bioassays. Most studies do not consider biological processes such as the excretion of organisms or the exudate formation by algae during biotests, and the presence of feces in natural ecosystems. There also appears to be a gap in the understanding of the effect of DOM on REE toxicity for chronic exposures, as most studies on DOM are currently focused on acute exposure (Lachaux et al. 2023; Lachaux et al. 2022; Vukov, Smith, and McGeer 2016).

REEs in mixtures: REEs are rarely present as single elements in natural environment which is why studying their behavior and toxicity in mixtures is important. When in mixtures, REE bio-uptake tend to decrease due to an increase of competition for the same biotic ligand (Aharchaou *et al.*, 2020; Yang *et al.*, 2014). Studies have obtained varied effects for REEs when they are combined with additive effects (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b; Tai *et al.*, 2010). Moreover, synergistic effect were recorded on fish cells, bacteria and algae (Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2018; Fleurbaix *et al.*, 2022) while an antagonistic effect was reported on rotifers (Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2018) when exposed to REE mixtures. The underlying mechanisms or biological explanations for these antagonistic or synergistic effects remain to be fully elucidated.

Adsorption of REE: The adsorption of lanthanides to different surfaces has been studied in several studies (Weltje *et al.*, 2002a; Eichholz, Nagel and Hughes, 1965). For La, glass surfaces can adsorb up to 25% of the total concentration (Weltje *et al.*, 2002a), and it is thus recommended to avoid glass when performing bioassay experiments. Therefore, it would be recommended to use materials such as PET (polyethylene terephthalate), polycarbonate, or nylon (Reimann, Birke and Filzmoser, 2010; Weltje, den Hollander and Wolterbeek, 2003; Bau *et al.*, 2010). However, the knowledge on which materials and what specific material treatment is required to prevent REE adsorption on experimental vessels is currently limited. Even when using less adsorbing REE vessels during experiments REE can still adsorb strongly to organic surfaces such as sediments, organisms, and DOM (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018; Vijayaraghavan *et al.*, 2009; Birungi and

Chirwa, 2014; Das, Sharma and Talukder, 1988; Martinez *et al.*, 2018; Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b). The adsorption of REE can have impact in how we evaluate the toxicity of REEs in our ecosystems.

Quantifying exposure conditions: Considering that for La the dissolved EC_{50s} (Siciliano *et al.*, 2022) have been found to be four times higher than the nominal EC_{50s} (Sun *et al.*, 2019) for microalgae. Several studies have pointed out the importance of considering measured concentrations over nominal concentrations. The issue is that in order to use measured concentrations we need a good understanding of the chemical speciation of REE before performing the experiments. In addition, determining the dissolved concentrations is often very time consuming, expensive, and there is a lack of understanding of the kinetics involved in precipitation and an understanding of the cause-effect relationship for the different chemical species on organisms.

With the increase in use of REEs there has also been an increase in scientific scrutiny of the metals in various research fields. There is a need to have a deep knowledge of the biochemical and physical processes, environmental behavior, and fate of REE in freshwater, marine, and sediment environments. The comparison and interpretation of REE toxicity data is also often complicated even more due to other confounding factors such as pH, metal precipitation, adsorption, and exposure routes. The limited knowledge on chemical speciation and the interactions of REE with a wide range of biological systems, such as bacteria, microalgae, invertebrates, and vertebrates call for more systematic studies. We recommend that more ecotoxicological research is performed on a wide variety of biological species across all levels of both the aquatic and marine ecosystems, while taking biochemical and physical processes into consideration, paying special attention to the pitfalls and critical parameters when bio-testing rare earth elements. Not only are individual bioassays essential here but also further development across ecosystem levels and services. However, vertebrate studies should be limited as much as possible for animal welfare reasons. Most studies have focused on the nominal concentrations of La, Gd, and Ce. While there is also a need to look further into the mode of action of these lanthanides, the other REEs should also be included in further studies. It will be fundamental for the accurate performance of risk assessment to consider not only the nominal but also the measured concentrations of REE for both acute and chronic ecotoxicological determination.

Author contribution

Author contribution is in alphabetical order of surname. Conceptualization was done by Marion Revel and Chantal van Drimmelen. Most papers were collected and analysed by Marion Revel and Chantal van Drimmelen. The quality of the papers was checked by Chantal van Drimmelen. Original draft was written by Marion Revel (Chapters on Speciation, Adsorption, Freshwater microalgae, Freshwater vertebrates, Marine microalgae, Marine invertebrates, and Marine vertebrates), Susanne Heise (Chapters on Introduction, Natural occurrence and anthropogenic emissions to the aquatic environment), Chantal van Drimmelen (Abstract and the chapters on Uptake of REE and occurrence in biota, Freshwater bacteria, Freshwater invertebrates, Marine bacteria, Effects upon exposure to REE in sediment), and Lennart Weltje (various parts in chapters). The discussion and conclusion were conceptualized by Susanne Heise, and then written out by Marion Revel (Role of DOM on REEs toxicity, Influence of pH and use of buffer, REE in mixtures), Susanne Heise (Introduction, Complex formation, The impact of water hardness) and Chantal van Drimmelen (introduction, Adsorption of Ln, Conclusion). Andrew Hursthouse and Chantal van Drimmelen, conceptualized and analysed the data for the visual abstract. It was then reviewed, expanded, and edited by Marion Revel, Susanne Heise, Andrew Hursthouse, Chantal van Drimmelen, and Lennart Weltje.

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subcapitata

03.22 COD

C. vulgaris

14.03.22 LST

S. VA

14.0

CHAPTER 3

DOES PHOSPHATE MASK TOXICITY OF TWO REE FOR DIFFERENT MICROALGAE SPECIES?

Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen^{1,2,∞}, Marion Revel^{1,2,∞}, Andrew S. Hursthouse², Susanne Heise¹

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¹ Life Sciences, Hamburg University of Applied Science, Ulmenliet 20, D-21033 Hamburg, Germany

² University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

[∞] Equal contribution as first authors

Abstract

Assessing the toxicity of Rare Earth Elements (REEs) is challenging due to their tendency to precipitate with environmentally common chemical species, such as phosphate. For microalgae, which depend on phosphate, metal complexation with phosphate could induce nutrient deficiency and lead to growth and biomass inhibition. Therefore, it is yet unclear if the toxicity of REEs that has been measured in bioassays with microalgae stems from direct metal effects or phosphate-induced limitations. Consequently, this study aimed to assess the growth inhibition effects of two common REEs, lanthanum (La) and gadolinium (Gd), on three microalgae species—*Raphidocelis subcapitata*, *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Scenedesmus vacuolatus*—Using three media with distinct phosphate sources: ISO (with inorganic phosphate as per standardized tests), ISO-G1P (substituting inorganic phosphate with organic one), and phosphate-free MHSM. All EC₅₀ showed divergent outcomes based on metal type, media, and algal species. For instance, toxicity effects in ISO medium were limited for both metals while 100% biomass inhibition was recorded in the MHSM medium. In contrast, the ISO-G1P showed a higher maximum inhibition effect compared to the ISO but lower than for the MHSM. These results suggested that the difference of toxicity was related to the potential for metal to complex with ligands such as phosphate. The inorganic phosphate led to lower toxicity of REE on microalgae compared to the organic phosphate. In contrast, the absence of phosphate led to a significantly higher toxicity for La and Gd. Additionally,

measured dissolved concentration and toxicity were correlated with both metals, spanning all media, and confirming that toxicity primarily depends on metal bioavailability over nutrient limitation. The study also revealed significant variations in metal sensitivity among the three algal species, emphasizing the need to integrate chemical speciation and consider interspecies sensitivity variations in standardized toxicity tests.

3.1. Introduction

Since the first publication in 1947 (Meggers, 1947), the general research on Rare Earth Elements (REE) has been exponentially growing (Kang and Kang, 2020). Their application in green and sustainable technology as well as their wider use in society mean an increase in the global demand and in discharges of REE into aquatic environments (Cobelo-García *et al.*, 2015; Klaver *et al.*, 2014). Large positive gadolinium (Gd) anomalies due to hospital effluents in rivers have been identified by Bau and Dulski (1996). They found that Gd concentrations were three orders of magnitude higher than the geogenic background values. Since then, both lanthanum (La) and gadolinium anomalies have been reported in surface water worldwide, originating from anthropogenic inputs (Klaver *et al.*, 2014). The REE are now labelled as “emergent” contaminants due to their apparent disruption of biogeochemical cycles, especially in aquatic ecosystems (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Blinova *et al.*, 2020).

Few studies have addressed the toxicity of REE for different microalgae (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016), of which two use comparable incubation time (72h) and measured endpoints (cell density, growth) (Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020; Joonas *et al.*, 2017). Results for *Raphidocelis subcapitata* differ by one order of magnitude between studies and less for exposure to different REE. Most studies focus on two common species *R. subcapitata* and *Chlorella vulgaris* (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Joonas *et al.*, 2017; Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020), and toxicity tests have yet to be performed with other algal groups and species (Guida, Siciliano and Pagano, 2017).

Performing toxicity experiments are complicated due to the strong potential of REE to precipitate or complex with ligands (González *et al.*, 2015). The high affinity of REE for phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) might cause the complex formation of REE- PO_4 which precipitates in test medium (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). Strong affinity of REE with phosphate makes toxicity testing particularly problematic for microalgae biotests. Indeed, precipitation of REE with PO_4^{3-} , could induce nutrient limitation in microalgae (Goecke *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, it is unclear whether inhibition growth recorded in bioassay comes from direct REEs effects or phosphate-induced limitations (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b). To avoid phosphate precipitation, Aharchaou *et al.* (2020) studied the REE toxicity on other microalgae species, *Scenedesmus vacuolatus* (formally known as *Chlorella fusca*). This species can accumulate and store PO_4^{3-} in order to survive phosphate limitation (Kessler, 1976). However, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO, 2012) recommends two species to use for the algae growth inhibition test. One of them is *R. subcapitata*. They also acknowledge that the reactions to toxic ingredients are not identical for the two species. If phosphate limitation can cause toxic impacts in bioassays with REE, and algae show different phosphate requirements, this should result in different sensitivities of the respective algae species to the metals. To confound this, the

precipitation of REE-PO₄ could mask a toxic potential of REE by reducing the concentration of free REE ions.

Hence, the objective of the study presented here is to identify whether toxicity of La and Gd is caused by free metal ions or by phosphate-limitation. The study focused on the variability of the sensitivity of different algal species and the implication this may have for regulatory risk assessment. The hypothesis is that there is a similar sensitivity towards the two metals as the mode of action of REE is assumed to be similar (Joonas *et al.*, 2017). It is also anticipated that a strong difference in sensitivity among species will occur with *S. vacuolatus* having the lowest sensitivity. As it will be least affected by phosphate limitation as a consequence of REE-PO₄-complex formation, due to the lower phosphate requirement through the ability of *S. vacuolatus* to store phosphate. (Aharchaou *et al.*, 2020; Kessler, 1976). Which allows for the comparison of a limited-phosphate sensitive algae species with other algae species, *R. subcapitata* and *C. vulgaris*, that cannot survive in exposure media without phosphate being present in sufficient levels.

3.2. Materials and Methods

3.2.1. Algae cultures

Three freshwater microalgae species obtained from the Culture Collection of Algae at the University of Göttingen (SAG) were used for this experiment. *Raphidocelis subcapitata* (SAG Strain Number: 61.81) and *Chlorella vulgaris* (SAG 211-11b), two common species used in ecotoxicology laboratories, and *Scenedesmus vacuolatus* (SAG 211-15). *S. vacuolatus* is known for its ability to accumulate and store PO₄³⁻ in order to survive phosphate limitation for up to several days (Kuesel *et al.*, 1989). This makes *S. vacuolatus* an interesting species to test REE toxicity which are prone to form complexes with PO₄³⁻. The three strain cultures are maintained at 20 ± 1°C and with a lighting intensity between 6000 lx and 10 000 lx (Osram) and a light cycle of 8:16.

3.2.2. Media preparations

Four different media were studied for this experiment, ISO media from the international guideline (ISO, 2012) contains 1.17E-05 mol L⁻¹ of inorganic phosphate which can complex with REE and reduce its toxicity. In addition, the ISO media was modified, where the inorganic phosphate (PO₄³⁻) was replaced by an organic phosphate; ISO-G1P (containing α-glucose 1-phosphate, >95% purity; Sigma Aldrich). The third media (MHSM-2) used in this study was originally developed by Sueoka, Chiang and Kates (1967), is a modified high salt media used in a REE study by Aharchaou *et al.* (2020). This was chosen because of the absence of phosphate, making it ideal to study the toxicity of REE. All media were prepared a day before use to allow the carbonate buffer to settle.

3.2.3. Algae growth inhibition test

Toxicities of Gd and La in each media and for all microalgae species were determined by applying the 72h algae growth inhibition (AGI) test according to the international guidelines in ISO 8692:2012 (ISO, 2012). The algal pre-culture was prepared 4 or 5 days in advance of the test, which allows the test to be performed during the exponential phase of microalgae growth. A 1 mL portion of algal stock culture was inoculated in the test media and kept in the same climatic cabinet (BINDER KBW 240) as the stock culture. Because the MHSM-2 medium does not contain phosphate, MHSM-1 was required for pre-culture. MHSM-1 is a nutrient rich medium, containing phosphate stock, trace metals and necessary cations for the growth of microalgae **(SI3-1)**

After preculture in the MHSM-1, the algae were filtered through 0.2 μm cellulose nitrate filter (Whatman). The pellet was washed and resuspended in MHSM-2 medium, containing only necessary cations for the survival of microalgae. The spiked media were prepared in PET plastic beakers in order to adjust the pH at 8.2 ± 0.2 (for all the media except MHSM, 7.0 ± 0.2) in adding small amounts of NaOH (Roth) and HCl (Geyer). The media were spiked with a standard 2% HNO_3 (Roth, 4989.1) acidified stock solution of 50 g L^{-1} of Gd or La (as $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{LaCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99% purity; Sigma Aldrich) at incremental concentrations; 0.01; 0.1; 1.0; 3.0; 10; 30 and 100 mg L^{-1} . The concentrations 0.01 – 100 mg L^{-1} with increments of 10 were chosen to have both more environmentally and anthropogenic concentrations over a wide range. The 3.0 and 30 mg L^{-1} were chosen to cover the improve the calculations and understanding of the data. A solution of 3,5-dichlorophenol (97% purity; Sigma Aldrich) was used as positive control.

The tests were performed in 24 well microplates (Costar 2524, Corning Incorporated) where $1.3\text{E}4$ cells mL^{-1} of algae were inoculated at the beginning of the test. For 72h, the plates are kept in the climatic cabinet at temperature $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ at continuous light of 6000 to 10 000 lx on the horizontal shaker at 250 rpm (IKA, MTS 2/4 digital microplate shaker). At 0, 24, 48 and 72h, media in each well were homogenized and growth was determined in measuring chlorophyll levels in each 2 mL wells via fluorescence measurements (emission = 680 (35) nm; excitation = 465 (30) nm, integration time: 40 μs) with a TECAN GENios plate reader (Tecan, Männedorf, Switzerland). After 72h, the pH in each well was measured to determine if the pH stayed within the limit of ± 1.5 during the test. The average daily growth rate of the control was at least 1.4 and the variance growth coefficient did not exceed 5%.

3.2.4. Measured concentrations

Metal concentrations were measured at the end of the exposure so not to disturb the growth of the algae. At least 10 mL of each treatment were filtered through 0.2 μm cellulose nitrate filter (Whatman) to ensure only the potential bioavailable part was measured. The filtrate was acidified with 0.02 mL of

HNO₃ and REE concentration was measured using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS, ThermoFisher Scientific ICAP RQ Model, ThermoFisher Scientific, Courtaboeuf, France) at the PEA^{2t} Platform of Chrono-environnement laboratory (UMR CNRS 6249, University of Franche-Comté).

3.2.5. Statistics

For each test, a minimum of three repetitions were completed (N = 27). To determine nominal and measured median effective concentrations (EC₅₀), non-linear regression curves were created using GraphPad Prism version 9.3.1 for Windows. No constraints were applied to the non-linear regression curves using nominal concentrations. Due to the shape of certain non-linear curves, accurate estimation of some of the EC₅₀ values was not feasible. Consequently, these EC₅₀ values were considered unreliable and excluded from consideration. However, constraints were set to an upper limit of 100% inhibition when using measured REE concentrations. With these concentrations, dose response curves were predicted in each media individually and in all media combined. For that last case, outliers were determined and eliminated by the GraphPad prism program with a ROUT coefficient Q of 1% based on (Motulsky and Brown, 2006). Any EC₅₀ predicted lower than 1 x 10⁻¹⁰ mg L⁻¹ were considered as not accurate and were ignored. The algae biomass inhibition was analyzed for normal distribution with Shapiro Wilk and further analyzed through a Two-way ANOVA (p < 0.0001, N = 134) with a Tukey's for multiple comparison. The p-value was always 0.05 as reference.

3.3. Results and Discussion

3.3.1. Microalgae growth under control conditions - impact of media composition

In order to study growth in the presence of different phosphate preparations, the growth rates of *R. subcapitata*, *C. vulgaris* and *S. vacuolatus* in the different media were first investigated without exposure to REEs over 72 hours (Table 3-1). The ISO medium with dissolved inorganic phosphate provided the best growth conditions for all three species (growth rates: 1.5 to 1.61 per day). The medium containing organic phosphate (ISO-G1P) reduced growth of all species but to a different extent (by about 80 to 90% for *S. vacuolatus* and *C. vulgaris*, to 40% for *R. subcapitata*). Availability of dissolved organic P substrates such as phosphomonoesters has been linked to the activity of cell-surface bound alkaline phosphatases (AP). While inorganic phosphate (P_i; e.g., PO₄³⁻) is usually preferred, microalgae have been shown to upregulate AP activity under P_i deficiency (Kuenzler, 1965). But utilization of phosphomonoesters results in lower growth rates compared to P_i, possibly due to increased energy demand or lower provision of utilizable phosphate (Vrba *et al.*, 2018). Ren *et al.* (2017) reported growth rates in the presence of glucose-6-phosphate of 0.46 day⁻¹ for *R. subcapitata* and 0.61 day⁻¹ for *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* during a 10-days experiment (maximum growth rates). This compares well with the growth rates measured in the present

study of 0.67 day^{-1} (*R. subcapitata*) and 1.22 day^{-1} (*C. vulgaris*) (Table 3-1), considering the use of different culture conditions (media, light, length of exposure) and, in the case of *Chlorella*, a different algae species.

The MHSM-2 medium, which lacked phosphate and other trace elements such as Fe, Mn, Ze, Co, and Cu, resulted in the lowest growth, most pronounced again for *R. subcapitata*. Growth was possibly enabled by remaining intracellular phosphate reserves or extracellular traces. Positive growth rates between 0.47 and 0.69 day^{-1} over the 72 hours exposure time (Table 3-1) were considered still high enough to carry out the REE toxicity tests. As expected, *S. vacuolatus* was the least sensitive to phosphate limitation, due to its capacity to store and accumulate P_i for several days (Kuesel *et al.*, 1989). To take the media and species dependent differences into account, inhibition effects presented in this study always refer to the comparison with the respective non-spiked media.

Table 3-1 Growth rates per day of the three microalgae species in the control conditions of the three different media. SD: standard deviation, n: number of replicates.

Algae species	ISO			ISO-G1P			MHSM		
	mean	SD	n	mean	SD	n	mean	SD	n
<i>R. subcapitata</i>	1.62	0.21	27	0.67	0.15	16	0.47	0.14	10
<i>S. vacuolatus</i>	1.50	0.11	21	1.32	0.25	16	0.62	0.20	16
<i>C. vulgaris</i>	1.51	0.10	23	1.22	0.35	15	0.69	0.16	10

3.3.2. Impact of REE exposure

Growth inhibition in relation to the REE nominal concentrations was determined for all media, and EC_{50} values were calculated in order to compare any differences in the effect of Gd and La. Dose response curves for *R. subcapitata*, exposed to Gd and La (Figure 3-1) revealed different shapes for the two metals and the media. In the ISO medium (Figure 3-1a), the toxicity for the maximum inhibition caused by La (approximately 50%) was much lower than for Gd (100%). Similar observations were made for the ISO-G1P medium containing organic phosphate. The maximum effect on the biomass of *R. subcapitata* was higher for Gd (approximately 60%) than for La (approximately 40%). In the case of Gd, the first effect was reached at concentrations lower than 0.01 mg L^{-1} which was much lower than in the ISO medium.

Figure 3-1 Effect of nominal La (red) and Gd (blue) concentration on *R. subcapitata* biomass inhibition after 72h in the three cultures medium. Dots: observed data, lines: prediction of the dose response-curves.

The nominal EC_{50} values calculated for both REE on each microalgae species and culture media are displayed in Table 3-2. For *R. subcapitata* and *S. vacuolatus*, the absence of phosphate led to a higher toxicity by an order of magnitude of both La and Gd in the MHSM medium, in comparison with the ISO medium containing P_i . No significant difference in the estimated EC_{50} s was found for either between the microalgae species or between the different media.

DOES PHOSPHATE MASK TOXICITY OF TWO REE FOR DIFFERENT MICROALGAE SPECIES?

Table 3-2 EC_{50} for the biomass inhibition for *R. subcapitata*, *S. vacuolatus*, and *C. vulgaris* exposed to nominal concentrations in $mg\ L^{-1}$ of lanthanum and gadolinium in ISO, ISO-G1P, and MHSM medium. Average \pm standard deviation. Significant ($p < 0.05$) differences between the different media and REE are indicated by letters, $N = 21$. NA = Not Available.

	ISO	ISO-G1P	MHSM
La			
<i>R. subcapitata</i>	2.77 (NA)	0.96 (NA)	0.08 (NA)
<i>C. vulgaris</i>	NA	0.03 (NA)	0.01 (NA)
<i>S. vacuolatus</i>	3.67 (NA)	NA	0.02 (NA – 1.16)
Gd			
<i>R. subcapitata</i>	6.78 (4.26-NA)	4.73e-06 (NA)	0.05 (NA)
<i>C. vulgaris</i>	0.25 (0.15-0.44)	0.07 (NA)	0.01 (NA)
<i>S. vacuolatus</i>	0.80 (0.56-0.99)	NA	0.09 (NA)

The EC_{50} s therefore do not vary significantly with medium. However, a trend suggesting an increase of toxicity with possible decrease of REE-phosphate complex formation. This observation may suggest that REE toxicity is caused by the dissolved REE fraction and not by phosphate limitation. In that case, biomass inhibition effects of REE should depend on dissolved REE concentrations, independently of the media. For that reason, metal dose response curves and EC_{50} were then calculated according to the metal concentrations measured at the end of the bioassays, expected to represent the dissolved REE concentrations.

Figure 3-2 depicts the biomass inhibition depending on the measured REE concentrations over all media. In the case of *C. vulgaris* (Figure 3-2b), 12 (for La) and 16 (for Gd) data points out of 60 were identified as outliers, while 4 of 100 (*S. vacuolatus* (Figure 3-2c), Gd) and 4 of 91 (*R. subcapitata* (Figure 3-2a), Gd) were eliminated for the other species.

The R^2 for the nonlinear regressions indicates a high goodness of fit for *C. vulgaris* (both, Gd and La), a good fit in case of Gd for *R. subcapitata* and *S. vacuolatus*, but a less good fit for La. These data point to a strong dependence of toxicity from the measured REE concentrations for *C. vulgaris* and in the case of Gd for the other two species. For La, the fit is less good which could be explained by the media composition, having a greater influence on the toxicity of La (Firsching and Brune, 1991). These assumptions are reflected by the EC_{50} values from the non-linear regressions (Figure 3-3). *C. vulgaris* turns out to be very sensitive to both metals with EC_{50} s of 4.00×10^{-03} (Gd) and 2.0×10^{-03} (La) $mg\ L^{-1}$ over all media. In contrast, the EC_{50} s for *R. subcapitata* and *S. vacuolatus* were both close to 5.0×10^{-02} (Gd) and 7.0×10^{-01} (La) $mg\ L^{-1}$ and were therewith one (for La) and two (for Gd) power of magnitude higher than with *C. vulgaris*. Other studies have found measured EC_{50} values which are often a magnitude of order higher. For instance, González *et al.* (2015) calculated a measured EC_{50} for Gd of $2.2\ mg\ L^{-1}$ for

Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (González *et al.*, 2015) while Siciliano *et al.* (2022) calculated a measured EC_{50} of 2.46 and 0.98 $mg L^{-1}$ for La and Gd respectively for the marine microalgae *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*.

Figure 3-2 Effect of measured La (red) and Gd (blue) concentrations on the algae biomass inhibition after 72h of exposures in all medium combined. Three species were studied on three microalgae species. Dot: observed data, lines: prediction of the dose response-curves. R^2 for the linear regression as an indication for goodness of fit.

Figure 3-3 Measured EC₅₀ of La and Gd in mg L⁻¹ on three microalgae species regardless for the exposure media. The error bars represent the 95% confident intervals.

These results suggest that the variation in toxicity between La and Gd depends on the algal species and the metal bioavailability. This observation may provide an explanation for the conflicting conclusions found in the literature. Some studies propose that REE toxicity is consistent within the group (Tai *et al.*, 2010; Joonas *et al.*, 2017; Rucki *et al.*, 2021), while others suggest that it intensifies with higher atomic numbers (González *et al.*, 2015; Kurvet *et al.*, 2017; Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020). It is also known that different REE were found to be distributed differently in the microalgae cells between species. Řezanka *et al.* (2016) found that neodymium (Nd) and cerium (Ce) localized in the chloroplasts of *Desmodesmus quadricauda*, while La and Gd were found in the cytoplasm. The amount of REE on the outside of algae cells will differ with the number of sorption sites but might not it might not relate to toxicity if it does enter the cells.

There is currently only one report that studied the toxicity of REEs on *C. vulgaris* but cannot be fully compared with the current work, as the EC₅₀ were calculated from nominal concentrations of La, samarium (Sm) or Nd (Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020). However, Bergsten-Torralba *et al.* (2020) remains in agreement with the present results, as it calculated lower EC₅₀ for *C. vulgaris* than for *R. subcapitata* (i.e. EC₅₀ of 47.1 and 51.7 mg L⁻¹ of La for *C. vulgaris* and *R. subcapitata* respectively). The difference of sensitivity among the microalgae species could be due to a difference of exudate production. Indeed, microalgae are known to produce extracellular molecules to protect themselves against metal stress (Cavalletti *et al.*, 2022). These exudates usually have a high-affinity constant for the metal and can increase

metal complexation with it and metal desorption from the cell walls (Gonzalez-Davila *et al.*, 1995; Croot, Moffett and Brand, 2000; Ozaki *et al.*, 2003). Furthermore, under phosphorus limitation, phytoplankton was found to release more exudates, to the detriment of their growth (Obernosterer and Herndl, 1995). The significant variability in sensitivity observed between these two commonly used microalgae species; *C. vulgaris* and *R. subcapitata* highlights the critical importance of acknowledging and considering the species when conducting hazard assessments.

Nevertheless, measured REE concentration correlates with growth inhibition and suggests that it is the available REE ions that cause toxicity. The toxicity of REE appears to be lower in algae growth tests due to the presence of phosphate, as the phosphate by complexation and precipitation reduces the concentration of bioavailable free REE ions. This protective effect to the microalgae would be higher for La than Gd due to the lower solubility of La-PO₄ (Firsching and Brune, 1991). Complexation of REEs by multiple ligands makes the assessment of REE toxicity complex, especially for bioassays performed in nutrient rich media such as the algae growth inhibition test (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). It is thus of the uttermost importance that standardized toxicity tests consider chemical speciation.

3.4. Conclusion

The toxicity assessment of La and Gd in three different media, each with different phosphate sources, suggested that the metals' impact on microalgae primarily depends on their bioavailability rather than phosphate limitation due to metal complexation. Therefore, the presence of phosphate in the growth media of algae growth inhibition bioassays would mask the toxicity of REE. The variation between nominal and measured EC₅₀ values, along with dose-response curves, indicated the presence of metal precipitation in the presence of inorganic phosphate (ISO), thereby constraining bioavailability and toxicity of REE on microalgae. In contrast, organic phosphate and phosphate-free media (ISO-G1P and MHSM) limited metal complexation with ligands and showed a higher toxicity effect for the microalgae. The observed correlation between measured REE concentrations and toxicity across all media combined for a given metal reinforces that REE toxicity correlates more closely with measured concentrations than with phosphate constraints. Furthermore, the hypothesis that there is a similar sensitivity towards La and Gd is only applicable for certain species. Variation in toxicity between La and Gd was found across the different microalgae species. *C. vulgaris* exhibited greater sensitivity to both REEs. The EC₅₀ values found for *R. subcapitata* and *S. vacuolatus* were close, and one for La and two for Gd power of magnitude higher than with *C. vulgaris*. Therefore, the difference of toxicity between La and Gd directly depends on the microalgae species studied. Thus, the present study highlights the importance of integrating chemical speciation and interspecies sensitivity variation into standardized toxicity tests. The complexation of rare earth elements

makes assessing the toxicity, particularly in bioassays like the algae growth inhibition test, of REE very complex. When performing these tests there should be awareness that biological species have significant differences in sensitivity to REE and must be considered and acknowledged when carrying out hazard assessments.

Author contribution

Author contribution is in alphabetical order of surname. Pilot studies and conceptualization were performed by Susanne Heise and Chantal van Drimmelen. Marion Revel and Chantal van Drimmelen were responsible for conducting the bioassays and the preparation of the samples for ICP-MS measurements and analysis. The first draft of the paper was jointly written by Marion Revel (Materials and Methods, Results, and Discussion) and Chantal van Drimmelen (Abstract, Introduction, Results, Discussion, and Conclusion). It was then reviewed, expanded, and edited by Marion Revel, Susanne Heise, Andrew Hursthouse, and Chantal van Drimmelen. All authors agreed on the final version.

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CHAPTER 4

IMPORTANCE OF SPECIATION ANALYSIS FOR REE TOXICITY IN PRESENCE OF PHOSPHATE AND MICROALGAE

Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen^{1,2∞}, **Marion Revel**^{1,2∞}, Andrew S. Hursthouse², Susanne Heise¹

Keywords: Lanthanides, metal speciation, bioavailability, phosphate limitation, ecotoxicology, geochemistry

¹ Life Sciences, Hamburg University of Applied Science, Ulmenliet 20, D-21033 Hamburg, Germany

² University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

∞ Equal contribution as first authors

Abstract

Assessing the bioavailability of rare earth elements (REE) is crucial but challenging in ecotoxicology. The chemical speciation and formation of complexes in test media, especially in the presence of the essential nutrient phosphate, reduces the recovery of REE. It has been shown that formation of poorly soluble REE-phosphate complexes can mask REE toxicity. This paper studies the prediction of REE bioavailability using chemical speciation models against ecotoxicological bioassays. Standardized 72h algae growth inhibition tests were conducted using three freshwater microalgae species - *Raphidocelis subcapitata*, *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Scenedesmus vacuolatus* - in three media with different phosphate scenarios: Standardized medium containing inorganic phosphate, standardized medium containing organic phosphate, and a phosphate-free medium. Measured REE concentrations through Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) were compared with predictions from the geochemical model PHREEQC. The results confirmed that inorganic phosphate significantly limits REE bioavailability, with differences between La and Gd agreeing with their different formation constants. In the absence of microalgae, chemical speciation models were good predictors of metal bioavailability. However, the presence of microalgae modifies REE bioavailability, most likely due to the release of extracellular compounds with strong binding capacity for these metals. Microalgae activity cannot be taken into account within the model, limiting the predictive capacity of geochemical speciation models. This study highlights the need to integrate biological factors in geochemical modeling to better predict REE bioavailability for wider application in ecotoxicology.

4.1. Introduction

Rare Earth Elements (REE) are widely used in high- and green-technologies, leading to increasing concentrations in freshwater ecosystems (Lerat-Hardy *et al.*, 2019; Liang, Li and Wang, 2014) (Balaram, 2019), while knowledge on their effect on aquatic environments is still limited. Ecotoxicological studies face challenges due to the complex chemical speciation and low solubility of REE. Most of the median effective concentrations (EC_{50}) available are based on nominal concentrations, which do not equal the bioavailable fraction of these metals (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a; Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b).

Measured concentrations of REE in test media are considerably lower than nominal concentrations due to adsorption to glass surfaces (Weltje *et al.*, 2002) and precipitation (González *et al.*, 2015; Blinova *et al.*, 2018; Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2019; Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b; Revel *et al.*, 2023; Barry and Meehan, 2000). But even measured concentrations may not reliably predict bioavailability to organisms and thus explain toxicity. A substance is considered bioavailable when it can be absorbed by an organism and has the potential for distribution, metabolism, elimination, and bioaccumulation, which may result in a toxic effect (Drexler *et al.*, 2003; Newman and Jagoe, 1994). The bioavailable fraction of metals is influenced by its chemical speciation and is commonly defined as the dissolved fraction or more specifically its free ion concentration (Aharchaou *et al.*, 2020; El-Akl, Smith and Wilkinson, 2015). Batley and Campbell (2022) emphasized the need to investigate the link between metal speciation and bioavailability, especially for trivalent metals. They also remarked that the thermodynamic information on REE that is needed to run speciation models is often incomplete.

Geochemical speciation modelling is a cost-effective and fast method that can predict metal partitioning in aqueous samples using thermodynamic data. Many geochemical modelling software packages are currently available such as PHREEQC (Parkhurst, 1995), Visual MINTEQ (Gustafsson, 2011), and Geochemist's Workbench (Bethke, 2022). While these models have already been applied to assess REE bioavailability and toxicity (Weltje *et al.*, 2004; Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a; MacMillan *et al.*, 2019; Galdiero *et al.*, 2019), they do not account for the presence of live organisms. Their utility in ecotoxicology remains limited due to limitations in the available thermodynamic databases. For instance, some complexes between REEs and organic compounds lack equilibrium constants (Marsac *et al.*, 2021; Iqbal *et al.*, 2023).

In order to investigate the current applicability of chemical speciation models in predicting REE bioavailability in ecotoxicological bioassays, we compared measured REE concentrations in standardized microalgae bioassays with concentrations predicted by the chemical speciation model PHREEQC. The focus lay on the different forms of phosphate that were provided in the media. As the solubility constants of REE-phosphate complexes is very low, leading to precipitation of the essential nutrient phosphate, nutrient deficiency in algae bioassays has been suggested as the primary cause of REE-toxicity (Joonas *et*

al., 2017). This assumption has since been questioned by several authors (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b; van Drimmelen, Revel, et al., submitted). Consequently, this study seeks to shed light onto the interaction between living organisms and REE, and between REE and different phosphate sources.

4.2. Materials and Methods

4.2.1. Algae Growth Inhibition Test

Lanthanum (La) and Gadolinium (Gd) dissolved concentrations were obtained from a standardized algae growth inhibition test according to the international guideline ISO 8692:2012 (ISO, 2012) (see for a more detailed description van Drimmelen, Revel, et al., submitted), after 72 hours. To study the effect of phosphate on REE speciation, three media were used; 1) ISO medium from the international guideline (ISO, 2012) containing inorganic phosphate ($1.17 \times 10^{-05} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$); 2) ISO-G1P medium, adjusted ISO medium containing the organic phosphate source glucose-1 phosphate instead of the inorganic phosphate; 3) MHSM, a modified high salt medium originally developed by Sueoka, Chiang and Kates (1967) and used in a REE study by Aharchaou *et al.* (2020) because of its absence of phosphate. The composition of all the three media is available in supplementary data (also used as input for the geochemical modelling) (SI3-1).

The algae growth inhibition test was performed with three freshwater microalgae species; *Raphidocelis subcapitata* (SAG Strain Number: 61.81), *Chlorella vulgaris* (SAG 211-11b), and *Scenedesmus vacuolatus* (SAG 211-15). *R. subcapitata* and *C. vulgaris* were chosen due to the common use in laboratories for risk assessment. *S. vacuolatus* was selected for its ability to accumulate and internally store PO_4^{3-} for several days, reducing its dependency on phosphate in growth medium (Kessler, 1976; Aharchaou, Bahloul and Fortin, 2021).

The different test media were put in polyethylene terephthalate (PET) plastic beakers and spiked with a standard 2% HNO_3 (Roth, 4989.1) acidified stock solution of 50 g L^{-1} of Gd or La (as $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{LaCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99% purity; Sigma Aldrich) at gradual nominal concentration of 0.01; 0.1; 1.0; 3.0; 10; 30 and 100 mg L^{-1} . The pH was initially adjusted at 8.2 ± 0.1 for the ISO and ISO-G1P media or at 7.0 ± 0.2 for the MHSM medium, according to the preparation protocol. Then, the 2 ml of spiked medium was distributed in 24 well microplates (Costar 2524, Corning Incorporated) where $1.3 \times 10^4 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$ of algae were inoculated. The plates were kept at $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ at continuous light of 6000 to 10.000 lx on a horizontal shaker at 250 rpm (IKA, MTS 2/4 digital microplate shaker).

4.2.2. ICP-MS measurements

After 72h of exposure, the pH was measured in each condition to check whether it differed from the validity criterion of not changing by more than 1.5 over the course of the test. The medium was then

filtered through 0.2 μm cellulose nitrate filter (Whatman, 7182-004). The filtrates of 10 mL were acidified with 0.02 mL HNO_3 and subsamples were sent to the PEA^{2t} Platform of Chrono-environment laboratory to quantify the measured REE concentrations (UMR CNRS 6249, University of Franche-Comté). Concentrations of La and Gd were assessed using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS, ThermoFisher Scientific ICAP RQ Model, ThermoFisher Scientific, Courtaboeuf, France). Repeatability (within-run precision) and reproducibility of the measurements were surveyed (checking of relative standard deviation values and use of internal standards), and quality control (control solutions and blanks to check for the absence of drift) was conducted during measurements. Analysis accuracy was checked using two certified reference materials: soft drinking water for ICP-AES (LGC6027, LGC Standards, Molsheim, France) and surface water for ICP-MS (SPS-SW1, LGC Standards, Molsheim, France). The percentage of recovery between certified values and the average of the measured values was considered satisfactory between 80 and 120%. Blanks (HNO_3 + ultra-pure water) and certified reference materials were prepared and analyzed using the same methods as the samples. The concentrations of trace metals in water are expressed as mol L^{-1} .

4.2.3. Geochemical speciation modeling

PHREEQC (version 3) (Parkhurst and Appelo, 2013) is a computer code, which was designed to perform speciation and saturation-index calculations in water. The thermodynamic database of the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory “LLNL.dat” provided with PHREEQC was used. This database includes all reactions and stability constants at 0.0 mol L^{-1} ionic strength and 25°C for REE inorganic anion complexation (e.g., Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , PO_4^{3-}) in solution relevant to the present work. Missing complexation reactions and constants at infinite dilution between metal ions present in the media (e.g., Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+}) and EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) were taken from another PHREEQC database (“Minteq.v4.dat”) and from (Byrne and Li, 1995) for REE. The LLNL database lists several solid phases that were hypothesized to form during preliminary tests. Only the formation of $\text{REEPO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)}$ appeared relevant for the present study because it is stoichiometrically the most relevant and dominant thermodynamically dominant. Additionally, the formation of $\text{REEOHCO}_3_{(s)}$ was considered, by analogy with Am^{3+} , an actinide analogue of REE (Guillaumont et al., 2003). The solubility product of $\text{REEOHCO}_3_{(s)}$ was allowed to vary within ± 1 log unit (here 0 for La, +1 for Gd), which remains within the uncertainty on the value for Am^{3+} .

4.3. Results

4.3.1. Capability of speciation modelling to predict dissolved La and Gd-concentrations in algae growth medium in the absence of microalgae.

In order to compare speciation modelling to measured dissolved concentrations in test media, that provided organic, inorganic or no phosphate sources, nominal concentrations for Gd and La are plotted against dissolved Gd and La concentrations that were measured after 72h of exposure (dots) or modelled (lines) (Figure 4-1). For better comparison, logarithmic scales are used for the three individual media: ISO, ISO-G1P, and MHSM.

Figure 4-1 Observed (dots) and modelled (lines) REE dissolved concentrations against nominal concentrations, presented in logarithmic scale- in M. Concentration of La (left) and Gd (right) in different medium; ISO (red), ISO-G1P (blue), MHSM (green). The dotted line presents the dissolved PO₄³⁻ concentration.

4.3.1.1. ISO medium

The modelled PO₄³⁻ concentration, presented in red dotted lines in Figure 4-1, behaved similar for Gd and La in the ISO-medium (inorganic phosphate source). Around the nominal concentration of 10⁻⁵ mol L⁻¹ of REE³⁺, the PO₄³⁻ concentration decreases to a very low concentration, accompanied by an increase for both Gd and La (Figure 4-1; red line). The dissolved La and Gd concentrations (Figure 4-1; red squares) were lower than the nominal concentrations by at least one order of magnitude (Figure 4-1; black squares and line) with the exception of the lowest nominal concentration of La of 10⁻⁷ mol L⁻¹ which was similar to the measured one. The modeled data fit pretty well for both Gd and La in comparison to the measured data.

4.3.1.2. ISO-G1P medium

Modelling the REE speciation in the ISO-G1P medium (Figure 4-1; in blue) has currently no complexation constants available for the organic glucose-1 phosphate. The dissolved concentrations

(Figure 4-1; blue triangles) were predicted to be higher than in the ISO medium. The modelled concentrations of Gd in the ISO-G1P medium are in line with the measured concentrations. The predicted dissolved concentrations of Gd remained similar to the nominal concentrations until reaching 10^{-5} mol L⁻¹. At this point, the dissolved concentrations were anticipated to reach saturation, resulting in stable dissolved concentrations. In contrast, for La there is a slight underestimation by the model of the measured concentrations. However, the predicted concentrations are within the range by an order of magnitude. Thus, the modeled data could still be considered to be in line with the measured REE concentrations. The saturation for dissolved La concentrations was around 10^{-7} mol L⁻¹, which is much lower than for Gd.

4.3.1.3. MHSM medium

The modeled concentrations for both La and Gd are similar to the nominal concentrations in the MHSM medium in the absence of any phosphate source (Figure 4-1; green lines and diamonds). Thus, the model assumes that no complexes precipitate until higher concentrations of REE. The model predicts the measured concentrations of Gd very well, as the modeled data is very much in line with the measured. Only at concentrations higher than 10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ there is an underestimation from the predicted concentrations by the model. In the case of La the model overestimates the measured concentrations. The predicted La concentrations followed the nominal concentration until saturation at 10^{-5} mol L⁻¹, which is also when the PO₄³⁻ is predicted to precipitate from the ISO-medium. It is observed that the measured La concentrations in all three media have a similar pattern but are also all well below the nominal concentrations.

4.3.2. Role of algae on REE speciation

Chemical speciation modelling does not account for the presence of living organisms. By comparing the outcomes (1) of nominal REE concentrations, (2) of measured dissolved concentrations in test media after 72 hours exposure to microalgae, and (3) of theoretical concentrations resulting from speciation modelling, the impact of organisms on REE speciation and the applicability of speciation modelling for toxicity predictions was studied. Results for three microalgae species and three media with different phosphate sources are depicted in Figure 4-2. All 3 microalgae species give the same result (as the dots lie directly on top of each other) with ISO-G1P and Gd. Table 4-1 summarizes the observations with regard to the influence of algae in the respective media.

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Figure 4-2 Dissolved Gd (left) and La (right) concentration without and with three different microalgae species against nominal concentrations, presented in logarithmic scale. Grey: dissolved concentrations without microalgae, red: with *R. subcapitata*, blue: with *C. vulgaris*, green: with *S. vacuolatus*, black: nominal concentrations, and pink: modelled concentrations.

Table 4-1 Simplified overview over the effect of microalgae on measured REE concentrations by comparing data with and without algae ("Algae" as opposed to "media"). Blue: no effect ($C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$); Yellow: reducing effect of microalgae ($C_{diss(Algae)} < C_{diss(Media)}$); green: Green: Increasing effect of microalgae ($C_{diss(Algae)} > C_{diss(Media)}$).

Medium	Gd			La		
	<i>R. subcapitata</i>	<i>C. vulgaris</i>	<i>S. vacuolatus</i>	<i>R. subcapitata</i>	<i>C. vulgaris</i>	<i>S. vacuolatus</i>
ISO	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} > C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} > C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$
ISO-G1P	$C_{diss(Algae)} < C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} < C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} < C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$
MHSM	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} = C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} > C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} > C_{diss(Media)}$	$C_{diss(Algae)} > C_{diss(Media)}$

4.3.2.1. ISO medium

In the ISO medium, the dissolved Gd concentrations in the presence of the different microalgae species remained generally consistent with those without the microalgae (Figure 4-2; grey dots). In contrast, the concentrations of dissolved La were observed to be higher compared to exposures without microalgae, with the exception of *S. vacuolatus* (Table 4-1). In general, the dissolved data for the ISO medium had a good fit with the modelled data for both REE.

4.3.2.2. ISO-G1P medium

For both REE, the dissolved concentrations were close to the predicted concentrations by the modelled ISO-G1P data in presence of microalgae. In the case of Gd, all of the different microalgae species behave in a similar manner, but a small deviation occurs at nominal concentrations higher than $10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ compared to exposures without microalgae. The presence of microalgae does not appear to affect the dissolved concentration of La.

4.3.2.2. MHSM medium

The dissolved concentrations of Gd in the presence of microalgae in the MHSM medium were similar to the ones without algae. In this medium, which lacks PO_4^{3-} , the dissolved concentration of La varied in the presence of microalgae compared to its absence. The presence of the microalgae raised the dissolved concentrations of La, showing similar concentrations to the nominal data. However, it is worth noticing that no replicates could have been performed for this experiment. Each value in the dataset is unique, making it impossible to quantify the uncertainties caused by the preparation of the samples or the measurements method.

4.4. Discussion

4.4.1. How good is the modelling tool for REE?

In answer to Batley and Campbell (2022) the present study explored the links between speciation and bioavailability of REE. The results of the present study show that the modelled concentration of both Gd and La by the speciation modelling to measure dissolved concentrations in test media, fit pretty well. Constant lower dissolved concentrations measured by ICP-MS compared to the nominal concentrations in the three-culture media indicate the presence of strong metal precipitation with anions. This difference between these concentrations was lower for the MHSM compared to the ISO medium. In the ISO medium, the geochemical speciation model predicts that inorganic phosphate decreases the solubility and therefore bioavailability of REE. However, the predicted modelled concentrations are higher for Gd than for La. Which is probably due to LaPO_4 being the least soluble. The absence of PO_4^{3-} in this medium at highest nominal REE concentration led the metal to complex with other anions such as carbonates or hydroxides (Wood, 1990; Sneller *et al.*, 2000; Ng *et al.*, 2010).

In the ISO-G1P medium, similar maximum dissolved REE concentrations were predicted but were reached at lower nominal concentration than in the ISO medium, due to a reduction of metal precipitation in absence of inorganic phosphate. As no complexation constant for the organic glucose-1 phosphate is currently available in geochemical database, the dissolved REE concentrations were predicted in absence of phosphate, leading to an increase of metal complexation and precipitation with other ligands such as $\text{MOHCO}_{3(s)}$ and $\text{M(OH)}_{3(s)}$.

If precipitation was lower than in other media, due to the absence of phosphate and lower pH in the MHSM medium, it was still occurring leading to a decrease of REE bioavailability when performing ecotoxicology bioassays with microalgae. This was also found by Lachaux *et al.* (2022a) who found that expressing the EC_{50} values based on nominal, measured or predicted dissolved REE concentrations influenced by REE speciation changed the toxicity assessment on *Daphnia magna*. The results confirm the limitations of using nominal concentrations when performing standardized bioassays with REE in laboratory.

Differences of dissolved concentrations measured by ICP-MS or predicted by the model were observed between La and Gd. Phosphate REE solubility products can range over more than an order of magnitude (Liu and Byrne, 1997). Dissolved concentrations are generally lower for La than Gd, due to the lower solubility of La phosphate in aqueous solution compared to Gd (Firsching and Brune, 1991). La solubilities are larger than the heavier neighboring elements of La, and the solubility of LaPO_4 is much smaller than that of YPO_4 . The solubility product (K_{sp}) for La is around $10^{-25} \text{ mol}^2 \text{ L}^{-2}$ and for Gd $10^{-25.6} \text{ mol}^2 \text{ L}^{-2}$ (Liu and Byrne, 1997). Difference of solubility among the REE in similar media lead to a difference of

bioavailability between the two elements, which could explain the higher toxicity of Gd compared to La when looking at nominal concentrations (Joonas, 2017). Thus, speciation modeling, which accounts for variations in the solubility of different lanthanides with ligands like phosphates, can be valuable tools in ecotoxicology for predicting REE bioavailability.

4.4.2. The impact of microalgae on the modelling

The presence of microalgae adds an additional complexity to the system and thus also to the chemical speciation of the metals. These organisms can adsorb metal due to the presence of carboxyl and amino groups on their cell surface (Spain, Plöhn and Funk, 2021; Aharchaou *et al.*, 2020). When metal adsorption is strong, the dissolved concentrations measured in the media could decrease. The decrease in dissolved concentrations in presence of microalgae in the media was rarely observed in the present study.

Variation of dissolved La concentration was recorded in the ISO medium, depending on the exposed microalgae species. This variation suggests an interspecies difference of extracellular exudate produced or of metal adsorption and uptake. Which might be due to the ability of *S. vacuolatus* to internally store phosphate (Aharchaou *et al.*, 2020). Interspecies difference for metals has been observed for marine micro- and macro-algae which despite the same number of cells in the inoculation, enriched the seawater with organic ligands and changed the levels of the trace metals differently in coastal natural seawaters (Vasconcelos and Leal, 2008). This result suggests that, in most cases, different freshwater microalgae species have a similar impact on the speciation of REE, even though they vary in sensitivity when it comes to the effect of these metals on their growth (van Drimmelen, Revel *et al.*, submitted).

In most cases, geochemical speciation models predicted well the dissolved REE concentrations measured after 72h. Prediction was particularly good in the ISO and MHSM media as most of the complexation constants were available. In contrast, the absence of information of the organic phosphate used for the present study limited to good prediction of REE speciation in the ISO-G1P. There are other limitations like that the geochemical speciation models for ecotoxicology is their incapacity to integrate the effects of alive organisms in the system. A wide number of datasets for REE is only available for the abiotic compartments and there is a lack for specific to aquatic biota compartments (Rétif *et al.*, 2023). Which is further complicated when speciation calculations are needed for tests related to natural systems (Dupré *et al.*, 1999). A good understanding of the speciation changes is required to be able to understand the outcome of ecotoxicity tests (El-Akl, Smith and Wilkinson, 2015; Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a). Thus, a good understanding of the processes by the researcher, both chemical and biological, are required when applying modeling as a tool. Therefore, the results suggest the need for further research on REE speciation

and establishing databases to optimize the use of these geochemical models in predicting REE bioavailability under varying bioassay conditions, including living organisms, in ecotoxicology.

When comparing the concentration of dissolved REE in the presence of microalgae with the predicted values obtained through geochemical speciation modeling, strong disparities can be observed. Specifically, in the ISO medium, the concentration of La is significantly underestimated due to its low solubility, and this trend persists at elevated nominal La concentrations in the MHSM. These differences highlight the necessity of considering the influence of microalgae on REE solubility for more accurate predictions of speciation and, consequently, of bioavailability of metals with low solubility. In contrast, the dissolved concentration of Gd, a more soluble metal, is relatively well-predicted by the model, albeit with a slight overestimation in the ISO-G1P scenario, potentially attributed to metal adsorption onto the microalgae (Birungi and Chirwa, 2014; Guida, Siciliano and Pagano, 2017). The ISO and MHSM under lanthanum show similar results where there is no phosphate available after reaching nominal concentrations of 10^{-5} M, and the model predicts this well in the presence of microalgae but not in the absence.

The present study hypothesises that in the complete absence of phosphate that algae probably produce some kind of exudates, which keeps La in solution. While this does not appear to be the case for Gd, it is at least preferentially with La. Exudate production directly depends on the nutrient availability such as the phosphorus (Yoneyama *et al.*, 2012; Duan, Zhao and Zhang, 2020). Algae compete with La for phosphate, often resulting in a PO_4^{3-} deficiency which is needed for the growth of the microalgae (Joonas *et al.*, 2017; Aharchaou *et al.*, 2020). Phosphate deficiency might help microalgae acquire PO_4^{3-} from surroundings. Algae have developed several strategies to scavenge phosphate from external surroundings (Grossman and Aksoy, 2015). The unicellular green alga *Chlamydomonas* is one of the few species for which phosphate activities have been well characterized (Grossman and Aksoy, 2015), but for a lot of other microalgae species the exact processes are still unknown. Grossman and Aksoy (2015) highlighted that very little is known about the nutrient-deprivation responses, such as algal protein responses to P-starvation. Lanthanum being in solution in both the ISO and MHSM media could be a side effect of the production of exudates by algae as response to phosphate starvation could be a side effect. However, additional experiments are needed to see if this is really the case. Another possibility is that in response to P starvation algae produce enzymatic alkaline phosphates, which releases orthophosphate (PO_4^{3-}) from phosphorus-containing compounds as part of extracellular P-scavenging (Quisel, Wykoff and Grossman, 1996). Still little is known about these enzymes and the metal co-factors associated with alkaline phosphates are not well studied (Dyhrman, 2016).

The present study demonstrates the limitations of speciation modeling in predicting the bioavailability of REE in ecotoxicology. The accuracy of its prediction seems to differ with the type of REE. Indeed, metals like La, which tend to readily precipitate, appear to be more influenced by microalgae activity than more soluble metals, such as Gd. The presence of exudates generated by microalgae in absence of phosphate may influence REE precipitation and keep La but not Gd in solution. However, the exact processes behind the exudate production of microalgae related to phosphate and REE remain unknown. The present study demonstrates the complexity of the interactions between microalgae and metals and emphasizes the need for specific geochemical approaches when evaluating the bioavailability of different REE in ecotoxicological bioassays.

4.5. Conclusion

Comparing nominal REE concentrations with measured and predicted dissolved ones in three microalgae cultured media highlighted the difficulty of quantifying the bioavailability of these metals in ecotoxicology bioassays. The results confirmed that the presence of inorganic phosphate can strongly limit REE bioavailability by promoting substantial metal precipitation. The difference between nominal and dissolved concentration highlights the limitations of using nominal concentrations for risk assessments when microalgae are involved, as a substantial portion of the metal fraction can precipitate. When microalgae are absent, geochemical speciation modeling generally performs well in predicting metal speciation. However, this predictive tool encounters challenges in the presence of live organisms. The study clearly demonstrates that microalgae can modify the speciation of REE either enhancing or reducing their solubility depending on the culture medium and the metal. Notably, microalgae interspecies variation in the influence of different microalgae species on REE speciation was low, suggesting a general consistency in their impact, despite their differences in sensitivity to metal-induced effects on growth. To improve geochemical speciation modeling for ecotoxicological applications, the incorporation of a surface complexation model for the microalgae cell surface could be a valuable initial step. Nonetheless, based on the present findings, it becomes evident that the production of exudates plays a primary role in influencing metal speciation. Therefore, it would be necessary to integrate biological insights into geochemical modeling to effectively consider the impact of microalgae activity on the solubility of REE.

Author contributions

Author contribution is in alphabetical order of surname. Marion Revel, and Chantal van Drimmelen, were responsible for conducting the bioassays. Preparation of the samples for ICP-MS measurements and analysis were performed by Marion Revel and Chantal van Drimmelen. Interpretation of all ICP-MS data was done by Rémi Marsac, Marion Revel, and Chantal van Drimmelen. Rémi Marsac performed the speciation modelling. The first draft of the paper was jointly written by Marion Revel (Abstract, Materials and Methods, Results, Discussion) and Chantal van Drimmelen (Introduction, Materials and Methods, Results, Discussion, and Conclusion). It was then reviewed, expanded, and edited by Marion Revel, Susanne Heise, Andrew Hursthouse, Rémi Marsac, and Chantal van Drimmelen and. All authors agreed on the final version.

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CHAPTER 5

IMPACT OF RARE EARTH ELEMENTS ON THE GROWTH AND PHOTOSYNTHETIC EFFICIENCY OF *MYRIOPHYLLUM AQUATICUM*

Isidora Gjata¹, Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen^{2,3}, Franca Tommasi¹, Constantino Paciolla¹, Susanne Heise²

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¹ Department of Biology, Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, Via Orabona 4, Bari, Italy

² Department of Life Sciences, Hamburg University of Applied Sciences, Ulmenliet 20, Hamburg D-21033, Germany

³ University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Abstract

Rare Earth Elements (REE) are becoming more present in our everyday life. For this work, the aim was to study and compare the toxic responses of the REE lanthanum (La), cerium (Ce), neodymium (Nd), and gadolinium (Gd) to the macrophyte *Myriophyllum aquaticum*. The scope was to evaluate if these elements trigger a response on the photosynthetic system II (PSII), which causes inhibition of the growth rate of the plant. The fluorescence yield by pulse-amplitude-modulated chlorophyll fluorometer (PAM) was measured, which enabled simultaneous high-resolution fluorescence measurements of the whorl daily for the whole duration of the test (10 days) and fresh weight change (FWC) at the end of the test. The findings suggest that La significantly decreased FWC at the highest concentration (500 mg kg⁻¹) but did not cause any significant effects on the fluorescence yield. Ce and Nd significantly decreased the chlorophyll fluorescence between days 2 and 4, and after that the yield was not significantly different compared to the control. Of all the REE tested in this study, showed Gd the most negative effect as the whorls exhibited chlorosis/necrosis and the fresh weight at the end of the test decreased significantly compared to the same plant at day 0. The yield of *M. aquaticum* showed time-dependent effects for Gd at the highest concentration. Gd was the most toxic REE, strongly affecting both the yield and FWC. The measurement of the fluorescence yield of the PSII is a useful effect observation and of high environmental importance. The difference in sensitivity between the functional and growth endpoints may give hints about the mode of action of contaminants such as REE to aquatic plants.

5.1. Introduction

Rare earth elements (REE) refers to a group of 17 metals, that includes the lanthanide series and the elements scandium (Sc), and yttrium (Y). They are naturally present in the environment, constituting a chemical group sharing similar characteristics (Feng, Zhu and Li, 2013). REE are not individual native metals, rather they are found in numerous ore and accessory minerals as minor and major constituents (Siciliano et al., 2021). Though they are termed "rare," REEs are found in soils worldwide (Hu *et al.*, 2006). According to Carpenter *et al.* (2015) does the classification of "rare" solely refer to the fact that they are not found on large ores like silver and gold. REE are not widely known to the public, although their increased use in cutting-edge technologies, particularly renewable energy, is turning them into a highly valuable commodity (Lambert and Ledrich, 2014). REEs have become essential in high - and green technologies (e.g., wind turbines, solar panels, electric vehicles), but their supply capacity cannot keep up with the rising demand. Thus, REEs are regarded as critical raw materials (Parliament, 2013).

Cerium (Ce) is one of the most abundant elements among REE, displaying a wide range of human applications. Chloride and nitrate forms of Ce and lanthanum (La) are the main constituents of REE micro fertilizers used in China since the 1970s to improve crop yield (Hu *et al.*, 2004). In addition, REE utilization in agriculture, animal husbandry, and medicine are well known (Pagano, 2016). In 1996, the release of gadolinium (Gd) from contrast agents used in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) demonstrated for the first time the presence of anthropogenic REE in aquatic systems (Bau and Dulski, 1996). There is limited data on other REE available, notably on neodymium (Nd) (Blinova *et al.*, 2020). Even though REE exhibit similar chemical and physical properties, the toxicity of individual REEs can vary depending on several factors. The solubility of REE compounds in water influences their bioavailability and potential toxicity, and although REE have received increased attention recently, little is still known about their effects on the aquatic biome and aquatic organisms.

Aquatic macrophytes play an important functional and structural role in freshwater ecosystems by influencing the carbon and nutrient cycle, forming primary productivity, and providing food and habitat for other organisms. Especially in oligotrophic ponds and lakes, streams, and wetland communities, submerged, floating, and emersed macrophyte species are essential to harbor diverse organism communities (Wetzel, 2001). Regardless of the causes, any significant reduction in macrophytes can be expected to strongly impact the whole ecosystem (Lewis, 1995). *Myriophyllum spp.* is widely considered a suitable bioassay plant model for the detection of herbicidal activity (Forney and Davis, 1981; Paterson and Wright, 1987; Hanson, Sanderson and Solomon, 2003; Turgut, 2005) and has been used as a potential candidate for pesticide toxicity, as a dicot- and sediment-rooting macrophyte. Several mechanisms, such as the absorption of hydroxides of polyvalent metals (Fe, Mn, Co) and phosphorus compounds, limit the

accumulation of REE in water (Borzenko, Zamana and Zarubina, 2017). The ability of lanthanides to form complexes with inorganic and organic ligands controls their flow in natural processes.

The mode of action of REE in *Myriophyllum aquaticum* is not completely understood. These elements cause leaf chlorosis and abnormal growth responses in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, typical of many plant growth regulators (Ma *et al.*, 2013). The loss of photosynthetic pigments is also a common response of plants which has been observed after metal treatment in various species of *Myriophyllum* genus such as *M. heterophyllum* (Sivaci *et al.*, 2008), *M. spicatum* (Grudnik and Germ, 2010; Wang *et al.*, 2009) and *M. alterniflorum* (Delmail *et al.*, 2011; Ngayila *et al.*, 2009). However, it is indicated that REE could greatly increase the activities of the photosynthetic system II (PSII) –protein complex in wheat (Fashui *et al.* 2002).

Chlorophyll fluorescence analyses, as one of the most sensitive parameters of plant photosynthetic capacity, showed that terbium inactivated the performance of reaction centers in PSII, and with that decreasing the photosynthetic capacity on *Lemna minor* (Alp *et al.*, 2023). “Conventional” methods for measuring photosynthetic activity is often performed through identifying bioindicators that look at the decrease in photosynthetic pigments (Alp *et al.*, 2023) or by analyzing the chlorophyll status through remote sensing tools (e.g., single-photon avalanche diode (SPAD), Gomez-Garay *et al.*, 2014). However, working with bioindicators requires specific skills and knowledge, while chlorophyll fluorescence has been found to be more sensitive than the chlorophyll status when using SPAD. Some studies suggest an alternative method; the pulse-amplitude-modulated chlorophyll fluorometer (PAM), which can be used to evaluate the effect of REEs on different plant models (Gomez-Garay *et al.*, 2014; Goecke *et al.*, 2015). The PAM allows for simultaneous high-resolution fluorescence measurements of whole plants and plant sections in multiwell plates in parallel. This new method has not been widely used; however it is less time-consuming when monitoring the photosynthetic status over time for every individual exposed plant compare to other conventional methods.

The aim of this work was to study and compare La, Ce, Nd, and Gd, and the toxic responses of the macrophyte *M. aquaticum* to these REE. It is hypothesized that these elements trigger a response on the PSII, which causes inhibition of the growth rate of the plant. This hypothesis was tested through observation parameters of the terminal measure of the fresh weight change and the non-invasive measure of the photosynthetic status of the exposed macrophytes over time.

5.2. Materials and Methods

5.2.1. Maintenance and pre-culture preparation of *Myriophyllum aquaticum*

The stock culture of *M. aquaticum* (parrot feather) was obtained from the German Federal Institute of Hydrology (BfG, Koblenz, Germany). Non-axenic pre-cultures of *M. aquaticum* were grown

vegetatively in artificial sediment following the instructions for toxicity determination on the ISO 16191:2013 (ISO, 2013). The sediment was saturated with modified Steinberg medium ((ISO, 2005), **S15-1**) containing (pH 5.5 ± 0.2), under defined growth conditions in a growth chamber. The artificial sediment consisted of 74% quartz sand (average grain size 170 μm), 20% kaolinite clay, 5% peat, and 1% calcium carbonate (OECD, 2004). The pre-culture was maintained in glass pots at $24 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with a light exposure of 16:8 h light/dark and a light intensity of $80 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. A new pre-culture was prepared biweekly from the head and the three whorls below from 3- to 4-week-old *M. aquaticum* plants.

5.2.2. Spiking of sediment

The spiking solution for the artificial sediment (OECD, 2004) was prepared as follows: Ce, Nd, La and Gd-salts ($\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{LaCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99% purity; Sigma Aldrich) were dissolved in modified Steinberg medium and added to the sediments to reach a final concentration of 50, 250, and 500 mg kg^{-1} dry weight. These concentrations were chosen based on pilot studies that indicated the concentrations needed to see toxicity occurring in the plants. They also allowed for a potential comparison with other studies exposing REE to other plants (e.g., *L. minor*, the lentil *Lens culinaris* Medik, and onion *Allium cepa* L.). The negative control was clean sediment and for the positive controls were the plants exposed to 100 mg kg^{-1} 3,5-dichlorophenol (DCP, 97% purity; Sigma Aldrich) and 700 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ diuron (3-(3,4-Dichlorophenyl)-1,1-dimethyl-harnstoff, 98% purity; Sigma Aldrich). Acetone was used as the solvent solution for DCP. The spiked sediments were conditioned statically in glass pots with the growth media solution as supernatant in the ratio: 1 part (mass) mixed sediment plus a maximum of 0.5 parts (volume) nutrient solution and sealed with Parafilm® "M" (American National Can, Chicago, USA) for one week under exposure conditions ($24 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$; $80 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; continuous light) prior to use in the bioassay.

5.2.3. Sediment contact assay

A sediment contact test with *M. aquaticum* (Feiler, Kirchesch and Heininger, 2004) was adapted for application in six well multiwell plates (VWR International, 734-1599). Each well was half-filled (10 g) with the respective exposure sediment for the miniaturized sediment contact assay. When necessary, the sediment in the wells was water saturated with modified Steinberg medium and the stem of the *M. aquaticum* one whorl per well was inserted into the sediment. Before whorls from 3- to 4-week-old *M. aquaticum* were exposed to the sediment, the fresh weight of each whorl was determined. For the experiments, only whorls with a fresh weight between 10 and 20 mg were used (ISO, 2013). For the test, all six wells of one plate had the same exposure sediment acting as replicates. The plates were incubated under controlled standardized conditions at $24 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, under continuous lighting (neutral white), for 10

days. Light intensity was homogeneous within the range of $60 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ to $75 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. After 5 days of exposure, the modified Steinberg medium was added to the sediment in each slot to account for evaporation loss. At the end of the 10 days of exposure, the plants (whorl, roots, and shoots) were removed from the sediments, rinsed in Steinberg medium, pat dried and weighted. DCP and diuron were used as a positive control for the growth and chlorophyll fluorescence, respectively, on the same plate. Each experiment was repeated three times.

5.2.4. Measurement of the photosynthetic yield

Measurements of the photosynthetic yield were carried out as described by Küster and Altenburger (2007) in the six-well plates using a maxi-imaging pulse-amplitude-modulated chlorophyll fluorometer (I-PAM) (Walz, Effeltrich, Germany). The I-PAM employs pulse-modulated measuring light for fluorescence excitation plates, which were measured every 24 hours for the whole duration of the test (10 days). Hereby, the maximum fluorescence yield (F_m') is measured under actinic light during a saturation pulse. The momentary fluorescence yield (F) is determined between the pulses. The fluorescence parameter $Y(\text{II})$ was calculated according to Schreiber, Klughammer and Kolbowski (n.d.). I-PAM measurements were used to determine the effective quantum yield of the PS II ($Y(\text{II})$) of each whorl in the multiwell plate following the preparation of the plates. During the exposure time of 10 days, the $Y(\text{II})$ of each whorl was determined every 24h. Saturation light pulses were applied to samples that were adapted to an actinic illumination of $80 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ every 30 seconds for ten measurements. The area of interest was defined by surrounding the entire whorl with a circle in the software. All whorls of the plate were analysed, and only the last six measurements from each well were applied to estimate the median $Y(\text{II})$ at each time point, as a dark-adapted sample is important. The following measurement settings were used: pulse-modulated measuring light (ML) = 1, photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) = 35, gain = 2, actinic light (AL) = 3, saturation pulse = 10.

5.2.5. Inhibitory effects calculation

In the sediment contact assay, two parameters were considered: the inhibition of fresh weight change (FWC) and the inhibition of $Y(\text{II})$ in *M. aquaticum* whorls exposed to artificially spiked sediments in comparison to whorls grown under negative and positive control conditions. The FWC (in %) was calculated from the mass gain in fresh weight on day 10 of exposed *M. aquaticum* (Eq. 1).

$$FWC = \left(\frac{m_{d10} - m_{d0}}{m_{d0}} \right) \times 100, \quad (1)$$

where m_{d0} is the fresh mass of a single plant at day 0 and m_{d10} is the fresh mass of a single plant at day 10.

To calculate the inhibitory effects of REE on the FWC of the whorls (I_{FWC} in %), the FWC of exposed whorls (FWC_T) and of the control whorls (FWC_C) were calculated according to Eq. 2.

$$I_{FWC} = \left(1 - \frac{FWC_T}{FWC_C}\right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Similarly, the inhibitory effect ($I_{PSII, dx}$ in %) of spiked sediments to the Y(II) of *M. aquaticum* whorls at day x (dx) was calculated. (Eq. 3) The Y(II) of treated whorls ($Y(II)_{T, dx}$) and of the control whorls ($Y(II)_{C, dx}$) at dx is the average of the last six measurements from the I-PAM (data not shown).

$$I_{PSII, dx} = \left(1 - \frac{Y(II)_{T, dx}}{Y(II)_{C, dx}}\right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

The growth performance of the plants in the control sample must meet a minimum mean growth rate of 0.090 (ISO, 2013).

5.2.6. Statistical analysis

All analyses were performed separately for each REE, with the data presented as the mean of three distinct replicates (N = 30). A One-way ANOVA ($p < 0.001$) was performed followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test using the statistical software GraphPad Prism version 9.3.1 for Windows. Statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.01$ (*), $p < 0.001$ (**), and $p < 0.0001$ (***)

5.3. Results

5.3.1. Plant growth

The FWC of *M. aquaticum* whorls in the negative control sediment showed a significant gain ($p < 0.001$) of more than double the fresh weight during exposure in all sequential 4 experiments (Figure 5-1). The FWC of the whorls within the control varied between 110% and 170% at the end of the 10-day experiment. Whorls treated with Ce and Nd did not show a significant FWC at any concentrations. La induced a significant decrease on FWC (around 28%) at the highest concentration ($p = 0.0155$), while the lowest concentrations did not induce any changes compared to the respective control ($p = 0.8125$). Gd showed the highest effect of all REEs tested at 250 ($p = 0.001$) and 500 mg kg^{-1} ($p < 0.001$). At 500 mg Gd kg^{-1} , all whorls had entered a visually detectable state of chlorosis/necrosis, with a decrease in FWC of 101% compared to the control. As a result, the mean fresh weight of the whorls at this treatment

decreased from 28 mg at the onset of the experiment to 27 mg at the end of the exposure. When treated with 250 mg kg⁻¹, the FWC of the whorls decreased by 50% compared to the respective control. At 50 mg kg⁻¹ the FWC was not significantly different ($p = 0.478$). Acetone, used as a suitable solvent for DCP to spike the sediment, did not affect the growth rate (SI5-2).

5.3.2. Effects of different REE on the fluorescence yield

During the exposure of whorls of *M. aquaticum* to control and spiked sediments, the Y(II) was observed every 24h for each whorl over the 10-day exposure period. For whorls treated with La, there was no significant difference from the control (Figure 5-2a); at all concentrations there was a constant photosynthetic status. Whorls treated with Ce and Nd showed a decrease in yield between days 2 and 4 compared to the control, followed by no difference in yield for the duration of the experiment (Figure 5-2b and c; SI5-3). In contrast to the other REE, in Gd-spiked sediments, the Y(II) of *M. aquaticum* showed time and concentration-dependent effects (Figure 5-3). For the highest concentrations investigated (500 mg kg⁻¹), almost immediate effects could be detected with a drop in Y(II) of 36% within 3 days reaching 90% at the end of the test (whorls were in necrosis). For 50 and 250 mg kg⁻¹, there was a lower decrease in Y(II) of the exposed whorls over the length of the experiment of 19% on day 10 (Figure 5-2d).

Figure 5-1 Fresh weight change (a-d) of *M. aquaticum* whorls in control and spiked sediments after a 10-day exposure in percentage. Sediments were spiked with La (a), Ce (b), Nd (c) and Gd (d) at three concentrations. Data points of control and spiked sediments represent the mean value of four plants. Vertical bars indicate the SD of replicates in each treatment group. * Statistical significance at $p < 0.05$ (*); $p < 0.01$ (**); $p < 0.001$ (***).

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Figure 5-2 Time course of the effective quantum yield of the PS II (a–d) of *M. aquaticum* whorls in control and spiked sediments during a 10-day exposure. Sediments were spiked with La (a), Ce (b), Nd (c) and Gd (d) at three concentrations. Data points of control and spiked sediments represent the mean value of four plants and six measurements. Vertical bars indicate the SD of replicates in each treatment group.

Figure 5-3 Readings of the yield of the plants treated with Gd at 50 (a,b), 250 (c,d) and 500 (e,f) mg kg^{-1} on day 5 on the Maxi version of the Imaging - PAM. Darker areas show an effect on the PSII. Yield measurements were repeated every 24 hours for the whole test duration.

5.3.3. Inhibitory effects

Table 5-1 reports the inhibition of REE-treated whorls for both the yield and FWC. Diuron and DCP were the positive controls for the yield and the FWC, respectively. Exposure to La at all concentrations did not cause inhibition except for the FWC at the two highest concentrations. Nd showed inhibition at all concentrations for both parameters. The same was recorded for Ce, except for no FWC inhibition at the highest concentration. Gd showed the strongest effects in both parameters measured, being more significant at the highest concentration. For the FWC at the highest concentration there is a complete inhibition.

Table 5-1 Inhibition of the effective quantum yield of the PS II ($Y(II)$) and the inhibition of the FWC compared with control values of 10-day-old whorls exposed to spiked sediments. The inhibition was calculated using Eq. 2 and 3. Diuron and DCP values are from wells separate from the REE at concentrations 100 mg kg^{-1} and $700 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ respectively.

REE	Yield inhibition			FWC inhibition				
	50 mg kg^{-1}	250 mg kg^{-1}	500 mg kg^{-1}	Diuron	50 mg kg^{-1}	250 mg kg^{-1}	500 mg kg^{-1}	DCP
La	-0.18	0.00	-9.12	39.18	-14.6	3.74	28.18	52.88
Ce	3.45	9.62	8.35	38.29	20.75	13.54	-10.96	71.45
Nd	5.08	3.81	3.45	40.29	17.35	11.01	13.43	71.45
Gd	22.12	18.59	89.96	39.41	-16.52	50.64	101.52	51.36

5.4. Discussion

The advantage of the *Myriophyllum* sediment contact test is that the plant grows directly in the sediment, without further addition of a water column. Thus, it is able to detect toxicity caused by contaminated sediment. Especially as REE like to stick to sediment particles and fine organic matter (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018), making it very likely for *M. aquaticum* to be exposed to REE in nature as well. However, there are very few studies available on the immobilization of REE to this plant model (Ostroumov *et al.*, 2015) and as far as the authors know none on the effect. The results of the present study showed that La significantly decreased FWC at the highest concentration. However, it did not cause any significant effects on the fluorescence yield. On the contrary, Ce and Nd significantly decreased the chlorophyll fluorescence between days 2 and 4, and after that the yield was not significantly different with respect to the control. Previous studies have shown that PSII activity can be resumed in cells of *Synechococcus elongatus* that were recovering from Cu^{2+} treatment during chlorosis (Selim and Haffner, 2020).

Of all the REEs tested in this study, Gd showed the most negative effect as the whorls exhibited chlorosis/necrosis (**SI5-4**) and the fresh weight at the end of the test decreased significantly compared to the same plant at day 0. The Y(II) of *M. aquaticum* showed time-dependent effects for Gd at the highest concentration, with almost immediate effects detected and a decrease in Y(II). The difference from the other REEs can be explained by the fact that La, Ce and Nd are considered Light REE (LREE), while Gd is a Heavy REE (HREE). HREEs were preferentially translocated to leaves in the five *Phytolacca* species reported by Grosjean *et al.* (2019). This may also be the case with *M. aquaticum*, as only the leaves were considered when measuring the fluorescence yield. In future studies, it would be helpful to analyze the roots and evaluate the effects of REEs in different parts of the plants.

Li *et al.* (2013) reported that heavy metals damage plant chloroplast or photosynthetic organs and reduce photosynthetic efficiency. Results showed that when algae growth is inhibited by stress, it indicates that the photosynthetic system of algae has been damaged (Chen *et al.*, 2016). Leaf photosynthesis could also be inhibited due to damage to PSII as indicated by changes in chlorophyll fluorescence under Cd stress (Ci *et al.*, 2010). So, it can be hypothesized that REE induces a response on the PSII, which causes inhibition of the plant's growth rate.

Gd and La are known to inhibit calcium (Ca) channels and disrupt calcium signalling pathways in plant cells (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Tan, Yang and Wilkinson, 2017; Sherry, Caravan and Lenkinski, 2009; Martino *et al.*, 2018; Han *et al.*, 2019). Ca plays essential roles in various cellular processes, including signal transduction, enzyme activation, and cell wall synthesis (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014; Kulaksız and Bau, 2013; Pałasz and Czekaj, 2000; Trapasso *et al.*, 2021). Disruption of Ca

homeostasis by Gd can lead to impaired plant growth, nutrient uptake, and other physiological processes (Xing *et al.*, 2021). In this case, one could say that the hypothesis is not supported as Gd and La mechanisms primarily involve interference with ion uptake, rather than direct effects on photosynthetic machinery such as PSII. On the other hand, La can interfere with the uptake and assimilation of essential nutrients in plants (Xie *et al.*, 2002). Imbalances in nutrient availability can disrupt metabolic processes, inhibit cell growth and division, and impair overall plant growth and development. This would also explain the effect of this REE on the plant growth.

In soil and sediment, REE are often adsorbed onto the surface of the soil and sediment particles, with 99% of all REE in aquatic systems ending up in the soil and sediment (Weltje *et al.*, 2002). Even if the concentration of the elements in soil and water is the same, the roots will take a different amount of the element from the growth medium. It may be assumed that translocation of elements from roots to upper plant parts will also differ in the water-grown and soil-grown plants (Shtangeeva, Niemelä and Perämäki, 2022). Light rare earth elements (LREE, La – Eu) are more likely to form complexes with carbonates in the sediment, which makes it more likely for sediments to be enriched with LREE than with heavy rare earth elements (HREE, Gd – Y) (Smrzka *et al.*, 2019).

Because these elements belong to two different groups (light and heavy), it can be suggested that La caused different damage to the plant system compared to Gd. The same can be said for plants treated with Ce and Nd. Ce can induce positive effects at low concentrations by activating beneficial physiological processes (Preetha *et al.*, 2023), improving mineral nutritional content (Rico *et al.*, 2015) and increasing shoot length and fresh weight (Jahani *et al.*, 2019). Ce has been reported to induce hormetic effects on plants under certain conditions. Hormesis is a phenomenon where exposure to low doses of a stressor elicits a beneficial response, while higher doses may have negative effects. In the case of cerium, studies have shown that low concentrations can indeed stimulate positive physiological responses in plants, which is characteristic of hormesis (Gjata *et al.*, 2022).

The heterogeneous biological effects can also be explained by differences in test solution composition, which strongly influence REE speciation (i.e., the different chemical and physical forms of REE) and their bioavailability, and in consequence, induces different biological effects (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Borgmann *et al.*, 2005; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014; Vukov, Smith and McGeer, 2016). While both Ce and La are bioavailable to aquatic organisms, La is often considered to be more bioavailable due to its increased solubility, environmental concentrations, and potential for uptake and accumulation in biological tissues (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). However, it is important to consider site-specific factors and the bioaccumulation potential of individual REEs when assessing their ecological risks and impacts in aquatic ecosystems. This could explain the significant inhibition on the relative growth rate in plants treated with La compared to

the ones with Ce. In water, mineral elements are present in more available to a plant form and can be easily taken by roots. Further research is needed to better understand the underlying mechanisms and potential ecological implications (e.g., the genetic material and effects on the offspring of REE affected plants) of REE exposure on aquatic plant physiology and health.

5.5. Conclusions

Due to its ease of cultivation and handling, abundant growth, the fact that the species is not prone to contamination by algae and other organisms, and its acceptable variability and relative sensitivity, *M. aquaticum* should be considered a test model in environmental risk assessment. The measurement of the fluorescence yield of the PSII is a practical additional effect observation and of high environmental relevance. The difference in sensitivity between the functional and growth endpoints provides information about the mode of action of REE in sediments to macrophytes and offer scope for an advanced hazard assessment. Gd was the most toxic REE, strongly affecting both measured endpoints. Further biochemical and physiological studies can be done to better understand the specific stress responses. This will allow us to understand the mode of action of different REEs and identify potential bioactive compounds that can minimize or neutralize the effects and counteract their toxicity.

Author contributions

Author contribution is in alphabetical order of surname. Isidora Gjata and Susanne Heise contributed to the study's conception and design. Material preparations were performed by Isidora Gjata and Chantal van Drimmelen. Data collection was performed by Isidora Gjata with assistance of Chantal van Drimmelen. The statistical analysis was performed by Isidora Gjata and discussed with Susanne Heise and Chantal van Drimmelen. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Isidora Gjata; with additions by Chantal van Drimmelen. It was then then reviewed, expanded, and edited d by Isidora Gjata, Susanne Heise, Constantino Paciolla, Franca Tommasi, and Chantal van Drimmelen. All authors contributed to the review and discussion. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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CHAPTER 5

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CHAPTER 6

TOXICITY AND BIODISTRIBUTION OF LA AND GD IN *DAPHNIA MAGNA* FOLLOWING CHRONIC DIETARY AND WATERBORNE EXPOSURE

Marion Revel^{1,2∞}, **Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen**^{1,2∞}, Frederika Mišíková³, Edith Padilla Suarez⁴, Andrew S. Hursthouse², Susanne Heise¹

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¹ Life Sciences, Hamburg University of Applied Science, Ulmenliet 20, D-21033 Hamburg, Germany

² University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

³ Institute of Environmental and Chemical Engineering, University of Pardubice, Studentská 573, 532 10 Pardubice, Czech Republic.

⁴ Biology department, University of Naples Federico II, via Cinthia 21, 80126 Napoli NA, Italy

∞ Equal contribution as first authors

Abstract

Daphnia magna has frequently been used to assess the toxicity of rare earth elements (REE) such as lanthanum (La) and gadolinium (Gd) that are representing an emerging class of pollutants. However, most studies have focused on acute toxicity, limiting the knowledge of chronic toxicity and the potential effects of dietary exposure on aquatic organisms. Therefore, the objective of this study was to investigate the effects of chronic waterborne and dietary route exposures of 0.5 mg L^{-1} of La and Gd; on mortality, growth and reproduction of *D. magna*. Four different exposure conditions were used: (i) control; (ii) dietary exposure; (iii) waterborne exposure; (iiii) a combination of dietary and waterborne exposure. The results showed that none of the REE exposures affected the mortality or the growth of the organisms. However, La slightly delayed the release of the first brood for the combined waterborne and dietary exposure by 1.13 days. For Gd, dietary exposure significantly decreased the total offspring of the organism by 15.8 offspring per adult and the combined waterborne and dietary exposure by 21.9 offspring per adult. The biodistribution patterns differed for each metal, with La being uniformly localized in the intestine and Gd bioaccumulating differently depending on the exposure route. Gd dietary and combined exposure led to an accumulation in the intestinal tract. However, waterborne exposure resulted in a more heterogeneous biodistribution within the individual *D. magna*. For both metals, dietary exposure led to the highest REE

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body burden in the organisms, in contrast to the waterborne exposures. The effects observed confirm the importance of considering dietary exposure for long term bioassays. A better understanding of the mode of action of REE on *D. magna* is needed and could be achieved by exploring the effects of REE accumulation in the gut and energy limitations for *D. magna*.

6.1. Introduction

The scientific interest in the impact of contaminants on aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems has been driven since the 1960s stimulated by the publication of *Silent Spring* by Rachel Carson (Landmarks, 2012). Acute and chronic toxicity bioassays with a wide range of species from various trophic levels are now standardised. One of the internationally common bioassays for toxicity testing of contaminants is the aquatic water flea *Daphnia magna*. The broad distribution of *D. magna* in a wide range of ecosystems, a short life cycle, easy to culture and maintain. This led to the organism being recommended as a test species in standardized test guidelines such as OECD (2012), and OECD (2004).

Therefore, *D. magna* has been used to study new emerging contaminants like rare earth elements (REE) (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). The research about these elements has grown exponentially from one publication in 1947 to a predicted 325 studies in 2023 (Kang and Kang, 2020). REE entering into the aquatic environment through wastewater from hospitals and effluents from a number of industrial activities has led to environmental levels far in excess of the low natural background concentrations (Bau and Dulski, 1996). However, despite an increasing number of scientific publications on the anthropogenic influence on their distribution, information on the toxicity and environmental hazard of rare earth elements remains scarce (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Malhotra *et al.*, 2020).

Most studies investigating the toxicity of REE in *D. magna* have been conducted using acute standardized tests (González *et al.*, 2015; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Revel *et al.*, 2023). For instance, the EC₅₀ values after 48h recorded for acute toxicity of REE at nominal concentrations range from 13.93 to 18.5 mg L⁻¹ for Gd and around 31.1 mg L⁻¹ for La (Blinova *et al.*, 2018b; Revel *et al.*, 2023). However, as with other metals, the bioavailability and therefore toxicity of REE is significantly influenced by their chemical speciation and solubility in the test media. Interpretation of toxicity data can become challenging due to rapid precipitation of REE in the test media and the high variation in dissolved REE concentrations (Blinova *et al.*, 2018b). Furthermore, concerns have been raised about the environmental relevance of acute data, emphasizing the need for toxicity data derived from chronic experiments to establish reliable freshwater quality criteria (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Blinova *et al.*, 2018a).

It has been demonstrated that exposing *D. magna* to 0.1 mg L⁻¹ of Gd for 39 days did not have any effect on the organisms (Blinova *et al.*, 2021). However, this test used standardised chronic testing protocols, performed in the presence of food (e.g., microalgae to ensure reproduction). These standardized tests do not consider explicitly the potential contribution of diet-borne metal in the observed toxicity. To date, the role of diet exposure on REE toxicity has still to be established (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Ma *et al.*, 2016; Blinova *et al.*, 2021). Under acute exposures, REE taken up by ingestion does not cause any effect on *D. magna* (Revel *et al.*, 2023). However, under longer exposures, it has been suggested

that dietary exposure may occur due to the algae adsorbing and taking up dissolved metals (e.g., copper) which could affect the reproduction of daphnids (De Schampelaere and Janssen, 2004a).

Therefore, the objective of the study was to investigate the effects of chronic dietary and waterborne exposure of La and Gd on *D. magna*, examining both their toxicity and biodistribution of the metals in the organism. From these experiments, three hypotheses were formulated as follows: 1) chronic dietary exposure affects *D. magna*, but the main route expected to cause toxicity is waterborne exposure; 2) toxicity is linked to a specific metal biodistribution in the tissues of the organism; 3) there is a difference in toxicity between La and Gd, with Gd being more toxic than La. These hypotheses were tested through a 21-day test, where daphnids were exposed to 0.5 mg L⁻¹ of REE through waterborne, dietary, or a combination of these two exposures.

6.2. Materials and Methods

6.2.1. Spiking *R. subcapitata*

During the experimental run, *D. magna* was fed with *Raphidocelis subcapitata* (SAG Strain Number: 61.81) obtained from the Culture Collection of Algae at the University of Göttingen (SAG). For this 4 x 10⁵ cells mL⁻¹ of microalgae were inoculated for 72h in either clean ISO medium or spiked ISO medium from the international guideline (ISO, 2012) containing 0.5 mg L⁻¹ of La(III) and Gd(III) (N9300127 and N9300118 for La and Gd respectively, PerkinElmer, Waltham, US). The spiked ISO medium was prepared in PET bottles and pH was adjusted with NaOH (6777.1, Roth) or HCl (836, Geyer) to 6.8 (± 0.1). The medium was stored at 20°C in the dark for 48h before the microalgae inoculation. After incubation for 72h, the microalgae cell suspension was centrifugated at 10000g for 10 minutes. The supernatant was pipetted off and the pellet was diluted with clean ISO medium until a concentration of 8 x 10⁷ cells mL⁻¹. The algae dilution was stored in the dark at 4°C. Every week, a sample of the culture was visually inspected under a microscope to ensure that no significant cell lysis or bacterial growth had occurred during storage.

6.2.2. REE toxicity towards algae

La and Gd toxicity to *R. subcapitata* were determined by applying the 72h algae growth inhibition (AGI) test following the international guideline ISO 8692:2012 (ISO, 2012), measuring growth inhibition as endpoint. To ensure exponential growth of the microalgae during the test, the pre-culture was prepared 4 or 5 days in advance. The spiked media were prepared in PET plastic beakers in order to adjust the pH at 6.8 ± 0.2 (deviation from ISO 8692:2012 using pH 8.2 ± 0.2) by adding small amounts of NaOH and HCl. The media were spiked with 0.5 mg L⁻¹ of La (III) of Gd(III) (N9300127 and N9300118 for La and Gd respectively,

PerkinElmer, Waltham, US). DCP (3,5-Dichlorophenol, 97% purity; Sigma Aldrich) was used as positive control.

A 24-well microplate (Costar 2524) was inoculated with 1.3×10^4 cells mL^{-1} of *R. subcapitata* at the beginning of the test. The microplate was kept in a climatic cabinet at temperature $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with continuous light of 6000 to 10 000 lx on a horizontal shaker at 250 rpm (IKA, MTS 2/4 digital microplate shaker) for 72h. Cell density was determined by measuring chlorophyll fluorescence (emission = 680 (35) nm; excitation = 465 (30) nm, integration time: 40 μs) with a TECAN GENios plate reader (Tecan, Männedorf, Switzerland) at 0, 24, 48, and 72h. Validity criteria were an average daily growth rate in the controls of at least 1.4, a maximum coefficient of variation of the growth in the three control wells of 5%. At the end of the test the pH in each control well was measured to determine if the pH remained within the ± 1.5 limit.

6.2.3. Chronic *D. magna* exposure

6.2.3.1. *Daphnia magna* culture

Adult *D. magna* were acquired from the German Environmental Ministry (Umweltbundesamt) and cultured at the University of Applied Sciences of Hamburg (HAW). The organisms were maintained in Elenedt M4 medium (OECD, 2012) 17 at a temperature of $21 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with a 16:8 light-dark cycle and fed daily with the freshwater algae *Chlorella vulgaris* (Collection of Algae at the University of Göttingen (SAG 211-11b)). However, *R. subcapitata* was chosen to be used to feed during the exposure period for various reasons; 1) this is the microalgae species recommended by the international guideline ISO 8692:2012 (ISO, 2012), 2) a previous study (van Drimmelen, Revel et al., submitted) has shown that *C. vulgaris* is more sensitive towards REE than *R. subcapitata*.

6.2.3.2. Procedure of the chronic *D. magna* test

The test medium was prepared from Elenedt M4-Medium (pH 6.8 ± 0.2), according to ISO 6341:2012 (OECD, 2012). However, the EDTA-complex was omitted, as it might interfere with REE in the test medium. The M4 is the medium the cultures are maintained in which automatically makes this meet the demand of acclimating the culture to the test medium at least 21 days before the test (US EPA, 2016). Three M4-media were prepared, with two of them spiked with 0.5 mg L^{-1} of La (III) or Gd (III) in PET bottles. The four media were stored for four days in a dark room at 4°C before used in order to reach the chemical equilibrium. One day before the experiment, the media was stored at 21°C to avoid high temperature differences for the test organisms.

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Neonates of less than 24h-old were exposed for 21-days to either La or Gd through four different conditions (modified from (De Schamphelaere *et al.*, 2007)); (i) The control where *D. magna* was exposed to clean medium and fed with non-contaminated algae, (ii) dietary exposure where the REE exposure was through diet (contaminated algae) with *D. magna* grown in clean medium, (iii) waterborne exposure where REE exposure was through the medium (0.5 mg L⁻¹), and (iv) a combined exposure where REE exposure was through both the contaminated microalgae as diet and the spiked media. For each condition, ten PET cups with one daphnid were placed in 50 mL of media. All cups were fed with a specific amount of cells per day of *R. subcapitata* per organism depending on the test day (Table 6-1). An additional cup that only contained algae and no daphnids was added for each test condition. This additional cup was used to estimate the daily algal concentration in order to calculate the feeding rate.

Table 6-1 Amount of *R. subcapitata* in cell per day per organism fed over the duration of 21-days

Days	Cells per day per organism
0-6	8 x 10 ⁺⁰⁶
7-8	1.2 x 10 ⁺⁰⁷
9-20	1.6 x 10 ⁺⁰⁷

On days 2, 5, 7, 9, 12, 14, 16, and 19, the cups were cleaned using pure water and a paper towel, after which the M4 medium was replaced. Daphnids were temporarily placed in a small volume of their corresponding exposure M4 medium (e.g., in either clean or in REE contaminated media). Prior to replacing the medium, the microalgae concentration in each cup was determined through fluorescence measurements.

Mortality and offspring of individual *D. magna* were recorded daily. Reproduction was studied with two endpoints: the date of each brood and the number of offspring per brood. However, according to personal observations, daphnids reproduction tend to vary over the year despite their cultivation in control conditions. For this reason, all endpoints were compared to the average of the control of its respective replicate test.

At the end of the 21 days of exposure, all adults per condition were collected and washed in control M4-medium for 10 minutes followed by a 5 mM Na₂-EDTA (EDTA disodium salt dihydrate, 6381-92-6, Carl Roth) solution for 20 minutes. Afterwards, the daphnids were dried for 48 hours at 40°C. The dried organisms were individually weighed and photographed using a Motic Images Plus 3.0 camera mounted on a Wiloskop stereomicroscope (Hund Wetzlar, Wetzlar, Germany). Subsequently, FIJI software

(Schneider, Rasband and Eliceiri, 2012) was employed to measure the length of each daphnid from the eye to the base of the tail, using the images obtained from the camera.

6.2.4. Biodistribution of La and Gd in daphnids

Dried samples were subsequently adhered on double-sided tape to the edge of glass slides to study metal biodistribution using micro-X-ray fluorescence (μ XRF). These measurements were performed at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon's institute for metallic biomaterials on M4 Tornado (Bruker) working at an energy of 50 kV and an anode current of 600 μ A with a spot size of 25 μ m and an integration time of 1.5 s pixel^{-1} for the area map scans (Helmholz, Luthringer-Feyerabend and Willumeit-Römer, 2019). One picture was produced per element, showing its distribution on the scanned zone, and were analysed using the image processing open-access software FIJI (Schindelin *et al.*, 2012). In order to minimize the background noise as much as possible, the average of the background was calculated, and the minimum display value of the image was adjusted to that average. The different images of interest were then combined and coloured.

6.2.5. REE body burden of *D. magna* and microalgae

Metal body burden of the daphnids and microalgae was quantified through total reflection X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (TXRF; S4 T-Star; Bruker Nano GmbH, Berlin Germany). For that purpose, microalgae were centrifuged at 10 000 rpm for 10 minutes using Thermo Heraeus Multifuge 15-R Chilled Centrifuge with TTH-400 Rotor 4x400 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The microalgae pellets were then freeze dried for 72h under vacuum (0.22 mbar) using single-chamber ice condenser Alpha 1-4 LSCplus (Martin Christ, Germany). The dried *D. magna* and the freeze dried microalgae were digested in a 1.5 mL microtubes containing 45 μ L of pure water, 400 μ L of HNO_3 (65%, Roth, 4989.1) and 50 μ L of HCl (35-38%, p.a., Th. Geyer, 836.2500) and 5 μ L of gallium (Ga) internal standard (final concentration: 10 mg L^{-1} ; VH; VH-PGANH-100) for minimal 48h. After the digestion, 20 μ L of the digested sample was diluted in 80 μ L of pure water and 5 μ L of 3% polyvinyl alcohol (9002-89-5, Carl Roth) was added for a more homogenous spreading of the sample on disc (personal communication Bruker Nano GmbH). From this dilution was 10 μ L of solution pipetted onto a quartz carrier disc and warmed at 60°C on a heating plate until the drop has evaporated. This process was repeated once more before the disc was placed in an oven at 80°C for one hour. The discs were then analysed with the TXRF (Puls: 130 kcps; Maximum energy mode: 40 keV; Excitation: Mo 17.5; Time: 1000 sec.; Type of quantification: liquid; Calibration data: Mo-Ka 17.5). Metal concentrations were calculated from the spectrum obtained and

analysed with TEsprit 1.0 software (Bruker Nano GmbH, Berlin Germany, **SI8-1** TXRF information and quality sheet).

6.2.6. Determination of Dissolved Metal Concentrations

A pre-experiment was performed in order to measure the potential effects of the three microalgae concentrations used as food for the daphnids on the dissolved REE concentrations. All exposure conditions were prepared as previously described but no daphnids were added in the plastic well. However, microalgae were added every day until 2 days of exposure. An aliquot of 20 mL was filtered through a 0.2 μm cellulose nitrate filter (7182-004, Whatman) and the filtrates were acidified with 0.04 mL HNO_3 . Dissolved REE concentration was then measured by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) at the Department of Environmental and Chemical Engineering at the University of Pardubice.

The following reagents were used for ICP-MS analysis: single-element standard solutions $1.000 \pm 0.002 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ of Gd and La (SCP Science, Canada) for instrument calibration, $1.000 \pm 0.002 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ of In (Analytika, Czech Republic) as internal standard (all of the analytical-reagent grade), ultrapure water (conductivity $0.07 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, Evoqua Water Technologies, Germany). The calibration solutions contained 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 5 and $10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Gd and La. Internal standard ($1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was added to all samples (blank, calibration standards and samples) which were then diluted 100 times.

An inductively coupled plasma time-of-flight mass spectrometer OptiMass 9500 (oaTOF-ICP-MS) (GBC Scientific Equipment, Australia) was used for trace analysis of Gd and La in the samples. The ICP-MS analysis parameters were: plasma power 1200 W; plasma, auxiliary and nebuliser gas flow rates were 12 L min^{-1} , 0.55 L min^{-1} and 0.91 L min^{-1} ; multiplier gain 2700 V; acquisition time 5s; and three replicates. Instrument detection limits were 0.4 ng L^{-1} for Gd and 0.2 ng L^{-1} for La. The quantification was performed using external calibration with internal standard In. Unwanted ranges of m/z (1–112, 118–135, 142–152 and 161–260) were excluded from detection using SMARTGATE ion blanking. The working isotopes were ^{139}La and ^{158}Gd . They were chosen with respect to possible isobaric overlaps of interfering ions of the same mass using the spectral library of the device and the mass spectrum of the samples.

6.2.7. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism version 9.3.1 for Windows. The Kolmogorov Smirnow test indicated only the microalgae growth inhibition data was normally distributed. In contrary, no normal distribution was found in the case of dry weight, length, total amount of offspring, number of offspring per brood, and time of each brood of each exposed adult.

Therefore, the microalgae growth inhibition was compared between La and Gd using an unpaired t-test. The dry weight, length, time of each brood, number of offspring per brood and after 21 days of each exposed adults were compared with the control group using the Mann-Whitney test. q-values were calculated with $p = 0.05$.

To compare the feeding rate of the daphnids in the different exposure groups, the slope of the linear curve was examined. It was observed that daphnia food consumption increased over time in a linear manner. The 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the slope were calculated to assess the differences in feeding rates between the exposure groups. By examining the non-overlapping nature of the confidence intervals, significant differences in feeding rates were identified among the exposure groups.

6.3. Results

6.3.1. Impact of waterborne REE exposure on microalgae growth

This study assessed the impact of REE on *R. subcapitata* over 72 hours ($N = 16$), which is the duration of the standardized algae growth inhibition test (ISO, 2012). This information was going to be used to assess availability of REE during dietary exposure over the duration of the chronic daphnia test. After 72h of exposure, the growth inhibition of *R. subcapitata* exposed to 0.5 mg L^{-1} of La or Gd were calculated according to their respective controls. REE affected the growth inhibition of *R. subcapitata* differently over 72h of exposure with growth stimulated by $11.04 \pm 0.88\%$ for La while Gd inhibited it by $7.45 \pm 4.14\%$.

To assess the bioaccumulated REE per cells, measurements were conducted without EDTA cleaning on these cells. This enabled a comprehensive quantification of the metals introduced into the system through dietary exposure (adsorbed and absorbed REE). The plot in Figure 6-1 represents the accumulated concentration of REE per cell of *R. subcapitata* cell after 72h of exposure. Both La ($p = 0.0046$) and Gd ($p = 0.0411$) exposure led to a significant increase in REE concentration per cell compared to the controls. Microalgae seemed to bioaccumulate these two elements on a similar way, as both exposures led to approximately $2 \times 10^{-04} \text{ ng}$ and $1.7 \times 10^{-04} \text{ ng}$ of La and Gd respectively per the microalgae cells.

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Figure 6-1: REE accumulated per *R. subcapitata* cell (in ng per cell) after 72h of exposure to 0.5 mg L⁻¹ of La or Gd. Ctr: control, La: lanthanum and Gd: gadolinium. The significant differences between the control and the different exposures are indicated by * $q < 0.05$. ** $q < 0.01$.

6.3.2. Effect of microalgae on dissolved REE concentration in chronic daphnia test (in absence of daphnid)

Preliminary experiments were conducted to assess the influence of microalgae on dissolved metal concentrations in M4 medium in absence of daphnids, specifically to ascertain the potential for adsorption or desorption processes. ICP-MS analysis was performed for the three exposure types: dietary, waterborne, and combined exposures and the three microalgae concentrations used during the chronic daphnia test (Figure 6-2) (N = 36).

Compared to Gd, the La concentrations were much lower than the nominal concentration of 0.5 mg L⁻¹. Waterborne and combined exposures showed highest La and Gd dissolved concentrations compared to the dietary and the controls. However, this difference was independent of the food concentration for Gd while it was only visible when $1.2 \times 10^{+07}$ cells were added per day for La.

Figure 6-2: La (top) and Gd (bottom) dissolved concentration (in logarithmic scale) under four exposure condition and three dose of microalgae. White: control, green (symbol /): dietary exposure, purple (symbol \): waterborne exposure, red (symbol ·): dietary + waterborne exposure. 3 replicates per conditions. Error bars: Standard deviations. The significant differences between the control and the different exposures are indicated by * $q < 0.05$. ** $q < 0.01$. *** $q < 0.001$

6.3.3. Toxicity in the chronic daphnia test

6.3.3.1. Mortality and feeding rate

After 21 days of exposure, no mortality was found in any of the tests regardless of the exposure type. Every 2-3 days over the experiment, the feeding rate was observed to compare the linear regression of each exposure condition (Table 6-2 and **SI6-1**). Compared to the control, the slope of the feeding rate tended to decrease over waterborne and dietary La exposure. For both metals, the combined exposure tended to decrease the feeding rate. However, the measured confidence intervals were relatively wide, making it impossible to identify any significant difference between the conditions. In conclusion, the feeding rate did not seem to change under La or Gd exposures.

Table 6-2 Effects of 0.5 mg L⁻¹ of La and Gd on feeding rate, dry length and weight of *D. magna*. Average ± standard deviation. For length and dry weight, the significant differences between the control and the different exposures are indicated by *q<0.05. **q<0.01. ***q<0.001, NA = Not Available

	Control	Dietary	Waterborne	Waterborne and dietary
La				
Feeding rate (95% CI)	1.54x10 ⁺⁰⁶ (1.00x10 ⁺⁰⁶ to 2.06x10 ⁺⁰⁶)	8.46x10 ⁺⁰⁵ (2.32x10 ⁺⁰⁵ to 1.46x10 ⁺⁰⁶)	9.42x10 ⁺⁰⁵ (3.13x10 ⁺⁰⁵ to 1.57x10 ⁺⁰⁶)	1.35x10 ⁺⁰⁶ (7.41x10 ⁺⁰⁵ to 1.96x10 ⁺⁰⁶)
Length (mm)	3.34 ± 3.38x10 ⁻⁰¹ 4.52x10 ⁻⁰¹ ±	3.34 ± 1.89x10 ⁻⁰¹ 5.75x10 ⁻⁰¹ ±	3.43 ± 3.10x10 ⁻⁰¹ 4.93x10 ⁻⁰¹ ±	3.37 ± 2.31x10 ⁻⁰¹
Dry weight (mg)	8.87x10 ⁻⁰²	3.89x10 ⁻⁰¹	2.73x10 ⁻⁰¹	6.67x10 ⁻⁰¹ ± NA
Gd				
Feeding rate (95% CI)	1.39x10 ⁺⁰⁶ (7.78x10 ⁺⁰⁵ to 2.00x10 ⁺⁰⁶)	1.31x10 ⁺⁰⁶ (7.56x10 ⁺⁰⁵ to 1.87x10 ⁺⁰⁶)	1.12x10 ⁺⁰⁶ (5.54x10 ⁺⁰⁵ to 1.68x10 ⁺⁰⁶)	1.16x10 ⁺⁰⁶ (5.48x10 ⁺⁰⁵ to 1.77x10 ⁺⁰⁶)
Length (mm)	3.55 ± 5.35x10 ⁻⁰¹ 4.21x10 ⁻⁰¹ ±	3.56 ± 2.68x10 ⁻⁰¹ 5.05x10 ⁻⁰¹ ±	3.57 ± 2.10x10 ⁻⁰¹ 4.70x10 ⁻⁰¹ ±	3.53 ± 2.01x10 ⁻⁰¹ 4.14x10 ⁻⁰¹ ±
Dry weight (mg)	9.67x10 ⁻⁰²	1.00x10 ⁻⁰¹	2.60x10 ⁻⁰²	1.59x10 ⁻⁰¹

6.3.3.2. Length and dry weight

The average length (N = 30) measured for all conditions was 3.51 ± 0.26 mm (Table 6-2). Calculations showed no difference between the exposed organisms and the control. Daphnids in the control group had an average dry weight of 0.43 ± 0.08 mg and the exposed organisms dry weight remained constant compared to the controls.

6.3.3.3. Reproduction

The number of offspring was counted daily over the period of 21 days to study the effects of La and Gd on *D. magna* reproduction (Table 6-3 and Table 6-4). The different La exposures had no effect on

the number of offspring produced per brood. The first brood was only slightly delayed by combined waterborne and dietary exposure, by 1.13 ± 1.26 days. In the case of Gd, the total reproduction of *D. magna* was decreased by dietary exposure by 15.8 ± 13.2 offspring per adult and for combined waterborne and dietary exposure by 21.9 ± 17.9 offspring per adult. More precisely, Gd dietary exposure affected the fourth brood by 4.79 ± 5.91 offspring per adult and the combined exposure reduced the third and fourth broods by 5.57 ± 5.79 and 4.14 ± 7.47 offspring per adult respectively.

6.3.4. Bioaccumulation of La and Gd in daphnids

After 21 days of exposure, the REE mass in daphnids was measured using TXRF (Figure 6-3). The body burden for La was higher (up to 200 ng daphnid⁻¹) than for Gd (below 80 ng daphnid⁻¹). While there was a significant difference detected, it must be noted that the standard deviation is especially high for the La exposure. Dietary exposure resulted in a significant increase in the internal REE burden compared to the control group, while waterborne exposure did not show any difference from the control. The combined exposure was only significantly different from the control for Gd, not La.

To collect further information on the toxicokinetic behavior of La and Gd, their biodistribution of was studied in the organisms by μ XRF measurements (Figure 6-4). For reference the distribution of Ca is shown in grey, and the distribution of both REE is shown in red. For the three La exposures, La appears to be uniformly localized in the intestine. Whilst for Gd, bioaccumulation is different depending on the type of exposure. Dietary exposure led to an accumulation in the intestinal tract while the waterborne exposure displayed a much more erratic biodistribution within the organism. After a combined exposure, Gd was also diffusely distributed in the organism and in the intestinal tract.

Figure 6-3 Median of La (left) and Gd (right) concentrations in ng per daphnia in *D. magna* after 21 days of exposure. Brackets represents the 2.5 and 97.5 percentiles. White: control (Ctr), green: dietary exposure (D), purple: waterborne exposure (W), red: combined exposure (DW).

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Figure 6-4 Lanthanum distribution in 21-day-old *Daphnia magna* according μ XRF measurements. Grey: calcium, red: lanthanum. D: Dietary exposure, W: waterborne exposure and DW: Dietary and Waterborne exposure. Energy: 50kV, pixel size: 25 μ m and acquisition time: 1.5s pixel⁻¹.

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Table 6-3 Effect of La on reproduction of *D. magna*. Average \pm standard deviation. Significant differences between the control and the different exposures are indicated by * $q < 0.05$. ** $q < 0.01$. **** $q < 0.001$, NS, not significant effect.

La	Control	Dietary	Waterborne	Waterborne + Dietary
Total reproduction in 21 days (juveniles/daphnid)	0.00 \pm 9.82	-3.86 \pm 1.99 $\times 10^{+014}$ NS	-2.07 \pm 1.40 $\times 10^{+01}$ NS	-5.15 \pm 1.71 $\times 10^{+01}$ NS
1 st brood day	3.09 $\times 10^{-16}$ \pm 1.13	9.18 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 2.20 NS	9.68 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 1.62 NS	1.13 \pm 1.26*
2 nd brood day	-7.72 $\times 10^{-17}$ \pm 9.90 $\times 10^{-01}$	7.49 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 2.22 NS	6.71 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 1.66 NS	8.17 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 1.31 NS
3 rd brood day	-3.09 $\times 10^{-16}$ \pm 1.22	-1.23 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 7.42 $\times 10^{-01}$ NS	1.24 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 1.58 NS	5.50 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 1.44 NS
4 th brood day	4.84 $\times 10^{-16}$ \pm 1.18	2.95 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 7.71 $\times 10^{-01}$ NS	5.03 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 1.18 NS	6.46 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 1.13 NS
5 th brood day	7.11 $\times 10^{-16}$ \pm 3.65 $\times 10^{-01}$	-4.73 \pm 8.91 NS	-3.67 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 6.12 $\times 10^{-01}$ NS	-3.80 \pm 8.46 NS
1 st brood size (juveniles/brood)	3.09 $\times 10^{-16}$ \pm 3.40	3.39 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 2.56 NS	6.97 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 3.48 NS	-9.60 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 3.52 NS
2 nd brood size (juveniles/brood)	-4.63 $\times 10^{-16}$ \pm 3.80	-1.37 \pm 4.70 NS	3.92 \pm 5.38 NS	-8.33 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 4.08 NS
3 rd brood size (juveniles/brood)	1.54 $\times 10^{-16}$ \pm 4.59	2.67 \pm 8.08 NS	1.91 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 5.51 NS	3.78 \pm 6.08 NS
4 th brood size (juveniles/brood)	-3.23 $\times 10^{-16}$ \pm 3.05	-6.85 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 4.54 NS	-3.58 \pm 5.59 NS	-9.45 $\times 10^{-01}$ \pm 5.81 NS
5 th brood size (juveniles/brood)	8.88 $\times 10^{-16}$ \pm 2.62	6.32 \pm 6.81 NS	1.80 \pm 3.81 NS	4.24 \pm 4.52 NS

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Table 6-4 Effect of Gd on reproduction of *D. magna*. Average \pm standard deviation. Significant differences between the control and the different exposures are indicated by * $q < 0.05$. ** $q < 0.01$. *** $q < 0.001$, NS, not significant effect.

Gd	Control	Dietary	Waterborne	Waterborne + Dietary
Total reproduction in 21 days (juveniles/daphnid)	$-2.21 \pm 1.80 \times 10^{+01}$	$-1.58 \times 10^{+01} \pm 1.32 \times 10^{+01}***$	$-1.06 \times 10^{+01} \pm 1.61 \times 10^{+01} NS$	$-2.19 \times 10^{+01} \pm 1.79 \times 10^{+01}***$
1 st brood day	$-9.47 \times 10^{-02} \pm 6.57 \times 10^{-01}$	$2.53 \times 10^{-01} \pm 1.17 NS$	$2.19 \times 10^{-01} \pm 1.43 NS$	$7.14 \times 10^{-02} \pm 9.82 \times 10^{-01} NS$
2 nd brood day	$-7.82 \times 10^{-02} \pm 8.33 \times 10^{-01}$	$-6.55 \times 10^{-02} \pm 1.36 NS$	$3.45 \times 10^{-03} \pm 1.47 NS$	$2.86 \times 10^{-01} \pm 1.33 NS$
3 rd brood day	$-5.35 \times 10^{-02} \pm 1.28$	$8.62 \times 10^{-02} \pm 1.90 NS$	$2.59 \times 10^{-01} \pm 2.10 NS$	$1.28 \times 10^{-01} \pm 1.59 NS$
4 th brood day	$1.32 \times 10^{-16} \pm 8.38 \times 10^{-01}$	$5.14 \times 10^{-02} \pm 1.06 NS$	$1.94 \times 10^{-01} \pm 1.07 NS$	$1.71 \times 10^{-01} \pm 6.37 \times 10^{-01} NS$
5 th brood day	$-5.08 \times 10^{-16} \pm 5.92 \times 10^{-01}$	$-8.89 \times 10^{-02} \pm 6.04 \times 10^{-01} NS$	$2.58 \times 10^{-01} \pm 1.78 \times 10^{-01} NS$	$1.73 \times 10^{-01} \pm 9.80 \times 10^{-02} NS$
1 st brood size (juveniles/brood)	$-6.58 \times 10^{-16} \pm 4.26$	$-7.25 \times 10^{-01} \pm 5.50 NS$	$-8.98 \times 10^{-01} \pm 4.92 NS$	$-4.33 \times 10^{-01} \pm 6.76 NS$
2 nd brood size (juveniles/brood)	$4.12 \times 10^{-03} \pm 4.58$	$-2.49 \pm 5.18 NS$	$-1.21 \pm 4.75 NS$	$-1.50 \pm 3.60 NS$
3 rd brood size (juveniles/brood)	$1.28 \times 10^{-01} \pm 3.60$	$-1.48 \pm 5.22 NS$	$-2.13 \pm 4.00 NS$	$-5.57 \pm 5.79***$
4 th brood size (juveniles/brood)	$3.95 \times 10^{-16} \pm 3.89$	$-4.79 \pm 5.91*$	$-1.97 \pm 3.43 NS$	$-4.14 \pm 7.47*$
5 th brood size (juveniles/brood)	0.00 ± 5.28	$-2.00 \pm 5.91 NS$	$-2.59 \pm 4.96 NS$	$-3.78 \pm 4.87 NS$

6.4. Discussion

The objective of the present study was to investigate toxicity of chronic exposure of La and Gd through different exposure routes for *D. magna*, as well as compare toxicokinetic for La and Gd. The first hypothesis, that exposure via the water phase would have the strongest toxic effect, was not confirmed. When assessing the chronic toxicity of REE on daphnids, it was observed that none of the exposure types—dietary, waterborne, or combined—had any impact on the survival, growth, or dry weight of *Daphnia magna*. However, dietary and combined exposures were able to affect the reproduction of the exposed organisms: 1) a combined La exposure delayed the first brood of the organisms, 2) dietary and combined Gd exposures affected the 3rd and 4th brood, reducing the number of offspring per adult. The impact of dietary REE exposure aligns with the findings of several studies showing that dietary exposure to metals does not induce general stress on crustacean, but specifically hinders their reproduction (De Schampelaere *et al.*, 2007; Hook and Fisher, 2001). However, the absence of discernible effects from the waterborne exposures refutes the hypothesis that waterborne exposure constitutes the main route for toxic effect. Nevertheless, there is also a potential for metals to leach from the microalgae, potentially resulting in waterborne exposure during dietary exposure.

Microalgae tests demonstrate that La stimulated the growth rate of *R. subcapitata* used as food for daphnids, whereas Gd inhibited it. This suggests that REE toxicity on microalgae increases with their atomic number (González *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, the study reveals that microalgae accumulated a significant amount of REE after 72 hours of exposure. Both metals were comparably accumulated by the microalgae, reaching around 2×10^{-05} ng of REE per cell after 72 hours of exposure (Figure 6-1). Although, it remains uncertain whether this accumulation was intracellular (absorbed) or extracellular (adsorbed), given that the organisms were not subjected to EDTA cleaning prior to measurements. However, the pre-experiments measuring dissolved REE concentrations without daphnids revealed that after two days of exposure, the actual dissolved La concentrations were much lower than the nominal concentration of 0.5 mg L^{-1} (Figure 6-2). In contrast, dissolved Gd concentrations were equal or slightly lower than 0.5 mg L^{-1} . This difference of concentration might be due to metal precipitation or metal adsorption to the plastic wells or to the microalgae. Indeed, the observed disparity in dissolved concentration between La and Gd can be attributed to differences in metal solubility. La has a higher tendency to precipitate as carbonate, which is derived from reaction with naturally present soluble carbon dioxide/bicarbonate under ambient pressure conditions (Smith, Martell and Motekaitis, 2004). However, microalgae are also recognized to be effective biosorbents for metals (Spain, Plöhn and Funk, 2021) and can accumulate REE in their cytoplasm or chloroplast (Řezanka *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, the results of the pre-experiments reject the risks of a REE

desorption in the media in the presence of contaminated microalgae which partly confirms the hypothesis that the chronic daphnia test responds to dietary exposure.

The metal biodistribution and bioaccumulation analysis gave a first insight into the mechanism of action of REE in *D. magna*. This analysis allowed to verify the second hypothesis of the present study that assumed that toxicity of REE is linked to a specific metal biodistribution in the tissues of the organism. The effects of REE on *D. magna* reproduction appeared to be positively correlated with the REE body burden in *D. magna*. The highest values were found to be in the daphnids exposed to dietary and combined exposures. These findings suggest that the ingestion of contaminated microalgae allows for a highest REE bioaccumulation and could explain why the waterborne exposure does not affect the organism. These results further validate the potential toxic effects of dietary REE exposure on *D. magna*. According to the μ XRF measurements, all La exposure led to a similar biodistribution in the organisms (Figure 6-4). Indeed, La mainly bioaccumulated in the intestinal tract of the daphnids which may result from metal precipitation leading to ingestion of the metal particles from the medium, or be due to a strong metal adsorption by the microalgae (He and Chen, 2014). Metals adsorbed by microalgae can be ingested by organisms, leading to metal transfer and bioconcentration throughout the food chain (Barata *et al.*, 2002). Compared to La, Gd biodistribution varied with the type of exposure. The dietary exposure for Gd, that affect the reproduction of *D. magna*, led to metal accumulation in the intestinal tract. REE could potentially be desorbed after uptake into the organism, for example due to lowered pH (around 5.5-6.0) in the gut of the *Daphnia* (Davis *et al.*, 2020). In contrast, the waterborne exposure seems to provide more diffuse accumulation inside the organism but did not cause any effect to the organisms. Therefore, these results reject the hypothesis that only metal biodistributed in the tissues can affect *D. magna*. However, the limit of detection of the Tornado XRF might not allow for the detection of very low signals compared to synchrotron XRF (Dias *et al.*, 2015).

Therefore, it is likely that a fraction of the diffuse La and Gd is not visible in the images taken with the Tornado XRF. Similar problem might appear regarding the metal biodistribution on the eggs of the organisms, that is a common observation for metal that affect *D. magna* reproduction (Evens *et al.*, 2012). In the present study, it is possible that low REE accumulation occurred within the eggs and could not be detected by the Tornado XRF. However, the bioaccumulation observed implies that the effects of REE might indirectly influence the mother organism rather than directly affecting the new generations. However, it also has been established that metal such as zinc (Zn) affected the reproduction of *D. magna* in accumulating in the gut epithelium (Evens *et al.*, 2012). This accumulation can reduce the digestive enzyme activity and potentially affecting the nutrient absorption. This hypothesis is aligning with the conclusions of De Schamphelaere *et al.* (2007) who indicated that chronic Cu toxicity was not dependent

on the dissolved Cu and that dietary exposure could directly affect the reproduction and growth of *D. magna* by inhibiting the vitellogenesis or affecting energy acquisition and consumption.

While the present study has demonstrated the importance of considering both La and Gd dietary exposure in cases of chronic exposure to *D. magna*, it also does not reject the third hypothesis that assumes a difference in both the toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic of the two REE within aquatic organisms. This difference was first visualized for microalgae, as the stimulation of their growth was stronger with La compared to Gd. With regards to the effects on *D. magna*, two distinct effects on their reproduction were recorded depending on the metal. As previously explained, La exposure delayed the first release of the first brood while Gd exposure led to a reduction in the overall number of offspring produced. Therefore, the impact of Gd raised more significant ecotoxicological concerns for *D. magna* reproduction than that of La. Gd effects can be considered to have a stronger and longer impact on the daphnid population cycle. Considering their key function in the aquatic food chain, this may have long-lasting effects on the biological community.

6.5. Conclusion

The present study has demonstrated the role of dietary exposure in REE chronic toxicity to *D. magna* and the differences in toxicity and toxicokinetic between La and Gd. Both metals affect the reproduction of *D. magna* only after 21 days exposures, on a different manner. For La a slight delay in the release of the first brood while Gd significantly decreased the total offspring of the organisms. These effects were not correlated with the dissolved metal concentrations but appeared to be more closely related to the REE bioaccumulation and biodistribution within the organism. The dietary exposure seemed to be the major uptake route as the REE bioaccumulated more than through the waterborne route. The observed reproductive effects appear to occur when metals accumulate in the gut which confirm the importance of taking the dietary exposure into account for long term bioassays. Additional studies need to be conducted to explore the effects of REE on the gut and energy limitations, aiming to gain a better understanding of the mode of action of these emerging contaminants on *D. magna*. Some of these future experiments could potentially focus on the analysis of the yolk-metal binding and yolk (vitellogenin) levels in exposed and unexposed *Daphnia*, or other physiological markers (e.g., cholinesterase activity).

Author contribution

Author contribution is in alphabetical order of surname. Conceptualization and study design by Marion Revel, Susanne Heise, and Chantal van Drimmelen. Frederika Mišíková, Edith Padilla Suarez,

Marion Revel, and Chantal van Drimmelen, were responsible for conducting the bioassays with chronic daphnia test. Susanne Heise, Marion Revel, and Chantal van Drimmelen conducted the TXRF measurements to study the metal bioaccumulation in microalgae and daphnids. The REE dissolved concentration was quantified by ICP-MS by Frederika Mišíková at the Institute of Environmental and Chemical Engineering from the University of Pardubice. Microalgae bioassays, preparation of the samples for μ XRF measurements, analysis and interpretation of all data were performed by Marion Revel and Chantal van Drimmelen. The first draft of the paper was jointly written by Marion Revel (Materials and Methods, Results, and Discussion) and Chantal van Drimmelen (Abstract, Introduction, Results, and Discussion). It was then reviewed, expanded, and edited by Marion Revel, Susanne Heise, Andrew Hursthouse, Fredericka Mišíková, Edith Padilla Suarez, and Chantal van Drimmelen. All authors agreed on the final version.

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CHAPTER 7

TO AVOID OR NOT TO AVOID RARE EARTH ELEMENT CONTAMINATED SEDIMENT? THAT IS THE QUESTION FOR *DAPHNIA MAGNA*

Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen^{1,2}, Andrew S. Hursthouse², Susanne Heise¹

Keywords: Avoidance behavior, Lanthanides, Sediment, Freshwater, Movement, Video recording

¹ Life Sciences, Hamburg University of Applied Science, Ulmenliet 20, D-21033 Hamburg, Germany

² University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Abstract

Rare earth elements (REE) are an emerging class of contaminants recently becoming enriched in many freshwater bodies. These elements associate with sediment and fine organic matter and resuspension of sediment can make REE bioavailable to not only to benthic species but also pelagic organisms. Studies on REE contaminated sediment and pelagic invertebrates are limited, with most research focusing on mortality and immobilization endpoints. However, behavioral endpoints, such as avoidance behavior, could support assessing an environmental risk. This study aims to determine if sediment contaminated with two REE, lanthanum (La) and gadolinium (Gd), leads to avoidance behavior by pelagic species like *Daphnia magna*. Conventional experimental vessels were not suitable for the study and custom 3D printed vessels were developed to measure avoidance behavior through the assessment of horizontal (a round vessel) and vertical (a rectangular vessel) migration. The vessels were filled with clean media and sediment spiked with different concentrations of La and Gd (0.001; 0.01; 0.1; 1; 10; 25; 50; 75; 100 mg kg⁻¹) ranging from natural background to enriched concentration levels. Results showed that avoidance behavior was more evident for Gd than La, which is likely to be due to the bioavailability of the elements within the sediment. Avoidance behavior was observed in the vertical experiments. The exact mechanisms behind the impact on daphnia behavior remain unclear. Dissolved Gd and La led to increased agitation in swimming. The study highlights the importance of further research on how REE

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contaminated sediment impacts behavior within pelagic organisms and if they can sense REE through mechanisms linked to, for example, competition with calcium. The avoidance of contaminated REE sediment by *D. magna* could affect population dynamics and increase the risk of predation. The method developed here introduces an additional more sensitive approach to risk assessment, allowing for digital analysis of video recordings to measure horizontal and vertical migration of pelagic species exposed to contaminated sediment.

7.1. Introduction

Rare earth elements (REE) are considered as an emerging class of pollutants with positive Gd and La anomalies now found almost in all urban freshwater bodies (Bau and Dulski, 1996; Kulaksız and Bau, 2013). They are known to partition to sediment and fine organic matter (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018; Schaller, 2013; Tijink and Yland, 1998; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b) causing the concentrations of REE in the sediment to be much higher than in the water phase (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). The sediment bound REE may become available to pelagic organisms via sediment resuspension and change in environmental conditions (e.g., extreme floods, pH changes, human activities like dredging) that they can become bioavailable (Mori, 1999). They can also become bioavailable to organisms through interactions, such as ingestion of sediment particles. However, REE sticking to the sediment can still affect benthic species, not only because of potential adverse effects but also because other species (e.g., food sources for the benthic species) might avoid the contaminated sediment causing them for example not being able to feed on pelagic species. Thus, sediment should also be considered as a potential source of REE toxicity in freshwater ecosystems.

However, most conventional ecotoxicity bioassays are currently established for acute and chronic effects for media and not for sediment. The tests that are conducted with sediment focus logically on benthic organisms and studies with pelagic species are limited (Johns *et al.*, 2023). Most of the research on REE and crustaceans is based on the evaluation of EC_{50s} for mortality and immobilization (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). Although these two endpoints are mainly used for toxicity determination, there are more sensitive endpoints such as behavior. Avoidance behavior often can occur directly upon contact with contaminated sediment, while other endpoints like mortality are more likely to take place over longer time periods (Moreira-Santos, Ribeiro and Araújo, 2019). Behavioral endpoints are not standardized within ecotoxicological testing (Moreira-Santos, Ribeiro and Araújo, 2019; Ågerstrand *et al.*, 2020), but the incorporation of these endpoints could assist in the risk assessment of various contaminants (Moreira-Santos, Ribeiro and Araújo, 2019).

Daphnia are common invertebrates that play a key role in freshwater ecosystems. They are filter feeders and regulate the population density of microorganisms such as microalgae. They are also a food source for various species of predators such as fish, tadpoles, salamanders, and aquatic insects. Daphnia apply vertical migration to avoid predators (Bownik, 2017). During the day daphnids move up in the water and during the night they move to the sediment. In this paper, we focus on the possibility that active avoidance may be a direct effect of REE. Daphnids are able to detect dissolved heavy metals in the surrounding as they responded to a copper gradient (Lopes, Baird and Ribeiro, 2004). To our knowledge, this is the first study to test daphnia behavioral changes in response to REE-contaminated sediments, which could be environmentally relevant at concentrations far below any toxicity thresholds. The objective

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of this study was to determine if sediment contaminated with two REE, lanthanum (La) and gadolinium (Gd), leads to avoidance behaviour by pelagic species such as *Daphnia magna*. La and Gd were chosen due to their wide spread of positive anomalies in global water bodies and being well studied in ecotoxicology (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Rogowska *et al.*, 2018; Trapasso *et al.*, 2021).

While swimming behavior of daphnia is complex it is also known to be affected by various substances (Bownik, 2017). If organisms actively avoid REE-contaminated sediments, changes in their behavior may have effects on their energy metabolism and survival rate, e.g., by rendering them more susceptible to predators (Bownik, 2017). To our knowledge only the effect of CeO₂ nanoparticles (Artells *et al.*, 2013) within the group of REE has been tested in relation to the swimming behavior of daphnids. However, the use of nanoparticles makes the results in regard to chemical behavior not comparable with the present study.

It has been observed in previous studies that *D. magna* grazed on the bottom on nanocosm experiments in the control but not those with REE contaminated sediment (van Drimmelen *et al.*, in preparation). Daphnia grazing on the bottom has been observed in other studies as well (Hessen, Alstad and Skardal, 2000). We hypothesize that, presuming that avoidance behaviour is a more sensitive end point compared to mortality, that avoidance behaviour will occur both for vertical and horizontal migration for *D. magna*. Horizontal migration is used as an indicator for the response to different environmental factors (e.g., predation pressure or food concentration) for microcrustaceans like daphnia. The vertical migration in the water column is altered by behavioural responses to light, predation, and temperature. The vertical migration requires more energetic potential of the daphnia than horizontal swimming (Bownik, 2017). From previous experiments it is also expected that there will be a difference at different concentrations between La and Gd in behaviour due to the mode of action of the two REE within the sediment (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016).

7.2. Materials and Methods

7.2.1. Maintenance of the Daphnia Culture

A culture of *Daphnia magna* that has been originally acquired from the German Environmental Ministry (UBA) is maintained at the Hamburg University of Applied Science in compliance with the International Standard (ISO, 2012). Daphnids are kept in Elendt M4 medium (OECD, 2012) at 21 ± 1°C with a 16:8 light-dark cycle. The medium is exchanged once per week. Daphnids are fed daily with the freshwater microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* (Collection of Algae at the University of Göttingen (SAG 211-11b)).

7.2.2. Experimental vessels

Tests were carried out in PETG chambers in order to avoid the strong adsorption that La and Gd show in the presence of glass surfaces (Reimann, Birke and Filzmoser, 2010). PETG is closest to PET to which REE have been shown to adsorb least and was chosen as PET filament was not readily available. Self-designed chambers were 3D printed from transparent PETG filament (Overture, diameter 1.75 mm using a SOVOL SV06 3D printer). Printing speed was 15 mm/s, with infill 100% aligned rectilinear and 2.5% infill anchor, extrusion multiplier 1.025, fan speed 0%. The nozzle temperature was 230°C and 70°C for the bed. For the horizontal migration test, a round vessel was printed with a diameter of 32 mm separated by a wall of 1 mm, with wall thickness 2 mm and bottom thickness 2.5 mm (**SI7-1**). For the vertical migration, a rectangle experimental vessel was printed with dimensions 71.2 mm by 34.3 mm by 11.2 mm with wall thickness of 0.6 mm and bottom thickness of 1.8 mm (**SI7-2**).

7.2.3. Sediment spiking and medium

The test medium was prepared from M4-Medium (pH 6.8 ± 0.2) (ISO, 2012), without EDTA, as it might interfere with REE in the test medium. For the uncontaminated sediment LUFA-Speyer 2.2 (Speyer, Germany, **SI7-3** Composition of Lufa-soil 2.2) (pH 5.6 ± 0.3) was used. The LUFA 2.2 matrix is a natural and well-defined sediment used in many soil and sediment tests (Domene *et al.*, 2011; Römbke *et al.*, 2006; Höss *et al.*, 2009). The sediment was spiked with anthropogenic concentrations of Gd and La ($\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{LaCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99% purity; Sigma Aldrich) at 25; 50; 75; 100 mg kg^{-1} , and environmentally relevant concentrations of 0.001; 0.01; 0.1; 1; 10 mg kg^{-1} . For each g of sediment 0.4 mL of the medium was added to make the sediment moldable and to fully being able to homogenize the sediment the REE. The mixing of the sediment was thoroughly done by hand for at least 2 minutes. The sediment was kept for 1h at 20°C in order for the REE to stabilize within the sediment. The experimental vessels were filled with 2.20 g and 5.80 g of wet sediment and 3 mL and 14.2 mL of medium for the horizontal and vertical vessel, respectively. The pH was measured at the beginning (t_0) and end of the experiment (t_3) to determine if the pH stayed in the limit of the test (6.0 ± 0.2).

7.2.4. Procedure for the Behavioral tests

Adult daphnia (10 days) were used for the tests because they are more easily identifiable on the sediment due to their size. Each daphnia was carefully separately placed into the vessel with a pipet from which the tip was cut off. For each treatment three replicates with three adult *D. magna* were observed for 15 seconds according to the OECD Test No. 202 (OECD, 2004) at 0h, 1h, 2h, and 3h. Scoring of the daphnia was based on the location of the daphnia within the experimental vessel for a 15 second period. Scoring was always carried out by two people independently and at the same time in order to avoid bias.

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If there was a disagreement for the scoring, it was discussed and based on the arguments a discussion was made or the scoring was averaged.

We defined horizontal migration as the movement of the daphnia to either the left or right side of the experimental vessel in order to test if there was a preference for uncontaminated or contaminated sediment. For the horizontal vessel (Figure 7-1) the scoring was as follows: if during the 15 seconds the daphnia remained predominantly on the uncontaminated side the score was 0 if the daphnia was mostly on the contaminated side a score of 1 was assigned. If the daphnia remained on the dividing wall or moved too much from one side to another, without a preference, it was scored 0.5. The control vessels had uncontaminated sediment on both sides and were scored based on the daphnia being on the left or right side.

The vertical migration was seen as the up and down swimming behavior of daphnia. For the vertical vessel (Figure 7-2) the scoring was as follows: Daphnia could be scored between 1-3 for 15 seconds, with 1 being closer to the sediment and 3 being the top of the water column based on zones divided in 0.5 cm. Thus, the farther away the daphnia was from the sediment the higher the score. If the daphnia moved too frequently up and down, it was scored 2. If the daphnia were in between zones, it would be assigned a 0.5 increment, thus for example if a daphnia would be between 1 and 2 it got the score 1.5. The experiment was repeated five times (thus 15 daphnia in total per treatment).

Figure 7-1 Horizontal migration experimental vessel for scoring avoidance behaviour of *D. magna* for 15 seconds. 0 = Uncontaminated sediment, 1 = contaminated sediment, and 0.5 = on the division line or no preference for either side. Control had uncontaminated sediment on both sides, the contaminated site was either La or Gd at different concentrations.

Figure 7-2 Vertical migration experimental vessel for scoring avoidance behaviour of *D. magna* for 15 seconds. Scoring is based on zones between 1-3, with 1 being closed to the sediment and 3 being higher up in the water column. If the daphnia is in between zones, it would be assigned a X.5. Sediment was either uncontaminated or contaminated with La or Gd at different concentrations.

7.2.5. Video recording of movement

Video recording was applied in order to see if the daphnia could sense the REE and if this led to an activation or deactivation. This was measured through the average distance moved and active time of *D. magna* when exposed to media contaminated with Gd or La spike for up to three hours. The tests were performed in 24 well microplates (Costar 2524, Corning Incorporated) with anthropogenic REE concentrations at 25; 50; 75; 100 mg L⁻¹, and environmentally relevant concentrations of 0.001; 0.01; 0.1; 1; 10 mg L⁻¹. Each well contained individual adult daphnia, with a total of 5 adults per concentration.

The individual adults were recorded with an infrared sensitive digital camera (IDS camera, IDS Imaging Development Systems GmbH, Germany) in two dimensions for 5 minutes at 0h, 1h, 2h, and 3h by placing the plates on an IR light panel (Loligo Systems, Viborg, Denmark). In between each recording the plates were kept in the same room in the dark at temperature 20 ± 1°C to prevent the need for daphnia to adjust to environmental changes. Before each recording the plates were shaken for 15 seconds on a horizontal shaker at 250 rpm (IKA, MTS 2/4 digital microplate shaker). The recorded videos were then analyzed with LoliTrack 5 software through subtracting static background pixels and exported as .xlsx files.

7.2.6. Determination of Dissolved Concentrations

Total reflection X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (TXRF; S4 T-Star; Bruker Nano GmbH, Berlin Germany, S18-1 TXRF information and quality sheet) was used to quantify dissolved concentrations of La and Gd in individual *D. magna*, water samples, and sediment samples.

Prior to digestion, daphnia were dried at 80°C for at least 24h. Three adults were digested together for minimal 48h in 1.5 mL reagent tubes containing 45 µL of pure water, 400 µL of HNO₃ (65%, Roth,

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4989.1) 50 μL of HCl (35-38%, p.a., Th. Geyer, 836.2500) and 5 μL of gallium (Ga) internal standard (standard concentration 10 mg L^{-1} ; VHG; VHG-PGANH-100). The Ga standard was 0.1 g L^{-1} for the control and REE concentrations of 0.1, 0.01, and 0.001 mg L^{-1} and 1 g L^{-1} of Ga for concentrations equal or higher than 1 mg L^{-1} . The solution was then diluted with pure water in a 1:5 ratio of 20 μL of the digested sample and 80 μL of pure water. To this dilution was 5 μL of 3% polyvinyl alcohol (9002-89-5, Carl Roth) added for a more homogenous spreading of the sample on the quartz disc (personal communication Bruker Nano GmbH). For the water samples the ratio was 480 μL of the sample with 12 μL HNO_3 , and 5 μL Ga with the same standards as for the daphnia digestion.

The sediment samples were dried at 70°C for at least 24 hours before being digested following the US EPA 3051a (US EPA, 2007) method with microwave digestion (MARS6 by CEM). From each dried sample 0.5 g were transferred into Teflon tubes. Then, 9 mL HNO_3 and 3 mL HCl were added. The Teflon tubes were then digested in the MARS 6 at 175°C for 4.5 minutes after 5.5 minutes of warming up. After the samples reached room temperature, 12 mL were transferred to 50 mL Falcon tubes. From this solution 20 μL samples were diluted with 80 μL of pure water and 3% polyvinyl alcohol and 5 μL of gallium (Ga) internal standard as described above for the daphnia digestion.

For each sample, 10 μL of the solution were pipetted onto a quartz carrier disc. The disc was then warmed at 60°C on a heating plate until the drop had evaporated, and a second 10 μL drop was put on the disc and evaporated. The disc was then placed in an oven without fan at 100°C for one hour. The discs were analyzed with the TXRF (Puls: 130 kcps; Maximum energy mode: 40 keV; Excitation: Mo 17.5; Time: 1000 sec.; Type of quantification: liquid; Calibration data: Mo-Ka 17.5, **S18-1** TXRF information and quality sheet) and the REE concentrations were calculated from the spectrum obtained with TESprit 1.0 software (Bruker Nano GmbH, Berlin Germany).

7.2.7. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism version 10.0.2 for Windows. The average scoring for both the horizontal and vertical avoidance behavior of *D. magna* was visualized in heatmaps (N = 60). This was combined with frequency distribution using the chi-square test comparing the different REE concentrations to the control for both the horizontal and vertical migration behavior. The signal for the chi-square is more robust due to the different exposure times applied as replicates. The average distance moved (in pixels) and the time active in seconds were extracted from the .xlsx files and analyzed for normal distribution with Shapiro Wilk and further analyzed through a Two-way ANOVA ($p = 0.0002$, N = 20) with a Tukey's for multiple comparison. The p-value was always 0.05 as reference.

7.3. Results

7.3.1. TXRF results

No Gd or La were detected in the digested daphnids (LoD Gd: 0.002 mg kg⁻¹, and LoD La: 0.004 mg kg⁻¹) (Table 7-1). REE concentrations in experiments where sediments had been spiked with less than 10 mg kg⁻¹ were not detectable anymore after 3 hours by TXRF in water or sediment. Most of the measured REE was found back in the sediment phase by an order of magnitude more compared to the media phase. La was more bound to the sediment than Gd, indicating that Gd is more remobilized in the water phase.

Table 7-1 Average measured concentrations for Gd and La at nominal concentrations 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 mg kg⁻¹ for adult *D. magna*, water samples and sediment samples after 3 hour exposure.

REE	Nominal concentration mg kg ⁻¹	<i>D. magna</i> body burden mg kg ⁻¹	Water samples mg L ⁻¹	Sediment samples mg kg ⁻¹	Difference from nominal concentration in mg kg ⁻¹	Difference from nominal concentration in %
Control	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
Gd	0.001	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.001	100*
Gd	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01	100*
Gd	0.1	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.1	100*
Gd	1	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1	100*
Gd	10	0.00	0.00	0.60	-9.40	94
Gd	25	0.00	0.21	8.57	-16.22	64.88
Gd	50	0.00	0.26	31.83	-17.91	35.82
Gd	75	0.00	1.26	59.20	-14.54	19.39
Gd	100	0.00	1.19	66.63	-32.18	32.18
La	0.001	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.001	100*
La	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01	100*
La	0.1	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.1	100*
La	1	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1	100
La	10	0.00	0.00	3.57	-6.25	62.50
La	25	0.00	0.01	22.07	-2.92	11.68
La	50	0.00	0.23	39.10	-10.67	21.34
La	75	0.00	0.64	59.23	-15.13	20.17
La	100	0.00	0.42	74.73	-24.85	24.85

*Below the detection limited of the TXRF

7.3.2. Horizontal Migration

No preference ($p = 0.3459$) for the uncontaminated site for Gd compared to the control was observed in the horizontal migration (Figure 7-3). The control does not indicate a preference for either the left or right side of the vessel, as at expoure time 0 the control is shown in green (score 0) but shifts

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overtime to red (score 1.0), green, and yellow (score 0.5). Gadolinium shows for most nominal concentrations that the average scoring was 0.5 in yellow, with some spots in red and one in green at Gd 75 mg kg⁻¹ at 1h.

For La, the daphnia showed no preference for either the uncontaminated or contaminated site. Up to the La 25 mg kg⁻¹ concentration there is a similar pattern compared to the control. At the different exposure times there appears to be a pattern mixing the average scoring values. The concentrations 50-100 mg kg⁻¹ of La show a pattern similar to Gd where most values are 0.5 in yellow, with some 1.0 scoring in red. Thus indicating no preference for the uncontaminated side.

The frequency distribution (SI7-4), which is a more robust signal than the heatmap, was found to be significant for Gd at concentrations 50; 1; 0,01; and 0.001 mg kg⁻¹ compared to the control (p = 0.0116, 0.0158, 0.0168, and 0.0341 respectively) . La was not found to be significantly different from the control (p = 0.2578).

Figure 7-3 Average scoring of the horizontal vessel visualized in a heatmap with the *D. magna* being on 0 (green) uncontaminated sediment, 1.0 (red) contaminated sediment, and 0.5 (yellow) indicating no preference for either side at exposure time 0-3h. Control was measured using uncontaminated sediment for both sides. On the left Gd and on the right La.

7.3.3. Vertical Migration

For the vertical migration, the heatmap (Figure 7-4) showed that both Gd and La cause avoidance behavior in *D. magna* compared to the control. For Gd this was the case for all exposure concentrations as most average scoring points are above 2.0 (light blue), while the control is 2.0 up to exposure time 1h and then moves onto the sediment at 2h.

For La the avoidance behaviour was only observed for the anthropogenic concentrations (25-100 mg kg⁻¹) with the average scoring being above 2.0. For the environmental concentrations (0.001-10 mg kg⁻¹) the daphnia moved, at around 2h, or stayed on the sediment overtime just like the control.

The vertical avoidance behaviour shown in the heatmaps was in agreement with the frequency distribution (SI7-4) where both Gd ($p < 0.0001$) and La ($p = 0.0007$) were overall significantly different from the control. For Gd only the lowest concentration 0.001 mg kg^{-1} was not significantly different ($p = 0.0643$). However, for La it was mostly of the environmental relevant concentrations at 10; 0.01; and 0.001 mg kg^{-1} that were not significantly different from the control.

Figure 7-4 Average scoring of the vertical vessel visualized in a heatmap with the *D. magna* being on the sediment 1.0 (brown) or further into the water column 3.0 (dark blue) at exposure time 0-3h. On the left Gd and on the right La.

7.3.4. Video movement measurements

The trend and significant differences ($p = 0.0002$, $N = 20$) of the two REE compared to the control for both the distance moved and the time that the adult daphnids were active indicate that *D. magna* became more agitated when exposed to either Gd or La. Figure 7-5 shows a general pattern of both Gd and La increase the distance moved by *D. magna* compared to the control. For Gd only 1 ($p = 0.018$) and 100 mg L^{-1} ($p = 0.045$) have been found to differ significantly compared to the control. For lanthanum the environmental concentrations ($0.001\text{-}0.1 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$), with expectation of 1 mg L^{-1} ($p = 0.0133$), were not found to be significantly different. La 50 ($p < 0.0001$) and 75 mg L^{-1} ($p = 0.0005$) did significantly differ from the control. No significant difference between the REE was found for the amount of distance moved.

The video recording data showed a trend where adult *D. magna* became more active when exposed to the REE than when compared to the control (Figure 7-6). Noticeable is that the active time between the two REE is also similar. Gadolinium was found to be not significantly different compared to the control at 0.01 and 0.1 mg L^{-1} , all other concentrations did differ significantly. Almost all concentrations of La were significantly different from the control, with the exception of 0.01 mg L^{-1} .

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Figure 7-5 Distance moved in pixels at time points 0,1,2, and 3 hours by adult *D. magna* exposed to Gd (left) and La (right) at concentrations 0.001, 1, 10, and 100 mg L⁻¹. See S17-5 for the graphs with all the exposure concentrations.

Figure 7-6 Active time in seconds at time points 0,1,2, and 3 hours by adult *D. magna* exposed to Gd (left) and La (right) at concentrations 0.001, 1, 10, and 100 mg L⁻¹. See S17-5 for the graphs with all the exposure concentrations.

7.4. Discussion

The objective of the study was to determine if the avoidance behavior by pelagic species, such as *D. magna*, could be caused by the contamination of sediment with either La or Gd. A difference in avoidance behavior of *D. magna* between the two REE at the various concentrations was validated and was probably due to the mode of action of the individual REE. The difference in avoidance behavior based on concentrations has also been found for copper. *D. magna* exposed to a mixture of glyphosate and copper showed concentration-dependent inhibition to swimming speed (mm/s²) (Hansen and Roslev, 2016). It has also been demonstrated that *Daphnia longispina* actively avoids chemical stress caused by copper and that this is concentration dependent (Lopes, Baird and Ribeiro, 2004). Thus, this confirms that the results for the avoidance behavior for REE contaminated sediment are related to the dissolved concentrations of the elements. However, as far as the authors know there have not been any comparable studies performed with the other REE. What is known is that Gd is more toxic than La for *D. magna* (Blinova *et al.*, 2018a) and this could be linked to the avoidance behavior already showing up more clearly for Gd in comparison to La.

The chemical speciation and partitioning of REE in sediment and pore water varies among the different REE due to the specific chemical speciation of the individual element, which is influenced by physicochemical parameters (Moermond *et al.*, 2001). The relationship between the different REE and sediment and organic matter is very complex. For inter-elemental comparison the REE elements have been categorized in subgroups based on their atomic weight; light (LREEs; La to Sm) and heavy (HREEs; Gd to Lu). LREE are more likely to adsorb to organic matter than HREE which prefer to form complexes with carbonates (Smrzka *et al.*, 2019). This results in the higher concentration of LREEs in natural sediments compared to HREEs (Brito *et al.*, 2018; Jiang *et al.*, 2022). It is also known that LREE cycle in aquatic environments much more efficiently than HREEs (Sholkovitz, Shaw and Schneider, 1992). Resuspension of sediments can lead to an enhancement in bioavailability and bioaccumulation from water and sediment (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). This explains the results of our study which shows that Gd is more readily available than La, as lanthanum remains within the sediment. Although most of the REE is partitioned in the sediment and not as much in the water, this potentially stimulates avoidance behavior of the daphnia when sediments are contaminated, as Gd becomes more bioavailable.

The results of the study do not confirm that the avoidance behavior towards REE contaminated sediment occurs both for the vertical and horizontal migration of *D. magna*. Assessing the average scores in the heatmaps and the frequency distribution, it is suggested that both Gd and La indicate more random horizontal migration than attraction or avoidance towards the REE contaminated sediment. The results indicated that the avoidance behavior could only be identified for the vertical experiments. The vertical avoidance behavior for the REE contaminated sediment could be explained by the daphnia potentially are able to sense REE as a form of threat. This was also confirmed by the results of the video recordings where the distance moved and active time indicated that the daphnia became more agitated by both REE compared to the control. However, we know little about the mechanisms by which the daphnids may sense heavy metals like REE.

It has also been suggested that oxidative stress might play a role in behavioral changes, as it is known to be induced by heavy metals and REE in other aquatic species (Bownik, 2017; Figueiredo *et al.*, 2018; Zhao *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2018). Indeed, Ce and Er have been found to decrease oxidative stress in *D. magna* (Galdiero *et al.*, 2019). During 48h of exposure the nanoparticle LaCoO₃ caused significant oxidative stress towards *D. magna* at 5 mg L⁻¹ and 50 mg L⁻¹ with a higher degree of oxidative stress being induced at the higher element concentration (Zhou *et al.*, 2019). The oxidative stress mechanism induced by LaCoO₃ causes within the first 12 hours of exposure oxidation inhibition, followed by antioxidative recovery. So, it is possible that in our experiment, which was maximum of 3h duration, the daphnia reaches

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the oxidation inhibition phase. However, further research into how La and Gd affect behavioral changes in relation to oxidative stress would need to be performed.

Daphnia can sense natural chemical signals e.g., when predators are around. Daphnia use info chemicals, also known as kairomones (Weiss *et al.*, 2018), to indicate the presence of predators or toxic blue-green algae, allowing the daphnids to respond to the potential threat (Ebert, 2022). For the sensing of the info chemicals daphnia use their well-developed gustatory receptors (Peñalva-Arana, Lynch and Robertson, 2009). Environmentally relevant concentrations of Cu and Ni are known to interfere with the chemical communication system between the predatory phantom midge larvae *Chaoborus americanus* and *Daphnia pulex*. It is suggested that the two heavy metals can interfere with the signal pathway of the info chemical receptors (Hunter and Pyle, 2004). The start of the signal transduction of the informative chemicals probably takes place in the antennae of the daphnia (Krieger and Breer, 1999). It is known that the rare earth element Ce can reduce the length of the first segments of the antenna up to 27.8% of *D. magna* (Galdiero *et al.*, 2019). The characteristic hops of daphnia are due to the regular beating with the second set of antennae. Confirming that there is a potential for REE to influence the signaling behavior of daphnia. However, our study was limited to 3 hours, so it is unlikely that the antenna of *D. magna* are affected within that time period. At present, it remains unclear how REE can impair the chemosensory function in daphnia.

It is most likely that the uptake of calcium is interfered with by the REE causing behavioral changes. Changes in the concentration of intracellular dissolved calcium are known to effect survival and reproduction (Muysen, De Schamphelaere and Janssen, 2009). Several chemical and physical properties of trivalent La^{3+} and Gd^{3+} ions resemble Ca^{2+} ions, and REE have been identified as potential competitors for calcium uptake and transport usually binding with higher affinity than Ca^{2+} (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Tan, Yang and Wilkinson, 2017; Sherry, Caravan and Lenkinski, 2009; Martino *et al.*, 2018). REE have also been shown to interfere with Ca metabolism in cells and disturb enzyme activities (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014; Kulaksiz and Bau, 2013; Pałasz and Czekaj, 2000; Trapasso *et al.*, 2021). Both La^{3+} and Gd^{3+} compete for available binding sites with Ca^{2+} , with Gd^{3+} (1.107 Å) having a shorter ion radius having a stronger inhibition than La^{3+} (1.216 Å) (Das, Sharma and Talukder, 1988; Cardon *et al.*, 2019; Nosov *et al.*, 2023). The interaction of the REE with calcium dependent biological systems can result in ecotoxicological effects. It has been shown that most *Daphnia spp.* prefer high calcium localities (Hessen, Alstad and Skardal, 2000). With La sorption to the sediment, it might be that there is more calcium available for the daphnia, leading to them not avoiding the sediment as much in comparison to Gd where there might be more competition with the free Ca^{2+} ions. Causing lower calcium zones, resulting in daphnia avoiding the Gd contaminated sediment. However, the exact mechanisms behind the impact on daphnia

behavior to changing Ca concentrations are still unknown. Calcium uptake has been linked to changes in locomotor activity in various aquatic crustaceans, but this has not been extensively studied for daphnia (Honnappa, Hannah Sulochana and Jayaraman, 1975; Muysen, De Schampelaere and Janssen, 2009). It has been hypothesized that reduced Ca levels lead to smaller daphnia, reducing the swimming ability (Betini *et al.*, 2016). We only looked at adult daphnia under acute exposure, thus morphological changes are less likely. Thus, while there seems strong evidence that calcium plays a role in the change of behavior by daphnia when exposed to REE contaminated sediment, the mechanisms behind it remain unknown.

These experiments on avoidance behavior indicate perceived stress of the organisms resulting in behavioral changes. This is important because the active avoidance of REE-contaminated sediment by organisms could impact the various interactions the organism has with the aquatic ecosystem. The way behavior is measured also impacted the results of the sensitivity noted, as horizontal did not seem to indicate toxicity but the vertical movement did. However, there is currently no standardized test to measure behavior of daphnia with contaminated sediment. Behavior can also be measured in various ways, such as swimming time, swimming speed, behavioral strength, hopping frequency (Bownik, 2017), each resulting in different endpoints that are not always comparable. However, it is important to further extend the research on how REE contaminated sediment can impact behavioral changes within daphnia. It would be of further interest to study if daphnia can sense REE in the sediment through mechanisms linked for example to the competition with Ca^{2+} ions. Potential ways to look into this are applying fluorescence techniques, such as confocal microscopy, or looking at bioindicator activities such as cholinergic neurotransmitter acetylcholine (ACh) and reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Zhang *et al.*, 2023; Atchison, 2003).

As behavioral changes in *D. magna* can have an environmental significance as daphnia are primary consumers and a potential reduction in population numbers, due to for example increased predation, could result in a cascading effect on the freshwater ecosystem in the form of exponential phytoplankton growth (Christensen *et al.*, 2005; Amorim and Moura, 2021; Miner *et al.*, 2012). We have demonstrated that there is potential for behavioral bioassays with pelagic species and sediments for future risk assessment (Lopes, Baird and Ribeiro, 2004), due to behavior being more sensitive than mortality. However, we do also suggest additional studies which include but are not limited to how daphnia react to the introduction of metals, to perform the experiments over a longer period of time, to perform these experiments with various sediments and metals.

7.5. Conclusion

Contaminated REE sediment causes avoidance behaviour for *D. magna*, but the avoidance is related to the type of REE and the concentration. Influencing the predation risk and by extension changing the population dynamics of *D. magna*. With the knowledge that REE contaminated sediment can alter the behaviour of *D. magna*, the question arises if these effects can also be measured in more natural settings with different circumstances over longer time periods and with the interaction with several other aquatic species. Especially with the predicted increase in elevated environmental concentrations due to anthropogenic activities. Increasing the likelihood of exposure of REE towards aquatic organisms, both pelagic and benthic. If organisms actively avoid REE-contaminated sediments, changes in their behaviour may also have further implications for the freshwater ecosystem. Therefore, avoidance assays using contaminated sediment and pelagic species could be a complementary tool in ecological risk assessment. Behavioural measurement methods that require filming equipment and software are not always available or feasible financially. We have provided an alternative and addition for measuring horizontal and vertical migration through the use of digital analysis of video recordings.

Author contribution

Author contribution is in alphabetical order of surname. Chantal van Drimmelen was responsible for developing and conducting the behavioral tests, the TXRF measurements to study the REE bioaccumulation in daphnids and the quantification of the dissolved REE concentrations. The initial draft of the paper was written by Chantal van Drimmelen. It was then reviewed and revised by Susanne Heise and Andrew Hursthouse. All authors agreed on the final version.

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CHAPTER 8

14-DAY NANOCOSM TO INVESTIGATE THE TOXICITY OF LA AND GD ALONG THE FOOD CHAIN MICROALGAE-DAPHNIA

Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen^{1,2}, Andrew S. Hursthouse², Susanne Heise¹

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¹ Life Sciences, Hamburg University of Applied Science, Ulmenliet 20, D-21033 Hamburg, Germany

² University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Abstract

Nanocosms are experimental systems that provide a model to simulate ecosystems, simplified to facilitate research on the effects of contaminants and stressors under controlled conditions, often with a limited number of co-exposed species. The microalgae *Raphidocelis subcapitata* and the water flea *Daphnia magna* are well established in ecotoxicological testing and play an important role in the aquatic ecosystem as primary consumers and producers, respectively. This study investigates the impact of REE in a water-sediment system on the dynamics between the two biological species by a series of 300 mL nanocosm experiments. The water column of the nanocosms was spiked with a range of lanthanum (La) and gadolinium (Gd) concentrations, covering environmentally relevant (1 and 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and anthropogenically relevant nominal concentrations (100 and 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Population development in the nanocosms as well as a number of subchronic endpoints was monitored over a course of 14 days using a sacrificial method. Although, no significant differences were found for most of the endpoints, some trends could still be detected. The onset point of reproduction for the daphnia appeared to increase in most of the La and Gd exposures. It was also observed that doubling time of the daphnia population was longer for Gd than for La at environmental concentrations of 1 and 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The *R. subcapitata-D. magna* population followed the predator-prey relationship for the control, but not for the REE where a more adverse effect was observed. These trends suggest that already at environmentally relevant concentrations, REE could negatively affect the food web with Gd being more toxic than La. This provides further insight to our understanding of the adverse effects caused by the rising anthropogenic concentrations of La and Gd in the aquatic environment.

8.1. Introduction

Many studies of the aquatic ecosystem examine the pelagic and benthic habitats separately (Schindler and Scheuerell, 2002). The various factors that influence the benthic-pelagic coupling are often overlooked and studies focus more on single-species assays. These standardized tests can be too simplistic and nanocosms provide a relatively simple alternative. Nanocosms can be established to research the effects of contaminants and stressors on a limited number of co-exposed species under controlled conditions, and thus simulate natural aquatic ecosystems (Clements and Newman, 2003). While it is impossible in the laboratory to reflect the variability of responses to e.g., contaminant stressors and the extent of interactions in natural systems, “cosm”-experiments can be designed that feature more than one species and run over longer periods compared to single species bioassays.

For emerging contaminants application of “cosm” studies is very limited particularly for the Rare Earth Elements (REE), (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b; Fuma *et al.*, 2001). The REE consist of a group of 17 elements, the 15 lanthanides and the chemically similar elements scandium and yttrium. They are naturally present in the environment, but their wider use in society (e.g., mining, agriculture, and industry) (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018) has led to positive anthropogenic anomalies in aquatic ecosystems (Song *et al.*, 2017; Bau and Dulski, 1996). The rise in anthropogenic concentrations of REE has increased the concern for adverse effects on the environment (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016), especially in sediments where they tend to accumulate (Khan *et al.*, 2017; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b). With nanocosms it can be simulated what happens when REE are introduced into the water phase (e.g., by emission from industry), and then end up in the sediment. This is a much more “natural” system than having only the water phase as seen in standardized tests with pelagic species.

Consequently, this study was designed to investigate the potential effects of REE contaminated sediment on the dynamics between two pelagic species, the microalgae *Raphidocelis subcapitata* and the water flea *Daphnia magna*. They represent organisms at a low trophic level which have been shown to often contain the elevated concentrations of REE (MacMillan *et al.*, 2017). *Daphnia spp.* have key functions in the aquatic food web and are probably among the most studied invertebrates (Ebert, 2005). A number of studies have been carried out on the ecotoxicological effects of REE on daphnia (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Ma *et al.*, 2016; Blinova *et al.*, 2018a; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a). They are grazer feeders and one of their main sources of food are microalgae. Microalgae are also ecologically important organisms as primary producers in aquatic systems. Just like daphnia this has led to a number of studies identifying the sensitivity of algae towards REE (Bergsten-Torralba, 2020; Joonas, 2017; Tai *et al.*, 2010; Ramasamy, Porada and Sillanpää, 2019).

The nanocosm experiments focused on the light REE lanthanum (La) and the heavy REE gadolinium (Gd) both have been reported to show positive anomalies in surface waters worldwide, originating from anthropogenic inputs (Klaver *et al.*, 2014; Rogowska *et al.*, 2018b; Trapasso *et al.*, 2021; Bau and Dulski, 1996). We wanted to see whether previous results acquired in single species short time tests, exposure would still hold when two prey-predator species were exposed over 14 days. Specifically, we wanted to validate the following conclusions derived from single species tests: (1) The crustacea *D. magna* is more affected by REE than its food source, the microalgae *R. subcapitata* (Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016); (2) Reproduction of *D. magna* is the a highly sensitive endpoint, as shown for anthropogenic concentrations by (Ma *et al.*, 2016; Galdiero *et al.*, 2019; Lüring and Tolman, 2010; Revel, van Drimmelen *et al.*, submitted). (3) Gd is more toxic than La (Blinova *et al.*, 2018b; Blinova *et al.*, 2018a; Korkmaz *et al.*, 2021; Revel, van Drimmelen *et al.*, submitted; van Drimmelen, Revel, *et al.*, submitted).

8.2. Materials and Methods

8.2.1. Microalgae and water flea cultures

The freshwater microalgae species *Raphidocelis subcapitata* (SAG Strain Number 61.81) was obtained from the culture collection of algae at the University of Göttingen (SAG). The cultures are maintained at $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, with an 8:16 light cycle and lighting intensity between 6000 lx and 10 000 lx (Osram) in culture medium according to the ISO8692:2012 (ISO, 2012). The water flea species *Daphnia magna* was obtained from the German Environmental Ministry (Umweltbundesamt, Hamburg, Germany). The daphnia were maintained in Elendt M4 medium (OECD, 2012), which was exchanged once per week. The culture was kept at $21 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ degrees with a 16:8 light-dark cycle. The adult daphnia culture was fed daily with the microalgae *R. subcapitata*. Both the *R. subcapitata* and *D. magna* were cultured at the Hamburg University of Applied Sciences (HAW-Hamburg)

8.2.2. Installation of the nanocosms

Nanocosms (Figure 8-1) used in this study consist of PET-cups (Polyethylene terephthalate) of 300 mL ($\varnothing 95$ mm, 76103, Wimex) with 25 grams of LUFA-soil 2.2 (Speyer, Germany, **SI7-3**) ($\text{pH } 5.6 \pm 0.3$) and 200 mL of modified M4-Medium without EDTA ($\text{pH } 6.8 \pm 0.2$) to prevent interference with REE in the test medium. LUFA standard soil 2.2 is a natural and well-defined soil used in many soil and sediment tests (Domene *et al.*, 2011; Römbke *et al.*, 2006; Höss *et al.*, 2009). PET-cups were used because REE are less likely to adhere to the plastic wall of the cups (Reimann, Birke and Filzmoser, 2010). Nanocosms were maintained in a controlled environment at 20°C , humidity $>50\%$, 16:8 light:dark cycle. After setting up the cups with the sediment and media, they were left alone for an hour to equilibrate the “cosms”. At 3 days

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before the start of the experiment 16.0×10^6 cells mL^{-1} *R. subcapitata* were added to each cup, in order to establish a population. The microalgae in the cups must have reached ± 145900 cell mL^{-1} in order for the experiment to be continued. One hour before the addition of daphnia, nanocosms were spiked with environmentally relevant (1 and 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and anthropogenically relevant nominal concentrations (100 and 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) of Gd and La ($\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{LaCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99% purity; Sigma Aldrich), in the water column respectively. After one hour each nanocosm received one adult *D. magna*. The nanocosms were analyzed over a course of 14 days using a sacrificial method, i.e. one cup per treatment was removed each day for analysis so that on the last day of the experiment only one cup was left per treatment. Abiotic factors of pH (7.00 ± 1.5), temperature ($20.0 \pm 1.0^\circ\text{C}$), and dissolved O_2 ($8.00 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \pm 1.00$) were measured daily to determine if the values stayed within their limits. The experiment was repeated at five times.

Figure 8-1 A 300 mL PET cup as nanocosm with the water flea *D. magna* and the microalgae *R. subcapitata*.

8.2.3. Measurements

The growth of *R. subcapitata* was determined daily by measuring chlorophyll levels in a 2 mL water sample from each sacrificed nanocosm via fluorescence measurements with a TECAN GENios plate reader (Tecan, Männedorf, Switzerland) (emission = 680 (35) nm; excitation = 465 (30) nm, integration time: 40

μ s) in 24-well microplates (Costar 2524, Corning Incorporated). Endpoints comprised parameters such as death rate, reproduction rate (first offspring date, total amount of offspring), and population count (doubling time and total amount of daphnia) for *D. magna*, and the growth rate for *R. subcapitata* according to the guidelines of the single-species test (ISO, 2012).

8.2.4. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism version 10.0.2 for Windows. Reproduction and the onset point of first offspring for *D. magna* (N = 16) was tested through the Multiple Mann Whitney test. For the doubling time of daphnia (N = 70), a nonlinear regression was performed, with a constraint for the Y0 constant being equal to 1. With this constraint the parameter is constant at time point zero. The number of *D. magna* was visualized in heatmaps with an overlay of the *R. subcapitata* fluorescence in red lining. Non-linear regression of the microalgae data between day 7 and day 14 suggests that all data of the control, La and Gd (for all concentrations) can be represented by one single graph. Shapiro Wilk was applied to analyze both the algae growth and total amount of daphnids for normal distribution and further analyzed through a Two-way ANOVA ($p < 0.0001$, N = 210) with a Tukey's for multiple comparison. The p-value was always 0.05 as reference.

8.3. Results

8.3.1. Dynamics of daphnia over the course of 14-days

No significant difference for any endpoint in the exposure of *D. magna* to La ($p = 0.857$) or Gd ($p = 0.629$) was found. However, trends could be observed. The onset point is defined as the first day offspring was observed. For La (Figure 8-2a) a trend of slight stimulation can be observed for the onset point for 1, 10, and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ compared to the control. At La concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ the onset point is delayed compared to the control. This slight trend in stimulation at the lower concentrations for La was not observed for Gd (Figure 8-2b). At 1 and 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ there is slight stimulation occurring for Gd, while there is a delay observed for Gd 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

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Figure 8-2 Onset of reproduction in days for *D. magna* in days after the start of the experiment for a) lanthanum and b) gadolinium.

At the end of the experiment the total average daphnia in the control was 69 and 40 in La, and 30 in Gd (Figure 8-3). In the heatmaps it becomes easier to visualise that the daphnia reproduce more in La compared to Gd. The heatmap indicates the number of daphnia with the darker colors (indigo-blue, 10-30 daphnia) being fewer daphnia and slowly changing to lighter colors (green-yellow, 40-50 daphnia) as the amount of *D. magna* increase. For La the lighter colors (yellow and green, 40-50 daphnia) indicate that the daphnia are less impacted by the lower concentrations of 1 and 10 µg L⁻¹, but not the higher concentration of 100 and 1000 µg L⁻¹ (blue hues, <30 daphnia) in comparison to the control (bright yellow >50 daphnia). Compared to Gd where the colors of the heatmap are all within the blue zone (<30 daphnia) at all exposure concentrations. This trend also becomes clear when comparing the doubling time of the growth rate for *D. magna* in days (Table 8-1) for La with that of Gd. The trend that can be identified is that it takes longer for the daphnia population to double over time in days exposed to Gd compared to La under environmentally relevant concentrations (1 and 10 µg L⁻¹).

Figure 8-3 Heatmap of number of *D. magna* at concentrations 1, 10, 100, and 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for lanthanum (left) and gadolinium (right).

Table 8-1 Doubling time of the growth rate in days and the average number of total *D. magna* at the end of the experiment for lanthanum and gadolinium in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Doubling time in mean, (min-max). Significant differences between the control and the different exposures are indicated by <0.05 and NS = not significant.

	Control		1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$		10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$		100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$		1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
	Doubling time	Total average amount								
La	2.41 (2.26 – 2.66) ^{NS}	69	2.47 (2.38 – 2.60) ^{NS}	54	2.54 (2.41 – 2.72) ^{NS}	43	2.76 (2.55 – 3.12) ^{NS}	27	2.67 (2.54 – 2.87) ^{NS}	35
	2.41 (2.26 – 2.66) ^{NS}	69	2.87 (2.66 – 3.20) ^{NS}	32	2.79 (2.64 – 2.99) ^{NS}	25	2.73 (2.57 – 2.97) ^{NS}	31	2.66 (2.46 – 3.00) ^{NS}	30
Gd	2.41 (2.26 – 2.66) ^{NS}	69	2.87 (2.66 – 3.20) ^{NS}	32	2.79 (2.64 – 2.99) ^{NS}	25	2.73 (2.57 – 2.97) ^{NS}	31	2.66 (2.46 – 3.00) ^{NS}	30
	2.41 (2.26 – 2.66) ^{NS}	69	2.87 (2.66 – 3.20) ^{NS}	32	2.79 (2.64 – 2.99) ^{NS}	25	2.73 (2.57 – 2.97) ^{NS}	31	2.66 (2.46 – 3.00) ^{NS}	30

8.3.2. Microalgae development over the course of 14-days

The *R. subcapitata* cell count per mL^{-1} for both La (Figure 8-4) and Gd (Figure 8-5), and the control, the pattern stayed stable over the 14-day exposure time. The control show increases and decreases at certain points in a repeating pattern. When looking at the time points of days 6 and 7 for both La and Gd at 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ it seems that the algae increased around day 6 and go down around day 7. However, this pattern is clearer at the lower concentrations for both La and Gd and *R. subcapitata* was not significantly affected by the two REE in comparison with the control, or in comparison with each other.

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Figure 8-4 Microalgae *R. subcapitata* in cells mL⁻¹ over the course of 14-days at concentrations 1, 10, 100, and 1000 µg L⁻¹ for La.

Figure 8-5 Microalgae *R. subcapitata* in cells mL⁻¹ over the course of 14-days at concentrations 1, 10, 100, and 1000 µg L⁻¹ for Gd.

8.3.3. Development of *R. subcapitata* compared to *D. magna*

Neither La nor Gd led to any die-off at any nominal concentrations for either biological species and, thus, are not considered to be acutely toxic (Figure 8-6). The heatmap indicates the number of daphnia with the darker colors (indigo-blue, 10-30 daphnia) being fewer daphnia and slowly changing to lighter colors (green-yellow, 40-50 daphnia) as the amount of *D. magna* increase. This heatmap is overlaid by a line graph for the amount of the microalgae *R. subcapitata* in cell mL⁻¹. The microalgae in the control seems

to indicate there is a predator-prey relationship, where as the abundance of prey increases, the predator abundance also increases and vice versa, showing the nanocosms have stabilised. This becomes clearer when looking at the time points of days 6 for all treatments (Figure 8-6). It seems that the algae decrease around day 6 is in line with when there is an increase of daphnia, and thus most likely not caused by REE. Although the results indicate that a trend occurs to the population dynamics of *D. magna* and *R. subcapitata* when exposed to either La and Gd (Table 8-2), generally decreasing, neither species was found to be significantly affected by the two REE in comparison with the control, or in comparison with each other.

Figure 8-6 Heatmap of number of *D. magna* with *R. subcapitata* in cell mL⁻¹ overlay for control, gadolinium, and lanthanum. Microalgae data is combined in one curve for the control and both REE, deviation is shown as SEM.

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Table 8-2 Compilation of the trends observed for *D. magna* and *R. subcapitata* over the duration of the 14-day experimental period.

	Daphnids			Microalgae
	Onset point	Doubling time	Total amount	Cell mL ⁻¹
La 1 µg L ⁻¹	Increase	Stays the same	Decrease	Decrease (after day 6)
La 10 µg L ⁻¹	Increase	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease (after day 6)
La 100 µg L ⁻¹	Increase	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease (after day 6)
La 1000 µg L ⁻¹	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease (after day 6)
Gd 1 µg L ⁻¹	Increase	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease (after day 6)
Gd 10 µg L ⁻¹	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease (after day 6)
Gd 100 µg L ⁻¹	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease (after day 6)
Gd 1000 µg L ⁻¹	Increase	Decrease	Decrease	Decrease (after day 6)

8.4. Discussion

No significant differences were observed between La, Gd, or the control for either *R. subcapitata* or *D. magna*. Which means that the hypothesis that the primary consumer, in this case *D. magna*, is more affected by La or Gd in comparison to the primary producer, *R. subcapitata*, can be rejected. This is not in agreement with studies where either daphnia (Bergsten-Torralba *et al.*, 2020) or microalgae (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022b) were found to be more sensitive towards REE than the other species. When looking at the compiled trend between *D. magna* and *R. subcapitata*, it suggests that the microalgae are less sensitive towards both La and Gd as the decrease observed after day 6 is probably due to daphnia predation. The sudden increase of the microalgae on day 6 is probably related to nutrients being released by the daphnia and less predation occurring, before an equilibrium with the daphnia is established in the form of a traditional predator-prey relationship. Although this could not be confirmed.

The fact that no significant difference was observed in the nanocosms is probably due to all of the REE being absorbed by the sediment due to their high affinity for organic matter (Khan *et al.*, 2017), which would explain why the results between La and Gd, and the different concentrations are similar. This study directly spiked the water column with REE, to simulate direct discharge of REE contaminated effluents getting into the river. The distribution of REE between, the sediment and the water is affected by environmental factors, such as pH, phosphate, and ammonium, constantly change the equilibrium among sediment and the water surface (Khan *et al.*, 2017; Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a; Santos *et al.*, 2023). This can also play a role in the expression of toxicity in aquatic organisms. For example, phosphate has been found to mask the toxicity of REE in the standardized growth media for algae growth inhibition bioassays (van Drimmelen, Revel, et al., submitted). However, the determination of the bioavailability of REE and other

toxicants can be limited in studies, such as ours, due to sample availability and the complexity and cost of carrying out more detailed analysis.

Another factor that should be considered when working with nanocosms is that variability can also impact on the significance of results. The variability in “cosm” experiments is well known and various reasons are identified (Fettweis, De Schampelaere and Smolders, 2018; Bell and Coull, 1978). These include differences in organism morphology, physiology and behavior can increase variability in the nanocosms (McGeer *et al.*, 2004). Variability has also been found to be related to the trophic relationship between the microalgae and daphnia, as main food source and main primary consumer (Triffault-Bouchet, Clément and Blake, 2005). This increase in variability creates a great challenge for identifying the potential negative effects of REE in “more” natural settings, like the nanocosms. However, it also shows that sediment is an effective sink for REE under natural conditions. So, the current work could act as a foundation for the further development of studies looking into how sediment disturbance (e.g., change in pH, temperature, and oxygen) influences the bioavailability and with that the toxicity of REE on the algae-daphnia relationship. So, the variability among the nanocosms should not exclude the use of “cosm” studies for the evaluation of the ecotoxicity of REE or other contaminants. The results presented here provides further insights into potential adverse effects caused by La and Gd, and other studies have demonstrated that results can be applied in environmental risk assessment (Fuma *et al.*, 2001).

While no significant differences were found for most of the endpoints for either species between either element or the control, trends were detected. The development of the microalgae in the nanocosms impacted by the REE is not detectable but observations after day 6 and seems related to feeding by the daphnia. The *R. subcapitata*-*D. magna* population followed a prey-predator pattern (Wangersky, 1978) for the control, but this was not observed for either La or Gd. Changes in feeding behavior of daphnia can be an indicator of toxic stress caused by REE, and can predict reductions in reproduction (Juchelka and Snell, 1995). In general, grazing inhibition leads to a stimulation of algal growth (Clément and Zaid, 2004). However, daphnia are also not only exposed to the REE through the media and sediment, but also through their food source the microalgae. Which leads to the new hypothesis that for La and Gd decreased daphnid reproduction might increase food uptake by *D. magna* to compensate for stress.

Daphnia are also more likely to graze algae from the water column rather than on the sediment (Lamonica *et al.*, 2016), and they may only graze from the sediment when the amount of microalgae is too low in the water column (Siehoff *et al.*, 2009). *R. subcapitata* that was settled on the sediment in the nanocosms at the end of the experimental period are not considered here. However, in the present study it was observed that daphnia appeared to avoid the sediment in the REE contaminated nanocosms, but not in the control. Which could potentially impact the predator-prey interaction between the daphnia and

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the microalgae. However, further studies are needed to be performed to confirm if daphnia indeed avoid REE-contaminated sediment.

Food for *D. magna*, in this case *R. subcapitata*, plays an important role in the way toxicants can affect the reproduction of daphnia (De Schampelaere *et al.*, 2004; Hook and Fisher, 2001). Other studies were the most adverse effects in daphnia for La and Gd found to be through dietary and a combined media and dietary exposure. The accumulation of Gd through dietary exposure happens in the intestinal tract of the daphnia, correlating with affected reproduction (Revel, van Drimmelen, *et al.*, submitted). That the daphnia start feeding on the microalgae after day 6 might be also related to reproduction. Food supply has been linked to reproduction rate as neonate production increases with increasing food ratio (Smolders, Baillieul and Blust, 2005). The daphnia start feeding more on the microalgae before the lay of a clutch. This explains why it is observed that the *R. subcapitata* population goes down on day 6 but the number of *D. magna* start to increase two days after on day 8. Reproduction of *D. magna* is known to favor offspring quality over quantity when being exposed to toxicants (Fettweis, De Schampelaere and Smolders, 2018; Knops, Altenburger and Segner, 2001). Which explains the that while reproduction was also not impacted significantly by either La or Gd in the nanocosms; another trend was detected for reproduction as an endpoint for *D. magna* towards both REE. Thus, the hypothesis that the most sensitive endpoint with *D. magna* at environmental relevant concentrations is the reproduction is not rejected.

The trend that was observed for the doubling time of reproduction for *D. magna* was that it takes longer for the daphnia population to double over time for Gd than La at environmental concentrations of 1 and 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. In the nanocosms there was also a clear visual difference for the onset of reproduction of daphnia between the control, La, and Gd. The onset point for the daphnia was delayed sooner by Gd at 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ compared to La at 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. This agrees with (Revel, van Drimmelen, *et al.*, submitted) where a La concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ delayed the release of the first brood. However, for the Gd exposure at 500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ the overall number of offspring was reduced, but no significant delay was observed (Revel, van Drimmelen, *et al.*, submitted). That the trend of the delay is observed in the nanocosms at lower concentrations but not at higher concentrations of Gd could be due to that *D. magna* exposed in “cosm” studies has been found to be more sensitive to toxicants than in single-species bioassays exposed through only media (Triffault-Bouchet, Clément and Blake, 2005). A slight stimulation for the onset point was detected for both REE in comparison to the control. An explanation is that some detoxification processes are activated. Detoxification is known to occur when *D. magna* is chronically exposed to the REE cerium and erbium (Galdiero *et al.*, 2019).

Several studies have confirmed that Gd is more toxic than La for both *R. subcapitata* and *D. magna* (Blinova *et al.*, 2018b; Blinova *et al.*, 2018a; Korkmaz *et al.*, 2021; Revel, van Drimmelen, *et al.*, submitted;

van Drimmelen, Revel, et al., submitted). For example, the maximum inhibition for different species of microalgae has been found to be 100% for Gd compared to 50% for La (van Drimmelen, Revel, et al., submitted). While for daphnia the acute toxicity EC_{50} values after 48h at nominal concentrations were determined at Gd 18.5 mg L^{-1} and La 31.1 mg L^{-1} (Blinova *et al.*, 2018a). La, which has been classified as a light REE (LREE), and Gd, classified as a heavy REE (HREE), have different preferences to form complexes with various ligands (Wood, 1990; Moermond *et al.*, 2001; Smrzka *et al.*, 2019). Concentrations of LREEs in sediment is significantly higher compared to HREEs (Brito *et al.*, 2018; Jiang *et al.*, 2022); making it more likely for the microalgae and daphnia in the nanocosms to be exposed to bioavailable Gd, and thus influencing the bioaccumulation and toxicity of the REE (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022a). Considering all these points the hypothesis of Gd being also more toxic than La in a simulated environment should not be rejected.

8.5. Conclusion

A modest trend in response can be identified from this study for both *D. magna* and *R. subcapitata* that could indicate that with the rise in anthropogenic concentrations of REE there could be a cascading effect along the food chain of algae-daphnia, which could have further ecosystem complications. Especially because the present study did not take into consideration variables related to seasonal changes, such as temperature, which are known to impact REE toxicity. The increase in anthropogenic REE concentrations could strengthen the trends seen in the present study, as many uncertainties remain about the adverse effects of REE due to their complexity within aquatic environments. Nanocosm tests should be considered as a complementation to single species test, as they offer the possibility to test emerging contaminants, such as REE, under more realistic natural conditions. They allow us to not only see the direct ecotoxicological effects but also the indirect effects and provide a helpful hand in making predictions of real risks for aquatic ecosystems. However, factors like chemical speciation, variability, and trends should be taking into account when performing “cosm” studies with rare earth elements.

Author contribution

Author contribution is in alphabetical order of surname. Chantal van Drimmelen was responsible for developing and conducting the nanocosm studies, as well as data analysis. The first draft of the paper was written by Chantal van Drimmelen. It was then reviewed and revised by Susanne Heise and Andrew Hursthouse. All authors agreed on the final version.

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CHAPTER 9

MICROCOSMS AS A TOOL TO STUDY REE TOXICITY IN A SIMULATED AQUATIC FOOD WEB

Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen^{1,2}, Andrew S. Hursthouse², Susanne Heise¹

Keywords: Lanthanides, pelagic invertebrates, benthic invertebrates, sediment, benthic-pelagic coupling

¹ Life Sciences, Hamburg University of Applied Science, Ulmenliet 20, D-21033 Hamburg, Germany

² University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Abstract

Benthic-pelagic coupling refers to the exchange of processes between the benthic and pelagic phases of aquatic ecosystems. Sediments in aquatic ecosystems hold 99% of anthropogenically discharged rare earth elements (REE), which pose a concern due to their potential adverse effects on aquatic food webs. Of the REE gadolinium (Gd) is one of the most widespread in freshwaters due to its use as a contrasting agent in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Indoor microcosms are an alternative to standardized bioassays, as they provide an artificial and simplified ecosystem which is closer to the structure of the natural environment. The objective of this study was to investigate the impact of sediment resuspension on the transfer of the rare earth element gadolinium (Gd) from benthic layer to the pelagic layer at the first consumer level. The microcosm experiment was not completely successful, at day 9 two types of biological contamination were observed. The first organisms were identified as to the diatom *Nitzschia spp.* The second species was identified as the freshwater microalga *Chlamydomonas spp.* It is probably *Nitzschia* that causes a shift in the equilibrium of the microcosms. These species were likely introduced through the natural soils used to establish the bacteria population. In this instance, the daphnia population reacted as an early responder to the ecosystem shift. However, it was still demonstrated that the aquatic food web can be negatively impacted by Gd 0.5 mg L⁻¹. While daphnia and ostracod population were less affected, the *L. variegatus* population was more susceptible to the REE contaminated sediment. Demonstrating that not all species were impacted equally by the biological or the Gd contamination. Benthic organisms (*L. variegatus*) are more likely to be impacted by REE contamination in aquatic environments than pelagic species (*H. incongruens*). Several factors are considered to prevent biological contamination in the microcosms. Microcosms provide an interesting tool that can assist in determining the potential impact of REE contaminated sediment in freshwater ecosystems.

9.1. Introduction

The exchange of various processes (e.g., energy, organic matter, organisms, and dissolved substances) via physical, chemical, biological, and human disturbances between the benthic (sediment phase) and the pelagic (water phase) is known as benthic-pelagic coupling (Testa *et al.*, 2020; Marinelli and Williams, 2003). In aquatic ecosystems, do sediments as a reservoir for various contaminants (Yang *et al.*, 1999; Khan *et al.*, 2017; MacMillan *et al.*, 2017; Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2018; Balaram, 2019).

In aquatic ecosystems, 99% of rare earth elements (REE) are bound to either the sediment or suspended matter. (Weltje *et al.*, 2002b). As emerging contaminants REE pose a concern due to prospective adverse ecotoxicological effects on aquatic food webs. The 15 lanthanides, lanthanum (La) to lutetium (Lu) (atomic ion 57-71), are included in the REE group, along with the elements scandium (Sc, 21) and yttrium (Y, 39). Rare earth elements (REE) have a strong adsorption to sediment particles and organic matter (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018; Schaller, 2013; Tijink and Yland, 1998; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). Causing benthic species to be more likely to be exposed to REE in contaminated sediment. The REE are generally not considered to be bioavailable to pelagic species when bound to the sediment. However, ingestion of sediment particles by organisms, disruption of chemical equilibria, or environmental changes through benthic coupling can cause REE to become bioavailable in the water phase (Yang *et al.*, 1999; Mori, 1999; Weltje *et al.*, 2002b; Andrade *et al.*, 2020).

Gadolinium is the most widespread REE in modern society and is applied as a contrasting agent in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). It can be transferred in the urine of humans and pass through wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) increasing anthropogenic concentrations in rivers and other freshwater bodies (Rogowska *et al.*, 2018b; Telgmann *et al.*, 2011). The first positive anomalies caused by anthropogenic activities of Gd in European rivers was recorded in 1996 (Bau and Dulski, 1996). Since then the median concentrations in stream sediments in Europe has been estimated to range between 0.2 - 90.5 mg kg⁻¹ (Salminen *et al.*, 2005). The anticipated increase in REE demand will probably lead to even greater positive anomalies, which will have more adverse consequences for aquatic ecosystems. Gadolinium occurring in aquatic ecosystems all over the world can have an impact on living organisms, however the ecotoxicological data on Gd remains lacking (Blinova *et al.*, 2020; Rogowska *et al.*, 2018b).

Standard ecotoxicological bioassays are too simplistic to represent of environmental conditions (Pontasch, Niederlehner and Cairns, 1989; Haegerbaeumer *et al.*, 2016). Indoor microcosms are artificial and simplified ecosystems that under controlled conditions aid in the research of the effects of contaminants and benthic-pelagic coupling in the natural systems (Clements and Newman, 2003). This makes microcosms attractive experimental systems to investigate the impact of sediment resuspension on the transfer of gadolinium (Gd) from benthic layer to the pelagic layer at the first consumer level. The

hypothesis being that benthic organisms higher will be more impacted by a REE-supply to the aquatic environment than pelagic species or primary consumers.

9.2. Materials and Methods

9.2.1. Organism cultures

9.2.1.1. Freshwater microalgae

The chosen species for this experiment is *Raphidocelis subcapitata* (SAG Strain Number: 61.81) was obtained from the Culture Collection of Algae at the University of Göttingen (SAG). The freshwater microalgae species was cultured at the Hamburg University of Applied Sciences (HAW-Hamburg). The strain cultures are maintained at $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and with a lighting intensity between 6000 lx and 10 000 lx (Osram) and a light cycle of 8:16 in culture medium according to the ISO8692:2012 (ISO, 2012). This species was chosen because it is recommended by the ISO 8692:2012 (ISO, 2012) as a species for the standardized microalgae test. *R. subcapitata* has also been well studied to determine REE toxicity (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; González *et al.*, 2015; Siciliano *et al.*, 2021a; Siciliano *et al.*, 2021b).

9.2.1.2. Water fleas

The water flea *Daphnia magna* was acquired from the German Environmental Ministry (Umweltbundesamt, Hamburg, Germany) and cultured at the HAW-Hamburg. The water fleas are maintained in Elendt M4 medium at a temperature of $21 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with a 16:8 light-dark cycle and fed daily with the freshwater algae *Chlorella vulgaris* (Collection of Algae at the University of Göttingen (SAG 211-11b)). *D. magna* was chosen because it is widely distribution in freshwater ecosystem and has been recommended as a test species in both acute and chronic test guidelines (OECD, 2012; OECD, 2004). It is also one of the most studied species for REE (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; González *et al.*, 2015; Blinova *et al.*, 2021).

9.2.1.3. Oligochaeta worms

The oligochaeta worm *Lumbriculus variegatus* was obtained from the Goethe University Frankfurt (Department Aquatic Ecotoxicology). *L. variegatus* is cultured at the HAW Hamburg in 60 L glass aquaria containing 40 L of deionized-water and 18 g of Tropical Marin® salt (Dr. Biener GmbH, Wartenberg, Germany) at $20^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, pH 7.0 ± 0.5 , with a 16:8 h light:dark cycle, and continuous oxygen flow. The bottom of the aquarium is layered with artificial sediment consisted of 75% fine quartz sand (type F36, average grain size 0.17 mm; Quarzwerke GmbH, Frechen, Germany). The worms are fed three times a week with Tetramin® (TetraWerke, Melle, Germany) and 70% of the water is exchanged twice per week. *L. variegatus* was chosen because it is a model bioturbator of sediments, has a wide distribution in freshwater

ecosystems, and has been well studied with contaminated sediments (Blankson and Klerks, 2016). As far as the authors know, have no other studies attempted to determine the ecotoxicological effects of REE on this species. Thus, using *L. variegatus* in the microcosms could provide additional information of the role of REE contaminated sediment in the aquatic food web.

9.2.1.4. Seed shrimp

The seed shrimp (ostracod) *Heterocypris incongruens* were purchased as dormant eggs (cysts) from Ostracodtoxkit F™ (MicroBioTests Inc., Gent, Belgium). The cysts were hatched in standard freshwater (moderately hard water) according to the manual instructions. They were incubated at 25 ± 1°C under light intensity between 6000 lx and 10 000 lx (Osram) for 52h. The Ostracodtoxkit F™ is widely used in sediment quality assessments within ecotoxicology (Casado-Martinez *et al.*, 2016), and has been widely studied especially in regards to species-environment relationships (Mesquita-Joanes, Smith and Viehberg, 2012). *H. incongruens* has also been applied to study the ecotoxicological effects of REE before (Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2018; González *et al.*, 2015), making it suitable for current experiment.

9.2.1.5. Bacteria

After some pilot studies with *Escherichia coli* and *Arthrobacter globiformis* the choice was made to use natural bacteria cultures from the uncontaminated lake Außenmühlenteich (53°26'28.2"N 9°58'41.8"E, Hamburg, Germany). The bacteria were added by mixing 0.5 g of the lake sediment into 195.5 g of uncontaminated sediment (**9.2.2. Installation of the microcosms**).

9.2.2. Installation of the microcosms

Glass microcosms of 2 L (Figure 9-1, Landgraf Laborsysteme HLL GmbH, Langenhagen, Germany) were set-up with 200 g of uncontaminated sediment LUFA-Speyer 2.2 (Speyer, Germany, **SI7-3**) (pH 5.6 ± 0.3) mixed with natural lake sediment and 2.5 L of M4 medium without EDTA (pH 6.8 ± 0.2)(OECD, 2012). In many soil and sediment tests, the naturally occurring and well-defined LUFA 2.2 matrix is applied to ecotoxicological testing (Domene *et al.*, 2011; Höss, Jänsch, Moser, Junker, & Römbke, 2009; Römbke *et al.*, 2006). The microcosm will be set-up in four gradual steps, in order for the ecosystem to develop and stabilize with each addition: 1) The microalgae (*R. subcapitata*) and natural bacteria culture were added to a layer of uncontaminated sediment and M4 medium without EDTA. Continuous measurements (24/7) with the datalogger D230 system (Consort BVBA, Turnhout, Belgium) were done every 10 minutes for the abiotic factors pH, temperature, O₂, redox, and ammonia.; 2) After a week were 5 oligochaeta worms (*L.*

variegatus) and 5 adult daphnia (10 days old *D. magna*) added to the established microalgae and bacteria population.; 3) The 5 ostracods (*H. incongruens*) were introduced, and the uncontaminated microcosms were spiked with an anthropogenic concentration of 0.5 mg L⁻¹ of Gd (GdCl₃·6H₂O, 99% purity; Sigma Aldrich) in the water column.; and 4) Finally the sediment was resuspended for one hour every day over the total experimental duration of 14 days.

9.2.3. Measurements

Every day was 2 mL of media collected to analyze the chlorophyll levels of the microalgae for each individual microcosm via fluorescence measurements (emission = 680 (35) nm; excitation = 465 (30) nm, integration time: 40 μs) with a TECAN GENios plate reader (Tecan, Männedorf, Switzerland). From this sample was also 1 mL taken for acidification with 2 μL HNO₃ (65%, Roth, 4989.1) which was stored in a -18°C freezer to be subsequently measured by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). The remaining part of the water sample was used to analyze and take pictures of the microalgae underneath the microscope.

A daily sediment sample of 1 g was also taken for later analysis of the bacteria population and chemical analysis. For the chemical analysis 0.5 g was acidified with 1 μL HNO₃, which was then stored in a -18°C freezer to be digested and later measured by ICP-MS. The remaining 1.5 g of sediment was then mixed with 1 mL of clean M4 medium without EDTA and 100 μL of formaldehyde (37%, 7398.1, Carl-Roth) was added. These samples were stored in the refrigerator at 4°C so that they could be analysed under an electron light microscope.

For *D. magna*, *L. variegatus*, and *H. incongruens* the population count, reproduction, and potential morphological changes were measured after 14 days. This was done in order not to disturb the established ecosystem too much. However, daily pictures of the microcosms were taken and to make observations about the condition of the organisms.

Figure 9-1 2L Microcosm containing microalgae (*R. subcapitata*), bacteria (natural culture), water fleas (*D. magna*), ostracods (*H. incongruens*), and oligochaeta worms (*L. variegatus*).

9.3. Results and discussion

At the beginning of the microcosm experiments the daphnids showed an exponential growth, and the microalgae population seemed to be established strongly enough to sustain the daphnia population and not decrease. As the abiotic factors appeared to be stable, it could be concluded that a stable ecosystem had been established. The microcosm experiment was halted at day 11 instead of day 14. At day 9 for Gd2 two types of biological contamination were observed in the microalgae samples underneath the microscope (Figure 9-2 and Figure 9-3). This had not been observed in pilot runs, and it is likely that the natural soils used to establish the bacteria population had introduced these organisms. Photographs were taken and video recordings made of the unknown organisms and used for identification.

The first organisms were identified as to be within the genus *Nitzschia spp.* (Figure 9-2), however, the exact species is unknown. *Nitzschia* are diatoms, with siliceous cell walls, which can be found in both freshwater and marine environments. In order to identify species level of *Nitzschia* is a detailed examination of the diatom frustule structure needed, through scanning and transmission electron microscopes (SEM and TEM)(Tan *et al.*, 2016), but was unavailable. Strains of *Nitzschia* (\pm 423 species validated) can be toxic, due to the formation of domoic acid (DA) (Tan *et al.*, 2016). *Nitzschia frustulum* is

a species that is tolerant to heavy metals, and has linked to take over shifting the community composition of the ecosystem (Moore, 1981). Heavy metal contamination is also known to lead to nutrient competition by *Nitzschia closterium* (Perrein-Ettajani *et al.*, 1999; Falasco *et al.*, 2009). So, it is possible that this biological contaminant led to a shift in the microcosms, disturbing the ecosystem equilibrium.

The second organism identified is most likely *Chlamydomonas* spp. (Figure 9-3), a unicellular freshwater microalga. *Chlamydomonas* has been linked to increase when the primary producers in freshwater ecosystems decreased due to exposure to the herbicide linuron (Van den Brink *et al.*, 1997). However, REE have been found to have an antagonistic effect on the RNA of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. Although, RNA sequencing alone is not enough to provide information about the overall fitness of the microalgae (Morel *et al.*, 2021). The sensitivity of *Chlamydomonas* has been linked to reduced pH as it affects the protective cell walls of the algae (Macfie, Tarmohamed and Welbourn, 1994). Although, the pH (6.5 ± 1.0) in all microcosms was stable over the duration of the 11 days. For REE the bio uptake by *Chlamydomonas* is also linked to the presence of small hydrophilic organic compounds (Yang and Wilkinson, 2018).

Figure 9-2 First biological contaminant noticed in the microcosms in the microscope water samples. This is suspected to be the diatom *Nitzschia* spp.

Figure 9-3 Second biological contaminant noticed in the microcosms in the microscope water samples. This is suspected to be the *Chlamydomonas* spp.

The control and Gd 3 had both quite low microalgae cell count, while the microalgae in Gd 1 and Gd 2 were very high in comparison (Figure 9-4). However, this might be due to the TECAN plate reader not being able to distinguish between *R. subcapitata* and the algal contamination. Considering this and the knowledge of *Nitzschia* it is more likely that the first organism (Figure 9-2) was the cause for the destruction of the ecosystem equilibrium in the microcosms. It must also be noted that neither of the biological contamination species showed to be largely affected by REE.

The result show that on day 10 the daphnia population in Gd 2 appeared to be absent, which was also noticed the next day for Gd 1. When investigating the microalgae samples the same kind of biological contamination discussed above was noticed in Gd 1, although in lower amounts compared to Gd 2. It is suspected that this might have been caused by cross-contamination due to the tools that were used to collect sediment samples in the microcosms. Notable, is that the oxygen in both Gd 1 and Gd 2 stayed stable around $7.0 \pm 1.0 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. At day 11 no daphnia were seen in both microcosms Gd 1 and Gd 2 (Figure 9-5). The control also started to show significant decrease in the number of daphnia ($t_{11} = 16$), especially compared to Gd 3 ($t_{11} = 297$). When checking the control, the same kind of biological contamination was

found as in Gd 1 and Gd 2. It was thus, decided to completely terminate the microcosm run. The daphnia population are in this case an early responder to the biological contamination in the microcosms. The sensitivity of daphnia to various substances is one of the reasons of why they are applied as a model organisms in ecotoxicological tests (Bownik, 2017). This makes daphnia also of special interest for environmental risk assessment (Juan-García *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 9-4 *R. subcapitata* in cells mL⁻¹ in the microcosms 5 days before the start of the experiment (in grey) and during the experiment.

It appears that the biological contamination might have affected the *L. variegatus* population. Showing that not all organisms are not impacted equally by the biological contamination. At day 11 zero oligochaeta worms were found in Gd 1 and Gd 2, only two were found in Gd 3, and the control had 8. However, the fact that Gd 3 only had 2 worms (no biological contamination noticed) and the control 8 might indicated that it is the Gd in the sediment that might have affected the *L. variegatus*. One previous study in Herrmann *et al.* (2016) identified that in a 96h bioassay the LC₅₀ of La was estimated to be 18.8 mg L⁻¹ and it has been suggested that Gd is more toxic than La for aquatic invertebrates (Blinova *et al.*, 2018b; Sneller *et al.*, 2000; Chen *et al.*, 2020).

The ostracods (*H. incongruens*) showed the least variation between the microcosms (Figure 9-5). They did not seem to be impacted as much by either the REE or the biological contamination. Although, there is no data available on how much the ostracod population developed over time. REE do not appear to be very toxic for ostracods, as only some toxic effects could be linked for REE contaminated sediments (Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2018). The REE did not cause mortality to *H. incongruens* at concentrations below

6.4 mg L⁻¹ and thus appear to be less toxic than more commonly tested heavy metals (González *et al.*, 2015). So, if there was an effect on the ostracod population it was likely to be caused by the biological contamination and not Gd. Further analysis of water and sediment samples was not completed.

Figure 9-5 Number of *Daphnia magna*, ostracod *Heterocypris incongruens*, and oligochaeta worms *Lumbriculus variegatus* during the termination of the microcosms (day 11).

9.4. Conclusion and Outlook

Although, this microcosm experiment was not completed, there is an indication that Gd 0.5 mg L⁻¹ can have adverse effects on the ecosystem. The results of the *L. variegatus* population show that these worms are sensitive towards Gd contaminated sediment. The daphnia might not be affected to the same extent at the concentration of 0.5 mg L⁻¹, but they can still act as an early responder to shifts in the ecosystem. The ostracod population was the least sensitive to biological contamination and was affected less by the REE in comparison to *L. variegatus*. This seems to indicate that the hypothesis that benthic organisms (*L. variegatus*) will be more impacted by a REE-supply to the aquatic environment than pelagic species (*H. incongruens*) should not be rejected. The potential ecotoxicological effects of REE in this microcosm set-up for the microalgae and bacteria remain unknown.

To prevent biological contamination in the future it would be advised to pretreat the natural lake sediment. However, one must then make concessions. One possibility would be to dry the sediment at temperatures of above 80°C so that the bacteria community mainly stays alive, but other organisms are killed. The negative impact might be that bacteria are lost that are more susceptible to high temperatures and that some organic material also might be lost. An alternative solution would be to filter the lake sediment with an Ø0.45 cm filter but may result in nutrient loss and lengthen the experimental process.

Microcosm experiments are complex with high variability, making them risky to perform. But by taking water and sediment samples daily, their analysis would provide early warning signs for unwanted ecosystem shifts and contamination. These early observations show that microcosms are a tool of value to ecotoxicological assessment of REE helping to increase our understanding of impact on the aquatic food web.

Author contribution

Author contribution is in alphabetical order of surname. Chantal van Drimmelen was responsible for developing the set-up and measurements of the microcosms. The first draft of the paper was written by Chantal van Drimmelen. It was then reviewed and revised by Susanne Heise and Andrew Hursthouse. All authors agreed on the final version.

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CHAPTER 10

SIMPLE FOOD WEB MODEL FOR THE CHRONIC IMPACT OF RARE EARTH ELEMENTS IN AN AQUATIC ECOSYSTEM

Chantal K.E. van Drimmelen^{1,2}, Jordi Vives i Batlle³, Andrew Hurthouse², Susanne Heise¹

Keywords: Lanthanides, lanthanum, gadolinium, aquatic invertebrates, predictions, biological communities

¹ Life Sciences, Hamburg University of Applied Science, Ulmenliet 20, D-21033 Hamburg, Germany

² University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

³ Belgian Nuclear research Centre (SCK CEN), Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium

Abstract

Rare earth elements (REE) are high-tech metals used in modern technologies, and their release in the environment causes concerns about the impact of REE on aquatic ecosystems. A food web model could help predict the behaviors of natural systems better. This study aims to develop a food web model for the chronic impact of La and Gd on six biological species, using existing literature and experiments to provide insights in different laboratory and field conditions. The prototype model output shows population oscillations for all species, except for daphnia and microalgae, and stabilizes after day 75. The model seems to indicate that daphnia and *Lumbriculus* are most sensitive to La and Gd. The nutrient submodel is under development, requiring more data on interaction with nitrogen and phosphate, production, and organisms' interactions with nutrients. The future food web model will incorporate benthic-pelagic coupling for La and Gd, requiring a sub model for sediments and changing EC_{50S} to chronic exposure. The model will also include precipitation and speciation of La and Gd. Validation will be through experiments, preferably with “cosm” experiments, to simulate an aquatic ecosystem under controlled conditions. Understanding the limitations of modeling is crucial, as aquatic systems are too complex to be fully captured in a model.

10.1. Introduction

Rare earth elements (REE) are high-technology metals that consist of the 15 lanthanides (lanthanum – lutetium, atomic numbers 57-71) and the elements scandium and yttrium (atomic numbers 21 and 39 respectively). REE are used in various modern technologies, which has raised their emission into aquatic environments. This has led to increasing concerns about the potential impact of anthropogenic concentrations on biological communities. This concern has especially been raised for lanthanum (La) and Gadolinium (Gd), the two most spread and studied REE (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Rogowska *et al.*, 2018a; Trapasso *et al.*, 2021).

Aquatic ecosystems are very complex and to completely understand how different organisms are impacted by REE would be extremely expensive and time consuming. A food web model could help us understand and predict the behaviors of the natural systems better. Food webs can be groups of organisms, populations, or trophic units that are connected through the interactions of consumers and resources (Schmid-Araya and Schmid, 2000). There is a need for studies on the effects of individual and mixtures of contaminants in food webs with which the relevance of trophic positions and biomagnification within aquatic food webs can be understood (Lescord *et al.*, 2015).

Bioaccumulation can occur through either the body surface from ambient media (bioconcentration) or by uptake with food (biomagnification) (Drexler *et al.*, 2003; Ali and Khan, 2019). Biomagnification is when there is an increase of metal concentration in the whole organism from a lower trophic level to a higher trophic level within a food web (Ali and Khan, 2019). It is usually expressed as the ratio of concentration in an organism of a higher trophic level to the concentration of a lower trophic level organisms. Biomagnification of metals in aquatic organisms is considered rare and also have not been generally observed to occur in soil invertebrates. It is generally agreed that it is more likely that there is a potential for bioaccumulation of metals in prey organisms to have a significant impact in predator organism instead of biomagnification (Drexler *et al.*, 2003; Ali and Khan, 2019). However, it is unclear to what extent REE biomagnifies in the aquatic food web compared to other well studied metals (e.g., Hg, Cd and Pb). The bioaccumulation and biomagnification of REE in aquatic food webs can have important implications for organism, ecosystem services, and human health (Ali and Khan, 2019).

The concentration of REE decline with the trophic position of the organism (Amyot *et al.*, 2017). There might be a difference in the concentration of REE with light REEs (La to Eu) being higher than heavy REE (Gd to Lu), especially in fish, shellfish, and crustaceans (Li *et al.*, 2016). REEs bioaccumulate more in biota lower in the food chain (e.g., invertebrates and plants), but that there is limited potential for biomagnification (MacMillan *et al.*, 2017). However, it must be kept in mind that laboratory studies do not

represent the behavior of REE within a natural ecosystem. This is where the modelling of the role of REE within the aquatic food web can provide a solution in understanding what happens in aquatic ecosystems.

Models are systems that are a mathematical representation of that system. It helps us understand the aquatic systems when time and resources are limited, expensive to study, or when it is too impractical to perform experiments in the actual system. However, the reality is that the aquatic systems are even too complex to be wholly captured in the food web model. So, the development of a food web model will require sacrifices of details but should still be a realistic representation of the “natural” system. The food web model should not be considered as a substitute for reality, but a heuristic tool for guiding further study. Meaning that it is used to see what aspects of the system are most in need of further study, and where more data would be needed.

To help the development of a food web model for the chronic impact of REE it is necessary to address some of the knowledge gaps of previous studies. This means that extensive literature research is needed, but also that experiments like nanocosms, microcosms, and even mesocosms are required to further develop the model. The objective of this study was to develop a simple aquatic food web model to identify the chronic impact of La and Gd on multiple biological species, that could be applied in the development of new insights in different laboratory and field conditions. The existing information and data from various literature studies on La and Gd should provide a baseline for the development of the model. The model will focus on six organisms from various trophic levels; primary consumers: microalgae *Raphidocelis subcapitata* and bacteria *Escherichia coli*; primary consumers: water flea *Daphnia magna* and oligochaeta worm *Lumbriculus variegatus*; and secondary consumers: seed shrimp ostracod *Heterocypris incongruens* (Figure 10-1), exposed to anthropogenic concentrations of La and Gd.

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Figure 10-1 Simplified aquatic food web model with six organisms from different trophic levels with primary producers: microalgae *Raphidocelis subcapitata* and bacteria *Escherichia coli*; primary consumers: water flea *Daphnia magna* and oligochaeta worm *Lumbriculus variegatus*; and secondary consumers: seed shrimp ostracod *Heterocypris incongruens*.

10.2. Model description

A prototype food web model (Figure 10-2) was developed in the software ModelMaker® version 3, for the chronic impact of 100 mg L⁻¹ of two REE lanthanum (La) and gadolinium (Gd) containing a sediment-water interface. Figure 10-2 shows each individual aquatic species in a separate-colored box with solid arrows indicating the interactions between itself and other species or situations that impact the organism (e.g., death). Double-lined boxes mean that there is information without a mathematical formula behind it; this can be an excel table or a submodel (e.g., a model within the main food web model). A dashed arrow is an influence, where the modeler needs to tell the model that x is dependent on y.

The prototype food web model build has different compartments based on several existing models described by: Barescut *et al.* (2005); Vives i Batlle (2012); Vives Vives i Batlle, Bryan and McDonald (2008); Vives i Batlle *et al.* (2020); Van Dyck *et al.* (2021); and Kryshev, Sazykina and Sanina (2008). The equations behind each compartment and model flows are given in Table 10-1. The food web model runs over a timescale of 14 days for best optimization.

The current model uses the Lotka-Volterra equations and first-order linear processes are set and solved for the transfer of REE in the aquatic food web. The Lotka-Volterra principle (Wangersky, 1978) assumes that if the abundance of prey increases, the predator abundance also increases and vice versa when the prey abundance reduces the predator abundance also decreases. The food web model also contains predator prey relationships (Barescut *et al.*, 2005), reproduction rates, death rates and a growth-limiting function (GLF) for each species (Van Dyck *et al.*, 2021). The GLF was defined by the effects of temperature (in °C), light function $f(T)$, and a nutrient sub model (still under development, with nitrogen $f(N)$ and phosphate $f(P)$).

The data used came from extensive literature research (Revel, van Drimmelen, et al., submitted) and from gathered information through single-species bioassays and “cosm” experiments (data not shown). Element uptake and toxicity data are integrated into a system of logistic mathematical equations. This is an “open model” whereby partial parameter information can be readily incorporated as information is gradually gained from various experiments and literature, thus refining the model parameterisation. The key challenge in this heuristic approach to modelling is that experiments are required to recalculate the relevant rate constants and the representation of the chemistry of the REE.

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Figure 10-2 Prototype of the food web model for REE toxicity on microalgae (olive green), daphnia (purple), ostracods (brown), Lumbriculus (orange), and bacteria (pink) in ModelMaker 3.

Table 10-1 Equations behind the model flows and compartments of the prototype aquatic food web model for REE examples given for species in general, the word "Species" can be exchanged for algae, bacteria, daphnia, Lumbriculus, or ostracod.

Description	Equation
<i>Compartments</i>	
Main Model	
Species_population	$dSpecies_population/dt = r_Species * ((1 - \ln(2)/(RC50_Species * 30) * REEdose) * (1 - Species_Population/kc_Species)) * Species_population - Pred_Species_to_PredatorSpecies - Death_flux_Species - GLF_Species_In$
Dead_Species	$dDead_Species/dt = + Death_flux_Species - Decomposition_Species$
Growth_Limiting_Function_Species	$dGrowth_limiting_function_Species/dt = fT * fB * fN * fP * fL - GLF_Species$
Submodel GLF	

fBiomass	fB = 1-B/hB
fLight	fL = Photo*(Lexp/KL+Lexp for Lexp<Lmax, Lmax/KL+Lmax by default)
fOrganicN	fN = Nutrient_N_In_Species/(Nutrient_N_In_Species+hN)
fOrganicP	fP = Nutrient_P_In_Species/(Nutrient_P_In_Species+hP)
fTemperature	fT = Texp-Tmin/Topt-Tmin
Submodel Nutrients	
Organic_P	dOrganic_P/dt = (Decomp_Species*M_indv_Species*Frac_P_Species)- Decomposition_Nitrogen
Organic_N	dOrganic_N/dt = (Decomp_Species*M_indv_Species*Frac_N_Species)- Decomposition_Nitrogen
<i>Main Model flows</i>	
Death_flux_Species	Death_flux_Species = d_Species* Species_Population*(1+ln(2)/(EC50_Species*30)*dose)
Decomposition_flux_Species	Decomposition_Species = Dcomp_rate_Species* Dead_Species
GLF_flux_Species	GLF_Species_In = GLF_Species_out
Predation_Flux	Pred_Species_to_PredatorSpecies = pr_Species* Species_Population*PredatorSpecies_population

In this model, the detrimental effect of the stressor (a chemical concentration) is assumed to be the combination of: a) a reducing (negative) effect on the growth rate by introducing, in the equation for dSpecies_population/dt, a multiplier factor to the growth rate r_species: $1 - \frac{\ln(2)}{LD_{50} \times 30} \times concentration$; and b) a promoting (positive) effect on the death rate, by introducing in the equation for the death flux for the species, the multiplier $1 + \frac{\ln(2)}{LC_{50} \times 30} \times Concentration$. The term $1 \pm \frac{\ln(2)}{LC_{50} \times 30} \times Concentration$ comes from expanding polynomially to the first order the exponential function $e^{\pm \frac{\ln(2)}{LC_{50} \times 30} \times Concentration \times t}$ where $\frac{\ln(2)}{LC_{50} \times 30}$ is an attenuation constant set-up to ensure that after t = 30 days of applying a concentration equal to LC₅₀, one gets a 50% effect.

10.3. Prototype model output

The prototype model output (Figure 10-3) shows that the first few days there are some spikes for all species, except daphnia and the microalgae. Afterwards all species except the microalgae (black) seem to stabilize until around day 75. The undeveloped nutrient submodel plays a role in the stabilization lines as this influences the growth of the organisms. The ostracod (red) and bacteria (pink) start showing almost an “heartbeat” pattern, but slowly stabilize towards day 100. The microalgae start to grow exponentially till day 40, then stabilize, and suddenly drop around day 75. The oscillations around day 75 might be related

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to predation by the daphnia (neon green) as small spikes can be seen in the daphnia lines (Wangersky, 1978). The lines for the daphnia and Lumbriculus (olive green) are close to 0 which indicates that these species might be the most sensitive towards La and Gd.

The nutrient sub model (Wilson *et al.*, 2010) is currently under development, but this requires more data on the interaction of REE with nitrogen and phosphate. As well as the production and interaction of the organisms with the nutrients when exposed to REE. However, running the nutrient sub model with adaptations causes the program to crash, a problem that likely relates to optimizing the solver algorithm parameters in ModelMaker as is often the case in models of this nature. The nutrient modelling issues are caused by the loss of the populations, as the uptake is modelled well but not the production. The nutrient mass constant is also still being defined.

Figure 10-3 Output of the model prototype for microalgae (black), bacteria (pink), daphnia (neon green), Lumbriculus (olive green), and ostracods (red) exposed to 100 mg L^{-1} of La and Gd.

10.4. Future Development, limitations, and lessons learned

In the future the model will have the benthic-pelagic coupling for La and Gd integrated. The addition of benthic-pelagic coupling would mean that a sub model for sediments would also need to be added. It is also important that the EC_{50} s, which are right now based on acute exposure, are changed to chronic exposure (Kryshev, Sazykina and Sanina, 2008). In addition to the element uptake and toxicity data a Reparation Mechanisms Model (Kryshev, Sazykina and Sanina, 2008; Vives i Batlle *et al.*, 2020), which considers organisms getting better or new organisms joining the existing population in the ecosystem, will be integrated. Another important element to add is the precipitation and speciation of La and Gd into the food web model. The model would then need to be validated through experiments, preferably with “cosm” experiments as these allow to simulate an aquatic ecosystem under controlled conditions (Clements and Newman, 2003).

For any modelling study, it is important to understand the limitations of modelling. The reality is that the aquatic systems are even too complex to be wholly captured in any food web model. So, the development of a food web model will require sacrifices of details, it needs to be simplified. It is important to find the balance between too complex and too simple. However, REE makes developing the model complicated due to confounding factors (e.g., nutrients and pH). Further systematic studies are necessary for the development of the food web model due to the limited knowledge on chemical speciation and the interactions of REE with the various biological systems (e.g., bacteria, microalgae, and invertebrates).

The current model is limited due to this lack in knowledge surrounding REE, the still developing nutrient sub model. Then there are also the limits of the software program used itself; While very user friendly and suitable for the current approach, it like many other software is also prone to crashing. Additional future study is recommended to investigate instabilities in the model solution, by which it is mend the tendency in nonlinear mathematical systems to predict multiple states within which the mathematical solution can shift. These shifts are not always smooth, leading to “tipping points” and apparently chaotic oscillatory behaviors. The current food web model could be expanded by combining it with other software models out there, such as PHREEQC for the speciation and MixSIAR for the nutrient sources.

A deeper understanding is needed for all of the processes involved in the food web model, as well as of the chronic impact of La and Gd on multiple biological species. The development of the food web model can help us understand the natural system better but also assist in the development of new insights in different laboratory and field conditions, using what is known as a heuristic approach. With hope that it one day may lead to easier and justified decision making of how we deal with contaminants in our natural systems in a more time and cost-effective manner.

Author contribution

Author contribution is in alphabetical order of surname. Chantal van Drimmelen was responsible for the development of the first version of the model with Jordi Vives i Batlle giving initial advice. Chantal van Drimmelen developed the model further and was responsible for performing experiments and gathering of information to provide the model with data. The first draft of the paper was written by Chantal van Drimmelen. It was then reviewed and revised by Susanne Heise, Andrew Hursthouse, and Jordi Vives i Batlle. The final version was approved by all authors.

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CHAPTER 11

GENERAL DISCUSSION

Rare earth elements (REE) have become a source of concern due to their potential ecotoxicological effects in aquatic ecosystems. Their widespread use in modern society and the subsequent increase in REE concentrations in global water bodies has led to these metals being labelled as emerging contaminants (Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018; Malhotra *et al.*, 2020; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). Only 1% of all REE present in aquatic ecosystems are present in the water phase, meaning that 99% end up in the sediment phase (or attached to suspended matter) (Weltje *et al.*, 2002). This might lead to the assumption that REE are of little importance to pelagic species.

Through benthic-pelagic coupling, however, REE may become remobilized and available to organisms in the water phase, too (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Moermond *et al.*, 2001). It has thus become urgent and critical to study the effects of REE on aquatic organisms, even though there are still many challenges and difficulties in assessing and quantifying their toxicity in both the water and sediment phase, e.g., due to confounding factors such as pH, chemical speciation and precipitation, and exposure routes. These challenges have led to contradicting conclusions from literature in the assessment of adverse effects on aquatic organisms, which are presented in **Chapter 2**.

The review clearly showed that most studies on the ecotoxicity of REE focus on acute effects and single-species bioassays. Most of these bioassays are performed with water systems, very few studies focus on sediment data and almost no data is available on the benthic-pelagic coupling of REE. Studies focus on selected species from few trophic levels. Little has been done involving complex (simulated) ecosystem approaches (e.g., “cosm” studies). As has been stated by Batley and Campbell (2022) and has been identified in the review, chemical speciation modelling of REE, while important, currently still has limitations, as the thermodynamic data are incomplete. It is further complicated in the presence of sediments being traps for REE. Additionally, for trivalent metals, the bioavailability of chemical species is still unclear (Batley and Campbell, 2022), as is the mode of action, even for relatively well-studied REE like La and Gd (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014).

The work of this thesis extended our knowledge and addressed some of the challenges that have been identified in the **Chapter 2**. It looked into both the acute and chronic effects in single-species and multi-species tests within the sediment-water phase. Sub-lethal and lethal endpoints were measured with special focus on behavior. Thus, the **objective of this thesis was to investigate the chronic effects of rare earth elements on the aquatic benthic-pelagic ecosystem, to better understand the toxicity on individual aquatic invertebrates and communities**. This was accomplished by combining acute and chronic exposure of La and Gd in standardized and non-standardized ecotoxicological bioassays with single- and multi-

species studies. With the goal to have an initial step toward connecting different trophic levels in the sediment and water phase, establishing benthic-pelagic coupling.

11.1. Acute effects by REE occur at concentrations that are not environmentally relevant, chronic effects at low concentrations are thus negligible

The main discourse within ecotoxicology and other scientific fields is that the available ecotoxicological data from standardized acute single-species assays are of low environmental relevance due to the use of high exposure concentrations (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; González *et al.*, 2015). However, acute single-species bioassays are still useful for uncovering the lethal concentrations of contaminants which helps with decision making in risk assessment. The mode of action behind REE also remains largely unknown, and single-species tests can help identify potential mechanisms.

The results of **Chapter 3** and **Chapter 4** show that the toxicity of REE is a direct effect of La and Gd on the microalgae, rather than indirectly through phosphate limitation. In **Chapter 3** the toxicity of La and Gd was studied on three different microalgae species: *Raphidocelis subcapitata*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, and *Scenedesmus vacuolatus*. The microalgae were exposed for 72h to different concentrations of La and Gd in three culture media containing different phosphate sources. The range of concentration of La and Gd were used to estimate the nominal and dissolved EC₅₀s for each REE under the different phosphate conditions. All EC₅₀s showed different outcomes based on the individual REE, the phosphate source, and the algal species. The ISO medium with inorganic phosphate (according to the international guideline (ISO, 2012)) is commonly used in standardized microalgae bioassays. The nominal EC₅₀ values for both La and Gd indicated low toxicity for all three microalgae species. These low nominal EC₅₀ values are related to the complexation and precipitation of REE with the inorganic phosphate (**Chapter 4**). This reduced the bioavailability of both La and Gd for the microalgae, which was confirmed by the low dissolved REE concentrations measured after 72h of exposure. The decrease of bioavailability of REE is due to the presence of ligands like phosphate (**Chapter 4**), which limits the toxicity of La and Gd (Lachaux *et al.*, 2022; Aharchaou *et al.*, 2020; Weltje *et al.*, 2004). This becomes clear when the replacement of the inorganic phosphate in the medium by organic phosphate (α -glucose 1-phosphate, ISO-G1P) resulted in less precipitation and an increase in the toxicity of La and Gd. The lowest EC₅₀ values for both La and Gd was observed in the medium that did not contain any phosphate (MHSM). Thus, the absence of phosphate in the media resulted in lower EC₅₀s due to the higher concentration of dissolved REE.

R. subcapitata is the species that is recommended by the international guideline (ISO, 2012) and the toxicity of dissolved Gd concentrations was found to be higher than for La. This result was similar for *S. vacuolatus*. The toxicity for *C. vulgaris* was an order of magnitude lower for La and two for Gd compared

to the other two microalgae species. The difference in toxicity between REE and microalgae species has also been confirmed by Bergsten-Torralba *et al.* (2020). Thus, varied toxicity of REE suggests that the toxicity of these elements is also dependent on the biological species. This variation in species sensitivity shows that standardized acute single-species assays should acknowledge interspecies differences in risk assessment.

Some studies have also shown that acute toxicity data of REE are not always reliable and that REE are not acutely toxic but can become so under chronic exposure (Blinova *et al.*, 2018). In **Chapter 6** *Daphnia magna* was chronically exposed to 0.5 mg L⁻¹ La and Gd through three different routes: waterborne, diet borne, and a combination of water and diet borne exposure for 21 days. The chronic exposure to both REE did not result in any mortality, alteration to the feeding rate, or the growth of the daphnia. Which is in agreement with the lack of inhibitory effects on the reproduction of *D. magna* found at chronic exposure of 0.1 mg L⁻¹ Gd (Blinova *et al.*, 2021).

However, the potential contribution of diet was not considered. Diet does play a role in the reproduction but is often not considered when acute bioassays are performed (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Ma *et al.*, 2016). The reproduction endpoints in **Chapter 6** indicate that REE contaminated food does play an important role for the reproduction of daphnia under chronic exposure. The first brood release for La was delayed for the combined water and diet borne exposure, and the total number of offspring after 21 days was significantly reduced by Gd for both the diet alone and combined exposure. Which is in agreement with other studies that found that dietary REE exposure hinders the reproduction of crustaceans (De Schampelaere *et al.*, 2007; Hook and Fisher, 2001). Reproduction has been linked to energy, and it could thus be that the bioaccumulation of REE within the intestines of *D. magna* found in **Chapter 6** affects the mechanisms that regulate the conversion of nutrients to energy (Smolders, Baillieux and Blust, 2005). The results on the reproduction were also in agreement with those of the onset point of **Chapter 8**. Reproduction is a sensitive endpoint that can have adverse effects on the population development of *D. magna* (Adamczuk, 2020).

Chapter 5 showed that chronic exposure on *Myriophyllum aquaticum* could also lead to recovery. REE triggers on the PSII of were evaluated for the chronic exposure (10 days) of La, Ce, Nd, and Gd. Ce and Nd decreased (even at the lowest concentration of 50 mg kg⁻¹) the chlorophyll fluorescence at the beginning of the test, but at the end there was no significant difference compared to the control. This indicates that during long-term exposure to REE that recovery can occur, which might not be observed under acute exposure. *M. aquaticum* appears to demonstrate a hermetic response (stimulation at low

concentrations versus negative effects at high concentrations) to Ce and Nd, which has been observed for Ce in plants (Gjata *et al.*, 2022; Preetha *et al.*, 2023; Rico *et al.*, 2015; Jahani *et al.*, 2019). It would thus be beneficial to expose *M. aquaticum* even longer to the different REE at even lower concentrations to investigate if the plants show a hermetic effect or long-term recovery.

However, it has been demonstrated that the chronic exposure to multi-species can result in more sensitive and subtle detection of impacts on natural communities compared to single-species bioassays (Santos *et al.*, 2018). So, there is a need to further investigate the effects of chronic exposure on REE in a multi-species setting. The nanocosms of **Chapter 8** showed that they are useful tools complementary to single-species assays to investigate REE in the water phase and sediment along the *R. subcapitata*-*D. magna* food chain. Understanding the relationship between prey and predator in the nanocosms gives insight in the potential effect of chronic REE exposure in a broader aquatic food web. The chronic endpoints after 14 days of exposure showed a trend for both *D. magna* and *R. subcapitata*. A clear prey-predator pattern could be noticed along the *R. subcapitata*-*D. magna* food chain for the control but not for La and Gd. The trend was stronger for Gd suggesting that La was less toxic along this food chain. Daphnia not eating on their prey is an indication that REE causes toxic stress. Which can act as an early warning sign that reduction in reproduction will occur (Juchelka and Snell, 1995; Bownik, 2017). Algal growth will be stimulated if no predators are around. Which can lead to algae blooms throwing off the equilibrium in the aquatic ecosystem and decreasing water quality (Clément and Zaid, 2004; Amorim and Moura, 2021).

This was noticed with the biological contamination in **Chapter 9**, which demonstrated that microcosm experiments are very complex and that the established ecosystems can be easily shifted out of equilibrium. However, it still provided information on chronic REE toxicity and microcosms should be considered a tool in understanding the wider impact of REE in the aquatic ecosystem. Especially because purely focused ecotoxicological microcosm studies with REE are very limited and as far as the author is aware the microbial microcosm with Gd from Fuma *et al.* (2001) is the only one published to date. The oligochaete worm *Lumbriculus variegatus* was sensitive towards 0.5 mg kg⁻¹ of Gd in the microcosm, while the ostracod *Heterocypris incongruens* was not significantly affected by a chronic exposure of 11 days. Several studies have confirmed that *H. incongruens* is not very sensitive to REE or other heavy metals (González *et al.*, 2015; Romero-Freire *et al.*, 2021). The microcosms also showed that pelagic species like daphnia are early responders to ecosystem shifts even if contamination is not the cause. This provides, in addition to ecotoxicity data, information on the sensitivity and tolerance of species and indirect ecological effects (e.g., ecosystems shifts) (Santos *et al.*, 2018).

In **Chapter 10** an attempt was made to develop a simple aquatic food web model to identify the chronic impact of La and Gd on multiple biological species. The model focused on six organisms from various trophic levels (microalgae, bacteria, water fleas, oligochaeta worms, and ostracods) chronically exposed to La and Gd. However, the data from **Chapter 2** and the information gathered from the experiments in this thesis were not sufficient to have the food web model completed and more research needs to be done on the toxicity and mechanisms behind REE contamination.

The results of this thesis show that acute adverse effects by REE occur at anthropogenic concentrations and not at environmentally relevant levels for single-species assays, such as microalgae (**Chapter 3** and **Chapter 4**). However, the chronic exposure of REE to pelagic invertebrates showed that even at low concentrations adverse effects can still occur (**Chapter 6**), but that organisms can also recover (**Chapter 5**). The chronic exposure at low concentrations of REE can have a big influence on the population and community interactions within an aquatic food web (**Chapter 8**, **Chapter 9**, and **Chapter 10**). Thus, **the hypothesis that chronic effects at low concentrations are negligible** should be rejected. This becomes very important as low effects have big consequences over a longer period of time, potentially leading to the collapse of the aquatic ecosystem.

11.2. As metals cannot be sensed by olfactory systems, they will not cause any active avoidance behavior by pelagic invertebrates

Chapter 7 showed that for Gd, the vertical avoidance behavior of *D. magna* was very clear. The aim of this chapter was to determine if La and Gd bound in sediment ($0.001 - 100 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) led to avoidance behavior by the water flea. The avoidance of REE contaminated sediment was noticed in the experiments of **Chapter 8**, even though there were microalgae available for feeding on the bottom of the nanocosms. It has also been demonstrated that microalgae can grow faster on the sediment than in the water column and so more food should be available for the daphnia at the bottom (Lamonica *et al.*, 2016).

The sediment of the experimental vessels in **Chapter 7** was spiked with various concentrations of La and Gd. Although the avoidance behavior was found to be only significant for the vertical movement of *D. magna*, the horizontal movement showed that dissolved Gd and La led to increased agitation swimming for the crustacean. However, this raised the question how do the daphnia sense the REE in the sediment? As far as the author knows, there is no literature available on the mechanism behind the sensing of metals by water fleas. It has been demonstrated that daphnia have the ability to discriminate between algae through odor (van Gool and Ringelberg, 1996), which is linked to the info chemicals (kairomones) used by the daphnia to sense the presence of predators (Weiss *et al.*, 2018). For pesticides it is known that the

sensing is related to the neurotoxic effects (Moreira *et al.*, 2023), but this seems unlikely as metals do not have a neurotoxic effect.

There is a need for more research into what the sensing mechanisms for metals are, but it is likely that for REE it is linked to the competition with calcium (Barry and Meehan, 2000; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Tan, Yang and Wilkinson, 2017; Sherry, Caravan and Lenkinski, 2009; Martino *et al.*, 2018). Calcium plays a role in the changes related to survival, reproduction, and locomotor activities in daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates (Muysen, De Schampelaere and Janssen, 2009; Honnappa, Hannah Sulochana and Jayaraman, 1975). **So, while the mechanisms behind daphnia sensing metals remains unknown, the hypothesis that contaminated sediment will not cause any active avoidance behavior by pelagic invertebrates cannot be rejected in the case of REE.**

11.3. Multispecies tests in sediment-water systems will not show any effects because of the strong partitioning of REE to the sediments

The avoidance behavior of *D. magna* to REE contaminated sediment investigated in **Chapter 7** is related to the type of REE and the concentration. The results of the TXRF showed that most of the measured REE could be found associated with the sediment phase by an order of magnitude in comparison to the water phase, which is in agreement with Weltje *et al.* (2002). Lanthanum, as a LREE, was more strongly associated with the sediment compared to the HREE Gd. This is in agreement with natural sediments where LREEs are found in higher concentrations than HREE (Brito *et al.*, 2018; Jiang *et al.*, 2022). LREE adsorb more strongly to organic matter compared to HREE which are more likely to form carbonate complexes (Smrzka *et al.*, 2019). The results demonstrate that Gd is more easily remobilized into the water phase and thus more likely to have a toxic effect on pelagic species like daphnia and microalgae. However, as metal toxicity does not necessarily come from presence of free ions (Adams *et al.*, 2020; Drexler *et al.*, 2003), bioavailability may not explain completely the avoidance behavior seen in **Chapter 7**.

Chapter 8 indicated that REE in a water-sediment system impacts the dynamic between pelagic predators like water fleas *D. magna* and pelagic producers such as microalgae *R. subcapitata*. Nanocosms containing sediment and media were spiked in the water column with environmentally relevant (1 and 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and anthropogenically relevant nominal concentrations (100 and 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) of La and Gd. This spiking of the water column simulates the effect of REE effluents getting into water bodies, these REE then form an equilibrium between sediment and the water phase.

The changes observed in the decreased feeding behavior of *D. magna* in **Chapter 8** and the avoidance and agitated swimming of the water flea in **Chapter 7**. These changes in behavior of *D. magna* caused by the

contaminated sediment indicate that REE results in stress to the primary consumer, impacting other endpoints such as the reproduction (Juchelka and Snell, 1995) which was also observed in the nanocosms .

The decrease of grazing by daphnia on microalgae established with REE contaminated sediment through the spiking of the water column of the nanocosms (**Chapter 8**) could lead to an increase in the growth of the microalgae (Clément and Zaid, 2004). For daphnia the predation risk can increase and change the population dynamics when the organism avoids REE contaminated sediment (**Chapter 7**) (Hanazato, 2001). However, not all pelagic species seem to be equally affected by REE contaminated sediments and benthic species such as *L. variegatus* and *M. aquaticum* (**Chapter 5**) are also still at risk.

In **Chapter 5** the toxic responses of *M. aquaticum* to La, Ce, Nd, and Gd were compared. This showed that even though LREE like La, Ce, and Nd are more likely to be bound to the sediment (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Gwenzi *et al.*, 2018) it is still the HREE Gd that is more toxic to the macrophyte *M. aquaticum*. Gd exhibited chlorosis/necrosis and significant adverse effects on the fresh weight of the plant. The REE are taken up via the roots of the plant but after that it is not clear where the REE migrates. Aquatic macrophytes do not only play an important role in the ecosystem through providing food and habitat for other organisms (Wetzel, 2001; Lewis, 1995). If they disappear from the sediment system, it would have consequences for the amount of REE that are resuspended into the pelagic phase.

The results of research described in this thesis show that although most of the REE end up in the sediment, they can still become a risk to multiple species through benthic-coupling (Yang *et al.*, 1999; Mori, 1999; Weltje *et al.*, 2002; Andrade *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, REE contaminated sediment can be seen as a potential driver for concentrations in aquatic systems (Amyot *et al.*, 2017; MacMillan *et al.*, 2019). Thus, the hypothesis that **multispecies tests in sediment-water systems will not show any effects because of the strong partitioning of REE to the sediments can be rejected**. Consequently, sediments can be seen as a source of REE in the water phase and a thorough understanding of the role of sediment bound REE is essential.

11.4. Conclusion

Various tools were applied to identify the ecotoxicological effects of benthic-pelagic coupling of La and Gd on multiple aquatic organisms. The results showed that it is important to study the effects of the role of REE contamination in both the water and sediment phase. The results for the individual species are needed to understand what occurs in simulated ecosystems when aquatic species are exposed to REE.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

However, simulated ecosystem experiments are also needed to have a better understanding of the potential consequences of the observed effects in single-species bioassays. It is here important to consider both acute and chronic exposure as well as the unique properties of REE which make it complex and challenging to fully understand the mechanisms behind the adverse effects; of which many remain still undiscovered.

With the predicted increase in REE concentrations due to anthropogenic activities the subsequent chronic exposure will have consequences for the whole aquatic ecosystem. When REE from effluents end up in the sediment phase both pelagic and benthic species will be affected by REE. The research presented in this thesis addresses the potential chronic effects of elevated REE concentrations on the aquatic benthopelagic ecosystem, and the need to look at various experimental set-ups, species, and exposure times required for the risk assessment of REE toxicity on individual aquatic invertebrates and communities.

11.5. References

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

SI3-1 Composition of the media with different phosphate sources

Table SI3-1.1 Composition of the ISO medium with pH adjusted to 8.2 ± 0.2

Sterile Ultrapure Water		97.2 ml
Stock solution 1) Macro nutrients	g L ⁻¹	1 ml
NH ₄ Cl	1.5	
MgCl ₂ * 6H ₂ O	1.2	
CaCl ₂ * 2H ₂ O	1.8	
MgSO ₄ * 7H ₂ O	1.5	
KH ₂ PO ₄	0.16	
Stock solution 2) Fe-EDTA	mg L ⁻¹	0.1 ml
FeCl ₃ * 6H ₂ O	64	
Na ₂ EDTA * 2H ₂ O	100	
Stock solution 3) Trace elements	mg L ⁻¹	0.1 ml
H ₃ BO ₃	185	
MnCl ₂ * 4H ₂ O	415	
ZnCl ₂	3	
CoCl ₂ * 6H ₂ O	1.5	
CuCl ₂ * 2H ₂ O	0.01	
Na ₂ MoO ₄ * 2H ₂ O	7	
Stock solution 4	g L ⁻¹	0.6 ml
NaHCO ₃	50	
MOPS buffer ≥ 99 % g (C ₇ H ₁₅ NO ₄ S)	209.3	1 ml

Table SI3-1.2 Composition of the ISO-G1P medium with pH adjusted to 8.2 ± 0.2

Sterile Ultrapure Water		97.2 ml
Stock solution 1) Macro nutrients	g L ⁻¹	1 ml
NH ₄ Cl	1.5	
MgCl ₂ * 6H ₂ O	1.2	
CaCl ₂ * 2H ₂ O	1.8	
MgSO ₄ * 7H ₂ O	1.5	
C ₆ H ₁₃ O ₉ P (Glucose 1-phosphate)	0.25	
Stock solution 2) Fe-EDTA	mg L ⁻¹	0.1 ml
FeCl ₃ * 6H ₂ O	64	
Na ₂ EDTA * 2H ₂ O	100	
Stock solution 3) Trace elements	mg L ⁻¹	0.1 ml
H ₃ BO ₃	185	
MnCl ₂ * 4H ₂ O	415	
ZnCl ₂	3	
CoCl ₂ * 6H ₂ O	1.5	
CuCl ₂ * 2H ₂ O	0.01	
Na ₂ MoO ₄ * 2H ₂ O	7	
Stock solution 4	g L ⁻¹	0.6 ml
NaHCO ₃	50	
MOPS buffer ≥ 99 % g (C ₇ H ₁₅ NO ₄ S)	209.3	1 ml

SUMMPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Table SI3-1.3 Composition of the (pre-culture) MHSM-1 medium with pH adjusted to 6.8 ± 0.2

Stock solution	Stock Solution	mg L ⁻¹
Beijerick's	g L ⁻¹	50
NH ₄ Cl	10	
MgSO ₄ * 7H ₂ O	0.4	
CaCl ₂ * 2H ₂ O	0.2	
Phosphate stock	g L ⁻¹	25
KH ₂ PO ₄	29.6	
K ₂ HPO ₄	57.6	
AAP trace metal solution	g L ⁻¹	1
H ₃ BO ₃	185.52	
MnCl ₂ * 4H ₂ O	415.38	
ZnCl ₂	3.28	
FeCl ₃ * 6H ₂ O	159.78	
Na ₂ EDTA * 2H ₂ O	300	
CoCl ₂ * 6H ₂ O	2.6	
Na ₂ MoO ₄ * 2H ₂ O	7.26	
CuCl ₂ * 2H ₂ O	0.01	
MOPS buffer	g L ⁻¹	
MOPS buffer ≥ 99 % g (C ₇ H ₁₅ NO ₄ S)	20.9	100

Table SI3-1.4 Composition of the (test) MHSM-2 medium with pH adjusted to 6.8 ± 0.2

Stock solution	g L ⁻¹
NH ₄ NO ₃	0.07
KNO ₃	0.42
MgSO ₄	0.01
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	0.02
NaOH	0.12
MOPS buffer ≥ 99 % g (C ₇ H ₁₅ NO ₄ S)	20.9
C ₂ H ₃ O ₂	0.01

SI5-1 Modified Steinberg medium

Modified Steinberg medium contained 350 mg L⁻¹ KNO₃; 295 mg L⁻¹ Ca (NO₃)₂ · 4H₂O; 90 mg L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄; 12.6 mg L⁻¹ K₂HPO₄; 100 mg L⁻¹ MgSO₄ · 7H₂O; 120 µg L⁻¹ H₃BO₃; 180 µg L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ · 7H₂O; 44 µg L⁻¹ Na₂MoO₄ · 2H₂O; 180 µg L⁻¹ MnCl₂ · 4H₂O; 760 µg L⁻¹ FeCl₃ · 6H₂O; 1500 µg L⁻¹ EDTA Disodium salt · 2H₂O, with pH = 5.5 ± 0.2

SI5-2 Effect of acetone on *M. aquaticum* growth rateTable SI5-2.1 Effect of acetone treatment on *M. aquaticum* growth rate

Replicas	Weight before test	Weight after test	Difference	Growth Rate/ Day	Inhibition per each plant %	FWC %	I _{FWC}
1	0.0241	0.0746	1.130	0.113	-17.701	209.544	-25.913
2	0.0195	0.0665	1.227	0.123	-27.790	241.026	-44.831
3	0.0214	0.0618	1.061	0.106	-10.470	188.785	-13.440
4	0.028	0.1	1.273	0.127	-32.601	257.143	-54.516
5	0.0298	0.096	1.170	0.117	-21.858	222.148	-33.487
6	0.0236	0.0765	1.176	0.118	-22.505	224.153	-34.692

SUMMPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

SI5-3 Yield of *M. aquaticum*

Table SI5-3.1 Yield of *M. aquaticum* and the significance for each day of the test. * Statistical significance at $p < 0.05$ (*); $p < 0.01$ (**); $p < 0.001$ (***)

Day	La				Ce				Nd				Gd			
	Control	50 mg kg ⁻¹	250 mg kg ⁻¹	500 mg kg ⁻¹	Control	50 mg kg ⁻¹	250 mg kg ⁻¹	500 mg kg ⁻¹	Control	50 mg kg ⁻¹	250 mg kg ⁻¹	500 mg kg ⁻¹	Control	50 mg kg ⁻¹	250 mg kg ⁻¹	500 mg kg ⁻¹
1	0.591	0.591	0.576	0.578	0.585	0.515	0.486	0.548	0.585	0.511	0.572	0.467	0.506	0.582	0.541	0.345* *
2	0.565	0.528	0.579	0.576	0.573	0.478*	0.47*	0.546	0.573	0.462*	0.506	0.404*	0.489	0.465	0.518	0.362* *
3	0.517	0.543	0.572	0.553	0.539	0.447*	0.434*	0.522	0.539	0.416*	0.469	0.441*	0.505	0.453	0.496	0.32**
4	0.53	0.524	0.486	0.57	0.561	0.51	0.473*	0.538	0.561	0.447*	0.475	0.474	0.481	0.477	0.496	0.271* *
5	0.507	0.547	0.536	0.566	0.562	0.524	0.46	0.535	0.562	0.492	0.507	0.493	0.482	0.478	0.496	0.271* *
6	0.511	0.53	0.541	0.563	0.56	0.513	0.479	0.546	0.56	0.498	0.51	0.496	0.476	0.448	0.461	0.198* *
7	0.529	0.546	0.541	0.564	0.55	0.501	0.489	0.541	0.55	0.517	0.544	0.532	0.498	0.458	0.47	0.179* *
8	0.548	0.563	0.541	0.563	0.556	0.516	0.516	0.54	0.556	0.524	0.532	0.526	0.546	0.481	0.488	0.126* *
9	0.558	0.567	0.553	0.597	0.551	0.532	0.498	0.505	0.551	0.534	0.537	0.537	0.541	0.449*	0.455*	0.089* *
10	0.559	0.56	0.559	0.61	0.551	0.532	0.498	0.505	0.551	0.523	0.53	0.532	0.538	0.419*	0.438*	0.054* **

SI5-4 Photographs of whorls of *M. aquaticum* under different conditions

Figure SI5-4.1 *M. aquaticum* whorls under control conditions (a) and after exposure to Gd at 500 μ M (b) for 10 days.

SI6-1 Algae consumption over time by *D. magna*

Figure SI6-1.1 Algae consumption over time of daphnia exposed to La and Gd. See Table S6-1.1 for linear curve equations.

Table SI6-1.1 Equations of each linear curve for figure S6-1.1

	La	Gd
Control	$y = 1.5E6x + 6.3E6$	$y = 1.4E6x + 1.7E7$
Dietary	$y = 8.4E5x + 9.4E6$	$y = 1.3E6x + 9.6E6$
Waterborne	$y = 9.4E5x + 1.0E7$	$y = 1.1E6x + 1.3E7$
Dietary + Waterborne	$y = 1.3E6x + 1.2E6$	$y = 1.1E6x + 1.4E7$

S17-1 3D-print information of the horizontal migration vessel

Figure S17-1.1 Schematic 3D-print overview in mm of the round shaped experimental vessel for the horizontal migration of *D. magna* made from PETG filament.

SI7-2 3D-print information of the vertical migration vessel

Figure SI7-2.1 Schematic 3D-print overview in mm of the rectangle shaped experimental vessel for the vertical migration of *D. magna* made from PETG filament.

SI7-3 Composition of Lufa-soil 2.2

Table SI7-3.1 Characteristics of LUFA-soil 2.2. based on the Chemical and physical characteristics of standard soils according to GLP from LUFA Speyer, Germany.

Organic carbon (% C)	1.77 ± 0.56
Nitrogen (% N)	0.20 ± 0.06
pH value	5.6 ± 0.3
Cation exchange capacity (meq/100g)	8.5 ± 2.0
Particle size distribution (mm) according to German DIN (%)	
<0.002	10.6 ± 1.9
0.002-0.006	3.3 ± 1.1
0.006-0.02	5.3 ± 0.5
0.02-0.063	7.4 ± 0.9
0.063-0.2	30.9 ± 3.4
0.2-0.63	41.6 ± 3.0
0.63-2.0	0.9 ± 0.1
Soil type	Loamy sand (LS)

SI7-4 Frequency distribution of vertical and horizontal migration

Table SI7-4.1 Frequency distribution for both Gd and La of the vertical and horizontal migration in Chi-square and degrees of freedom (df). Significant differences between the control and the different exposures are indicated by * $q < 0.05$; ** $q < 0.01$; *** $q < 0.001$; NS = not significant.

mg kg ⁻¹	Gd		La	
	Vertical migration Chi-square, df	Horizontal migration Chi-square, df	Vertical migration Chi-square, df	Horizontal migration Chi-square, df
100	26.06 ^{***} , 4	2.63 ^{NS} , 2	17.70 ^{***} , 4	1.68 ^{NS} , 2
75	28.24 ^{***} , 4	0.96 ^{NS} , 2	27.14 ^{***} , 4	3.79 ^{NS} , 2
50	20.99 ^{***} , 4	8.91 ^{**} , 2	11.36 ^{**} , 4	6.88 ^{**} , 2
25	27.25 ^{***} , 4	3.57 ^{NS} , 2	11.60 ^{**} , 4	3.39 ^{NS} , 2
10	24.77 ^{***} , 4	4.53 ^{NS} , 2	5.613 ^{NS} , 4	2.01 ^{NS} , 2
1	15.52 ^{***} , 4	8.29 ^{**} , 2	13.38 ^{***} , 4	0.89 ^{NS} , 2
0.1	39.78 ^{***} , 4	4.24 ^{NS} , 2	10.67 ^{**} , 4	6.81 ^{**} , 2
0.01	8.873 ^{***} , 4	8.18 ^{**} , 2	4.81 ^{NS} , 4	2.14 ^{NS} , 2
0.001	18.87 ^{NS} , 4	6.76 ^{**} , 2	8.36 ^{NS} , 4	1.25 ^{NS} , 2

S17-5 Video movement measurements distance moved all exposure concentrations

Figure S17-5.1 Distance moved in pixels at time points 0,1,2, and 3 hours by adult *D. manga* exposed to Gd (left) and La (right) at concentrations 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 mg L⁻¹.

Figure S17-5.2 Active time in seconds at time points 0,1,2, and 3 hours by adult *D. manga* exposed to Gd (left) and La (right) at concentrations 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 mg L⁻¹.

S18-1 TXRF information and quality sheet

S4 T-STAR®

TXRF spectrometer for element analysis

Instrument Book

2 Instrument Pass

Spectrometer	S/N: 4210 0078 0822
System configuration	Instrument version: S4 T-STAR 400 Configured system: no
X-Ray Tube 1	Type: ixtube-Mo-50 0,6m Tube target material: Mo S/N: 2003215
Monochromator 1	TXRF-multilayer Mo-HE S/N: MC 209
X-Ray Tube 2	Type: ixtube-W-50 0,6m Tube target material: W S/N: 2003058
Monochromator 2	Multilayer W/Si S/N: MC 213
HV generator 1	Type: HiTek MH60-503-06 S/N: 2180086
XGS 1	S/N: 0642
HV generator 2	Type: HiTek MH60-503-06 S/N: 2180085
XGS 2	S/N: 0629
Detector	Type: XFlash Detektor 660 PAR S/N: 17296
Stacker	Type: Cybertron S/N: 2122222233 088
Desktop-PC	Type: OptiPlex XE3 S/N: 2T91LK3
Monitor	Type:
T-ESPRIT Software	Version: 1.0.1.436 License: no
Date	2022-09-02
Tested by	E. Muhl

3 Technical Parameters

Spectrometer	
Size (W x D x H)	693 mm x 512 mm x 528 mm
Weight	89 kg
Line Voltage	100–240 V AC / 50/60 Hz
Connection	Two-pole plug with earthing contact P+N+PE According IEC 60320 C13/C14
Operating conditions	
Optimum room temperature	24 °C, with a maximal temperature drift of 1°C / h
Working temperature range	17 °C – 29 °C
Relative humidity	20 % – 80 %, not condensing
Dust, particles	free of corrosive fumes, no intensive dust exposure
High voltage generator	
Manufacturer	HiTek
Type	MH60-503-06
Input	24 V
Max. operating values	50 kV, 1000 µA
X-Ray Tube 1	
Manufacturer	Incoatec GmbH
Type:	Ceramic side window micro focus tube, 50 x 50 µm, Mo target, 0.1mm Be-window
Max. excitation energy	50 kV / 1000 µA
Monochromator	Multilayer monochromator, 17.5 keV
X-Ray Tube 2	
Manufacturer	Incoatec GmbH
Type	Ceramic side window micro focus tube, 50 x 50 µm, W target, 0.1 mm Be-window
Monochromator	Multilayer monochromator, 35 keV
3rd Excitation	
Monochromator	Multilayer monochromator, 8.4 keV

Detector	
Manufacturer	Bruker Nano GmbH
Type	Silicon drift detector, XFlash 660-PAR
Sensitive area	60 mm ² (standard)
Energy resolution	< 149 eV
Max. count rate	> 100 kcps output
Signal and control electronics	
Manufacturer	Bruker Nano GmbH
Type	XGS II
Beam path control	
Stage 1 - Tube	Travel: 270 mm
Stage 1 - Monochromator	Travel: 155 mm
Stage 1 - Detector	Travel: 155 mm
Stage 1 - Angle	Travel: +/- 5°
Sample changer	
Manufacturer	Cybertron GmbH
Type	Rack system with 10 tray positions Sample handling in XYZ direction by gripper arm LED status lights at every tray
Drive	3 servo drives
Sample capacity	90 discs (30 mm), 50 wafer (2"), 30 microscopy slides
Optical system	
Sample camera	CCD, 5 MPixel, USB
PC Workstation	
Manufacturer	Dell GmbH
Type	OptiPlex XE3
Processor	Intel Core i7-8700 3.20 GHz
Storage	32 GB RAM, 2 TB SATA hard disc
Operation System	Win 10 Pro, 64 Bit
Monitor	Dell 24", 1920 x 1200

4 Final Test Results

4.1 Detector FWHM

Pos.	Test parameter	Value	Unit
1	Sample	Mn	
2	Sample No.:	8778 21	
3	HV	50	kV
4	Current (I)	1000	μ A
5	Excitation	Mo-K	
6	Count Rate	18,887	kcps
7	Measure time	30	s
8	FWHM @ Mn-K	131,4	eV

4.2 Sensitivity and Detection limit Mo excitation

Pos.	Test parameter	Value	Unit
1	Sample amount	1	ng
2	Sample No.:	8243 21 8707 21	
3	HV	50	kV
4	Current (I)	1000	µA
5	Measuring time (t)	1000	S

Pos.	Measure Positions	Value	Unit
1	Stacker Axis X-	253,9	mm
2	Stacker Axis Y	22,43	mm
3	Stacker Axis Z	-4530	digits
4	Tube	0	digits
5	Monochromator	82061	digits
6	Detector	53263	digits
7	Angle	4740	digits

Pos.	Results	Value	Unit
1	Net area Ni (N _{Ni})	77472	counts
2	Background Ni (BG _{Ni})	613	counts

Sensitivity:

$$S_{Ni} = \frac{N_{Ni}}{T \cdot I \cdot 1ng}$$

Target value sensitivity (60 / 100 mm² SDD) > 40 / 50 counts ng⁻¹ mA⁻¹ s⁻¹

Measured value sensitivity: 77,68 counts ng⁻¹ mA⁻¹ s⁻¹

Detection limit:

$$LLD_{1ngNi} = 3 \cdot 1ng \cdot \frac{\sqrt{N_{BG}}}{N_{Ni}}$$

Target value LLD (60 / 100 mm²): < 2.0 pg

Measured value LLD: 0,96 pg

4.3 Sensitivity and Detection limit W-Brems excitation

Pos.	Test parameter	Value	Unit
1	Sample amount	3	ng
2	Sample No.:	8243-21 8707 21	
3	HV	50	kV
4	Current (I)	1000	μ A
5	Measuring time (t)	1000	s

Pos.	Measure Positions	Value	Unit
1	Stacker Axis X-	253,90	mm
2	Stacker Axis Y	22,31	mm
3	Stacker Axis Z	-4530	digits
4	Tube	65500	digits
5	Monochromator	9554	digits
6	Detector	53578	digits
7	Angle	4920	digits

Pos.	Results	Value	Unit
1	Net area Cd (N_{Cd})	953	counts
2	Background Cd (BG_{Cd})	85	counts

Target value sensitivity (60 / 100 mm² SDD) > 0.2 / 0.25 counts ng⁻¹ mA⁻¹ s⁻¹

Measured value sensitivity: 0,32 counts ng⁻¹ mA⁻¹ s⁻¹

Detection limit:

Target value LLD (60 / 100 mm²): < 200 / 170 pg

Measured value LLD: 87,07 pg

4.4 Nitrogen Gas Purge

Pos.	Test parameter	Value	Unit
1	Quartz disk, no sample		
2	HV	50	kV
3	Current	1000	µA
4	Measuring time	200	s
5	Argon peak without purge	3,210	counts
6	Argon peak with purge	0,385	counts
7	Ratio purge / no purge	0,1	0.06% Ar impurity from production gas supply
8	Required ratio	< 0.1	

4.5 Quantification (Mo excitation)

Pos.	Test parameter	Value	Unit
1	Sample Kraft 12	1	µl
2	HV	50	kV
3	Current	1000	µA
4	Measuring time	1000	s
5	Mean value of	3	samples

Kraft 12 Sample No.: 1. 8366 21 2. 6666 21 3. 8724 21				
Element	Certified values/ mg/l	Target mean values/ mg/l	Remarks	Measured values/ mg/l
Ti	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,962
V	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,942
Cr	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,976
Mn	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,953
Fe	1.00	0.90...1.10		1,027
Co	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,938
Ni	1.00	0.90...1.10	Set as internal standard	1,00
Cu	1.00	0.90...1.10		1,003
Zn	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,986
Rb	1.00	0.90...1.10		1,011

4.6 Quantification (W-Brems excitation)

Pos.	Test parameter	Value	Unit
1	Sample Kraft 12	1	µl
2	HV	50	kV
3	Current	1000	µA
4	Measuring time	1000	s
5	Mean value of	3	samples

Kraft 12 Sample No.: 1. 8366 21 2. 6666-21 3. 8724 21				
<i>8656</i>				
Element	Certified values/ mg/l	Target mean values/ mg/l	Remarks	Measured values/ mg/l
Ti	1.00	0.90...1.10	deconvolution only	
V	1.00	0.90...1.10	deconvolution only	
Cr	1.00	0.90...1.10	deconvolution only	
Mn	1.00	0.90...1.10	deconvolution only	
Fe	1.00	0.90...1.10	deconvolution only	
Co	1.00	0.90...1.10	deconvolution only	
Ni	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,960
Cu	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,975
Zn	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,965
Rb	1.00	0.90...1.10	Set as internal standard	1,00
Pd	1.00	0.90...1.10		0,92
Cd	1.00	0.90...1.10		1,09

5.4 Results

No.	Check	Test method	Result
1.	X-ray tube and sample are completely enclosed by the protective case	Visual test	OK
2.	Determine background radiation	Measure without radiation	<0.1 µSv/h
2.1	The local dose in a distance of 10 cm to the touchable surface does not exceed 1.0 µSv at 50 kV/600 µA, sample: quartz disc		
	Instrument	Thermo Electron Corporation ESM FH 40G-L10	
	Measuring point:	Surface	Distance 0.1 m
	door middle	<0.1 µSv/h	<0.1 µSv/h
	front, left side	<0.1 µSv/h	<0.1 µSv/h
	front, right side	<0.1 µSv/h	<0.1 µSv/h
	back side	<0.1 µSv/h	<0.1 µSv/h
	left side	<0.1 µSv/h	<0.1 µSv/h
	right side	<0.1 µSv/h	<0.1 µSv/h
	at the top	<0.1 µSv/h	<0.1 µSv/h
3.	By two from each other independent mechanisms it is guaranteed that		
3.1	a) Removal of the right side panel with HV on causes the immediate disconnection of the spectrometer from mains		OK
3.2	the radiation does not exceed 1 µSv/h with open door	Measuring point: at tray slit 1	<0.1 µSv/h

5.5 Overall results

The routine test of the S4 T•STAR has proven the compliance with the German X-ray regulations ("StrlSchV").

Tested by: **E. Muhl**

Department: Test Bay XRF

Date: 2022-09-02

Signature:

5 Radiation Protection Test Protocol

5.1 Record of Routine Test

Based on §20 of the German Radiation Protection Regulation ("StrlSchV")

5.2 Device components

Component	Type	Manufacturer	No.
Spectrometer	S4 T-STAR	Bruker Nano GmbH	4210 0078 0822
X-ray generator 1 Maximum operating values 50 kV, 1000 μ A, 50 W	MH60-503-06	HiTek Power Ltd.	2180086
X-ray generator 2 Maximum operating values 50 kV, 1000 μ A, 50 W	MH60-503-06	HiTek Power Ltd.	2180085
X-ray tube 1, (Mo-anode) Maximum operating values 50 kV, 1000 μ A, 50 W	ixtube-Mo-50	incoatec GmbH	2003215
X-ray tube 2, (W-anode) Maximum operating values 50 kV, 1000 μ A, 50 W	ixtube-W-50	incoatec GmbH	2003058

5.3 Test conditions

1	Excitation	50 kV, 1000 μ A, W anode 50 kV, 1000 μ A, Mo anode System in "Mo-17.5 keV" measurement position
2	Sample	Gain standard
3	Meas. device	Thermo Electron Corporation ESM FH 40G-L10

6 Declaration of Conformity

EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY

Product name: S4 T-STAR
Product type: S4 T-STAR 200, 400, 800
Manufacturer: Bruker Nano GmbH
Am Studio 2D
D-12489 Berlin
Germany

The designated product conforms to the provisions of the following European Council Directives on the approximation of the laws of the member states.

The conformity of the designated product to the provisions of the directive is attested by full compliance with the following harmonized European directives:

2014/35/EU: Directive relating to electrical equipment designed for use within voltage limits.
Used standard: **EN 61010-1:2010**

2014/30/EU: Directive relating to electromagnetic compatibility
Used standard: **EN 61326-1:2013**

2011/65/EU: Directive on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment (**RoHS**).

Affixing of the CE mark: 2017

Bruker Nano GmbH
Berlin, September 2017

T. Schülein, CEO
Name, function

Signature

Bruker Nano GmbH
Am Studio 2D
12489 Berlin - Germany

7 Document History

No.	Änderung / Kommentar	Author	Date
1.0.	Revision	Dr. A. Gross	September 2017
1.1.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Add actual configuration (chapter 2 and chapter 3)- Remove Chapter "Accompanying documents"- Updated measurement conditions at chapter 4- Updating Measurement devices at chapter 5	C. Moeller Dr. A. Gross	July 2018
1.2	- Add Tables for "Measure Positions" in Chapter 4	C. Moeller	September 2018
1.3	Add Sample Identifications Numbers in Chapter 4	C. Moeller	August 2019

PUBLICATIONS

PUBLICATIONS

PUBLICATIONS RELATED TO THIS THESIS

Revel, M., van Drimmelen, C. K. E., Mišíková, F., Padilla Suarez, E. G., Hursthouse, A. S., and Heise, S. (submitted) 'Toxicity and biodistribution of La and Gd in *Daphnia magna* following chronic dietary and waterborne exposure', *Ecotoxicology and Environmental safety*, October 2023

van Drimmelen, C. K. E., Revel, M., Hursthouse, A. S., and Heise, S. (submitted) 'Does Phosphate Mask the Toxicity of Two REE for Different Microalgae Species?', *Ecotoxicology and Environmental safety*, November 2023

Revel, M., van Drimmelen, C. K. E., Weltje, L., Hursthouse, A. S., and Heise, S. (submitted) 'Effects of Rare Earth Elements in the Aquatic Environment - Implications for Ecotoxicological Testing', *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*, December 2023

Gjata, I., van Drimmelen, C. K. E., Tomassi, F., Paciolla, C., and Heise S. (2024) 'Impact of Rare Earth Elements in sediment on the growth and photosynthetic efficiency of the benthic plant *Myriophyllum aquaticum*' *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-024-03867-x>

CONFERENCE CONTRIBUTIONS

van Drimmelen, C. K. E., Revel, M., Hursthouse, A. S., and Heise, S. (2021) 'The Chronic impact of REE on biological species in the benthic-pelagic food web'. *2nd International Conference on Contaminated Sediments*, pp 35.

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